

Publications Based on this Work

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The overall purpose of this research project is to study and explore the potential and limitations of the distributional approach with respect to lexical semantics.

The term “*distributional semantic*” is used to define a whole family of computational methods based on the assumption that the statistical distribution of words in contexts plays a key role in characterizing their semantic behavior. This assumption is founded on the *distributional hypothesis*, which assumes as fundamental for the exploration of the semantic space of a word, the ways in which it is combined with other words. The lexicon is then perceived as a metric space in which the words are separated by distances which depend on their degree of semantic similarity, measured through the statistical distribution of co-occurrences in texts. The principle upon which the *distributional hypothesis* is built is that two words are all the more semantically similar as they tend to occur in similar contexts (Miller and Charles [1991]).

The hypothesis that the statistical co-occurrence of words extracted from text corpora could provide a basis for their semantic representation has recently gained increasing attention, both in computational linguistics and in cognitive sciences. Terms like “*distributional*”, “*corpus-based*” and “*statistical*” are used almost interchangeably to define a family of approaches to semantics that share a “use-based” perspective to the meaning, which states that the statistical distribution of words in contexts helps defining their semantic behavior.

Semantic distributional models thus represent the meaning of words and measure the distributional similarity between words, based on the assumption that the proximity in distributional space could model semantics similarity. Distributional Semantics is basically founded on the well-known words of the English linguist Firth [1957]: “You shall know a word by the company it keeps”. On the cognitive level, this corresponds to a model of the mental lexicon in which meanings are represented according to contextual representations, as described by Charles [2000]: “an abstraction of information in the set of natural linguistic context in which a word occurs.”

However, there are many differences in the adopted mathematical and computational

techniques, in the type of semantic properties associated with text distribution and in the different definition of linguistic contexts used to determine the combinatorial spaces of lexical elements. At a closer look, it is possible to observe that the common properties could be many more than one would expect at first glance, and that there is a general pattern of meaning that can be closed off over all the differences, a model that makes specific assumptions regarding the specific format of semantic representations, of how they are constructed and processed by the human mind. Several methods for the computational analysis of the distributional properties of words have been developed, both in computational linguistics and in psychology; in the last decades many measures to compute similarity based on lexical distribution have also been investigated and developed.

Given the distributional hypothesis, it is possible to apply computational methods to texts, in order to dynamically acquire semantic properties through the mathematical processing of word distributions in texts. Despite all the basic assumptions described above, semantically related words could differ for the possible relations that exists between them.

The purpose of this work is to carry out a study about current state of the art distributional measures developed for the recognition of paradigmatic semantic relations, such as *synonymy*, *antonymy*, *hypernymy*, *hyponymy* and *co-hyponymy*, that greatly differ for their inferential properties. The purpose of this study is that of trying to assess the degree of success reported by such measures. Indeed, we would like to understand if distributional methods can actually be effective in recognizing and classifying paradigmatic semantic relations. We also want to verify if there is room for improvement in the techniques currently in use for the recognition of this type of relations.

Data gathered from the analysis described above could then be used in order to achieve the main goal of this research work: improve distributional semantic models to recognize and correctly classify different types of paradigmatic semantic relations.

Paradigmatic relations (*synonymy*, *antonymy*, *hypernymy/hyponymy*, *meronymy*) refer to words that belong to the same semantic field, that is, words that have similar meaning, opposite meaning, a meaning that could be more general or more specific with respect to a certain word and that can then be used in substitution to that very same word, depending on the context, the interlocutor or the aim of the undergoing communication: *happy/cheerful* (synonymy), *nice/bad* (antonym), *flower/violet* (hypernymy), *finger/hand* (meronymy).

Analyzing paradigmatic relations while using distributional methods could be very interesting and really challenging, for various reasons. First of all, state of the art semantic distributional methods have difficulties in distinguishing these relations. This is because these relations tend to distribute, within the texts, in a very similar way. To this regard, a sentence like “the *boy/girl/person* loves/hates her cat” shows how the (co) hyponyms *boy/girl*, referring to the same hypernym *person*, as well as antonyms *love/hate* might be used, respectively, in identical contexts. In particular, examining the

distributional characteristics of the paradigmatic relations, it is possible to notice that words pertaining to the *hyponymy/hypernymy* relation and *antonymy* relation in particular, raise many difficulties to be extracted and classified using distributional methods.

The *hypernymy/hyponymy* relation, for example, can not be recognized using these methods because of its being inherently asymmetric. Let's consider, for example, the pair of words *animal-dog*, related by the hypernymy relation; we can assume that, if it is true that being *dog* entails being an *animal*, being an *animal* will not be necessarily entail being a *dog*, since *animal* is a broader term, that includes *dog* and a lot of other concepts.

State of the art measures commonly used for distributional semantics tasks, simply measure the distance between words, which is a symmetrical relation: if a word, **A**, is close to a world **B** in the semantic space, this implies that **B** is close to **A** too. State of the art models then fail to characterize the different semantic properties of paradigmatic relations.

The antonymy relation, instead, raises interesting questions as it tends to distribute itself in the texts in the exact same manner of the synonymy relation. This makes it, in fact, extremely difficult to discriminate between the two using Distributional Semantics Methods. Given the obvious difficulties and peculiarities of the hyponymy/hypernymy relation and of the antonymy relation, we decided to focus our works on the study of these two relations.

On the practical side, the goal is to contribute to the creation of computational models functional for the recognition and classification (as well as of their discrimination with respect to other semantic relations) of the hyponymy and antonymy relations. The main difficulty to face, in fact, is that of developing a 'distributional measure' which is fine-tuned to classify these relations and is able to discriminate them with respect to other semantic relations.

In order to achieve our goals, we first carried out an analysis of the state of the art both in computational linguistics and in lexical semantics, with regard to the representation and modeling of the semantic relations under investigation. This is helpful in defining the procedures for selecting the data sets for the development of appropriate computational algorithms and for the evaluation of the developed models.

After this review, the project will focus on the actual development and testing of distributional semantics models.

Taking into account the basic assumption underlying these models, that is the fact that the proximity in distributional space correlates with semantic similarity or relatedness, we assume that it will be possible to compute the correlation between a pair of words and a semantic relation (that is, we assume we will be able to determine the semantic relation that binds a pair of words), while computing how distributionally similar they are (how similar the contexts in which the relation tends to occur in texts are to those in which the words tend to occur).

As already explained, we need to model the peculiarities of the two relations under examination with distributional models, so that they can be adjusted for the identification and classification of *hypernymy/hyponymy* and *antonymy*.

Once the models are developed, they will be tested in order to properly evaluate their performance in the identification of the target semantic relations.

This work is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** will outline a brief description of the linguistic and cognitive properties of semantic relations. It would particularly focus on the two paradigmatic relations we are going to deal with in this work: *hyponymy/hypernymy* and *antonymy*.
- **Chapter 3** will provide an introductory description of Distributional Models, together with the description of the mathematical models used to implement them.
- **Chapter 4** will briefly outline Relation Extraction state of the art models.
- **Chapter 5** and **Chapter 6** will describe the experiments we performed and analyze their results.

Chapter 2

Lexical Relations

2.1 Paradigmatic Relations

Most of the theoretical approaches to paradigmatic relations have their origins in different structuralist linguistic traditions. Given the variety of structuralist traditions and the vagueness of the word structural, there is a certain amount of polisemy in the term structural semantics. Coseriu and Geckeler [1981] identify three general meanings for this term.

The first meaning refers to an interest in the structure of the lexicon, based on association of similarity and contiguity. That is, the association of words with other words that go with them, either semantically, syntactically or morphologically. This theory can be called associative semantics, and its origins can be assigned to Saussure and his followers. The second meaning of structural semantics refers to the relations among the meaning of a single word (with particular interest in polysemy and homophony). The third meaning is what Coseriu and Geckeler [1981] called “structural in its analytical respect”. This definition regards the organization of the vocabulary based on contrastive relations. This form of structural semantics has been called analytical because it conducts to the componential analysis of word meanings.

Saussure [1959] assumed the study of relations to be central to the study of language, since in order to be meaningful, words must be related one another, such that the word becomes “the point of convergence of an indefinite number of coordinated items”. Saussure’s associative relations were not limited by any fixed number of types, nor did he distinguish between semantic relations and other types of relations.

Bally, one of Saussure’s disciple, limited his field of interest to semantic association between words, in the form of *association fields*. A word’s *associative field* is then seen as a “halo” radiating and dissipating from the word itself. Linguistic interest in *association fields* was limited to French-speaking linguists, even though echoes of this theory are present in many approaches that will be discussed later. *Associative fields* are entirely unconstrained in the type of relations that they may incorporate. Paradigmatic

relations may be a part of an *associative field*, as well as syntagmatic and idiosyncratic associations.

The more analytic distance from the associative approach was promoted in the movement of the Neo-Humboldtian Ethnolinguistics. The approach they promoted is called *cognitive-anthropological*, given that it is concerned with the middle ground between thought and reality. Researchers following this tradition compared lexicalization patterns across languages in order to hypothesize culturally proper conceptualizations of the world based on the culture's proper lexical structure. The Neo-Humboldtian tradition further developed the notion of lexical fields, particularly with Trier [1931, 1934]. Unlike Trier, Weisgerber [1963] emphasized the Humboldtian notion of *linguistic relativity* (i.e. language influencing thought). This particular point of view was ignored by later theorists.

Lexical semantics has developed and prospered in England, where a strong tradition in lexicography and the influence of the London school of linguistics made interest in words flourish. This tradition is better exemplified by Lyons [1977] and Cruse [1986]. For both of them paradigmatic relations are central to the study of meaning. Cruse named his approach *contextualist*, in relation to the Firthian notion of meaning in which a word's meaning can "be known by the company it keeps" (Cruse [1986], adapted from Firth [1957]). Cruse then states that "the semantic properties of a lexical item are reflected in appropriated aspects of the relations it contracts with actual and potential contexts" ¹.

The Prague school supplied the notion of markedness, first referring it to phonology, then applying it to semantics too (initially in Jakobson [1931]). The issue of semantic markedness is particularly relevant to antonymy, so it will be examined in depth later. Anyway, the vocabulary to talk about markedness relations among meanings is borrowed by Trubetzkoy [1969]'s one for oppositions among phonemes. Coseriu and Geckeler [1981] describe privative, gradual and equipollent oppositions among meanings. The influence of the Prague school can also be seen in the development of semantic features for the componential analysis of word meanings.

In the American linguistic tradition, the study of lexical semantics was not really scrutinized until recently. Following Bloomfield's studies, American structuralism discouraged the study of meanings, given that "the linguist cannot define meanings, and must appeal for this to other sciences" (Bloomfield [1936]). The generativist school had waxed and waned interest in the lexicon, but one of the most interesting and influential approaches has been that of lexical decomposition: identifying sub-lexical semantic components that combine to form lexical relations (e.g. Katz and Fodor [1963], according to whom part of the lexical representation of a word is a set of semantic features based on semantic primitives). Unlike the associative-structural view, in which the relations are taken as primary, in componential approaches paradigmatic relations are seen as entailed by lexical semantic structures.

¹All these theories will be further explained in the chapter concerning Distributional Models

Generativism marked a shift in interest from language as a cultural phenomenon, to language as a mental phenomenon. Frame semantics (Fillmore [1976, 1985]) has followed the footsteps of semantic field theory, but adopted the notion of frames from artificial intelligence. It is a cognitivist approach to the lexicon, looking for *non-linguistic* cognitive explanations for linguistic phenomena.

Interest in lexical relations takes many forms in computer science, which should not be surprising, since the lexicon is “the central component of natural language processing” (Handke [1995]). Computational semantic networks are valuable for many practical NLP (Natural Language Processing) tasks, such as word-sense disambiguation (that means finding the appropriate sense of a word by noting its relation to other words in a text), search engines (relations are used to recognize the appropriate conceptual fields for a query) and lexical databases. A semantic network is a prepositional knowledge structure consisting of a set of nodes that are selectively connected to each other by links labeled by the relation between each pair of connected nodes (Fahlman [1979], Quillian [1966]). Links in such networks may assert category membership or a part-to-whole property. These can be described as *is-(a)* and *has-(a)* relations (as in “a trout *is a* fish” and “a trout *has* gills”). Many other kinds of relations among nodes may also be represented by labeled links. For example a link could represent the *is made of* concept, as in “a crowbar *is made of* steel”. Computer implementations of semantic networks were first developed for artificial intelligence and machine translation, but earlier versions have long been used in philosophy, psychology, and linguistics. What is common to all semantic networks is a declarative graphic representation that can be used to represent knowledge and support automated systems for reasoning about the knowledge.

One issue that arises in reviewing this kind of models is the extent to which they can serve as models of the human mental lexicon. Some differences between computer and human systems relate to the fact that NLP systems are generally built for inferential competence but not referential competence. So, we might be interested in letting the computer know that *cats* are *animals*, and *animals* are *concrete objects*, but less interested in making a computer system skilled to recognize and label actual *cats*. A computer usually interacts with the world through language input and not direct experience, so it might be more economical for semantic knowledge to be represented as lexical knowledge, rather than trying to maintain the linguistic division required for a model of human cognition. Computational linguists have become more aware of the need to incorporate world knowledge in the interpretation of language, computational lexicons tend to be heavier in semantic content than the mental lexicons of theoretical linguistics, which have been increasingly treated as semantically empty. Given that this work focuses on relations among words, semantic network models are of most interest here.

The history of semantic network usually starts from Quillian [1966]’s work. Networks were already used in machine translation, but Quillian’s work made innovative

FIGURE 2.1: Quillian's semantic network

use of techniques such as spreading activation and parallel processing. Semantic networks, in Quillian's work, consist of nodes on a plane (with each plane representing a word-concept), connected by uni-directional associative links. Two kinds of nodes are involved here: a type node, which represents a single sense of a word and can recur in token nodes, which are the "building blocks" of a type node's sense. Within planes, relations between nodes include a type-to-token subclass relation, and token-to-token relation: modification, disjunction and conjunction, subject and object. Between planes, token nodes are linked back to the type node which represents the same word sense. Figure 2.1 shows the planes for COMFORT and CRY and their relation to the type node SAD. It illustrates how word senses, represented as token nodes, can serve as elements of other word senses, while being related to other meanings through the relation of the token nodes to their associated type node.

Types are never directly related in this model of semantic memory, types only indirectly relate to each other through a series of type-token and token-type relations. The relation between DOG and ANIMAL in such network is not a relation of the concepts, but the inclusion of a token instance of ANIMAL on the plane of the DOG type node. So, while ANIMAL participates in DOG's semantic representation, we cannot say that hyponymy is represented here. Hyponymy can, instead, be computed on the basis of the interrelation of the two types.

Those networks embody an associationist approach to meaning (meaning that any concept is part of a greater system of concepts and can be understood as a part of that system). For example, *buy* and *sell* might be represented by a single concept, but the word's meaning linking to that concept would be showing different perspectives on that single event. Figure 2.1 does not represent a network of words, it is a network of concepts (which obviously must be represented using words). Thus, the semantic network does not determine relations among words, but provides the necessary semantic information to which words map and the semantic bases for computing relations among words.

An innovation in the later works on semantic networks is the acquired distance from human-performed linguistic analysis, in order to determine the semantic knowledge to

be represented in the network.

Componential approaches to meaning do not discuss the nature of paradigmatic relations, but assume the nature of feature-inheritance system to allow the derivation of such relations. The relation among hyperonyms and hyponyms is one of the most investigated relations using computational approaches, since the superordinate category is considered to be the “most accessible property of a concept” (Collins and Quillian [1972]). Since we are talking about conceptual relations (relations among meanings) rather than relations among words, the prominence of taxonomic relations reflects the computational interest in representing declarative semantic knowledge and the usual bias towards studying concrete noun meanings, which more likely occur in hyponymy/hypernymy relations than the concepts associated with verbs or adjectives. Similarity relations (synonymy and near-synonymy) have received attention in NLP, partly due to the problem of building natural language systems able to choose appropriately between near-synonyms like “potential” and “possible”.

Semantic networks typically show positive relations between items, such as IS-LIKE or HAS-A, but rarely involve oppositional relation such as IS-NOT.

The main NLP resource which fully implements the concept of *semantic network* is WordNet (Fellbaum [1998]). WordNet is an online lexical database and its structure makes it a useful tool for computational linguistics and natural language processing. WordNet groups words together based on their meanings; in particular nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs (but not prepositions, determiners and other function words) are organized into sets of synonyms, called synsets, each representing a distinct concept. Synsets include simplex words as well as collocations like “*eat out*” and “*car pool*” . The different senses of a polysemous word form are assigned to different synsets.

WordNet can thus be seen as a combination of dictionary and thesaurus. It interlinks both word forms (i.e., strings of letters) and specific senses of words (synset), by means of a small number of relations:

- *Synonymy* is WordNet’s basic relation, since WordNet uses synsets to represent word senses. Synonymy is a symmetric relation between word forms.
 - An example adjective synset is:
good, right, ripe (most suitable or right for a particular purpose; “a good time to plant tomatoes”; “the right time to act”; “the time is ripe for great sociological changes”)
- *Antonymy* (opposing-name) is also a symmetric semantic relation between word forms, especially important in organizing the meanings of adjectives and adverbs. Pairs of “direct” antonyms reflect the strong semantic contract of their members.
 - *Wet* is an antonym of *dry*
 - *Young* is an antonym of *old*

- *Hypernymy* (super-name), and its inverse *Hyponymy* (sub-name) are transitive relations between synsets. Because there is usually only one hypernym, this semantic relation organizes the meanings of nouns into a hierarchical structure.
 - *Canine* is a hypernym of *dog*
 - *To perceive* is a hypernym of *to listen*
 - *Dog* is hyponym of *canine*
- *Meronymy* (part-name) and its inverse, *holonymy* (whole-name), are complex semantic relations. WordNet distinguishes component parts, substantive parts, and member parts.
 - *Brim* is a component part of *hat*
 - *Gin* is substance meronym of *martini*
 - A *ship* is a member part of a *fleet*
- *Troponymy* (manner-name) a verb (*Y*) is a troponymy of another one (*X*) if the activity *Y* implies doing *X* in some manner
 - *To lisp* is a troponymy of *to talk*
- Entailment relations between verbs are also coded in WordNet .
 - *To snore* entails *to sleep*

Additionally, a synset contains a brief definition (“gloss” and, in most cases, one or more short sentences illustrating the use of the synset members. Word forms with several distinct meanings are represented in as many distinct synsets, as it can be seen in Figure 2.2. Thus, each form-meaning pair in WordNet is unique.

WordNet has been used for a number of different purposes in information systems, including word sense disambiguation, information retrieval, automatic text classification, automatic text summarization, machine translation and even automatic crossword puzzle generation.

A common use of WordNet is to determine the similarity between words. Various algorithms have been proposed, and these include measuring the distance among the words and synsets in WordNet’s graph structure, such as by counting the number of edges among synsets. The intuition is that the closer two words or synsets are, the closer their meaning.

The pragmatic and psycholinguistics perspective is concerned with the relationship between competence and performance. The study of these relations revolve around determining what should be known in order to know how to do something and what are the results from having done this something. For example, knowing that two words are

administration#2 (#2 means the second sense of the word in Wordnet)	
"governing body who administers something"	
Synset: (administration, governance, establishment, brass, organization, organisation)	
Gloss: 2. administration, governance, establishment, brass, organization , organisation -- (the persons (or committees or departments etc.) who make up a governing body and who administer something; "he claims that the present administration is corrupt"; "the governance of an association is responsible to its members"; "he quickly became recognized as a member of the establishment").	
Hyponyms	Hypernyms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ executive - (persons who administer the law) → judiciary, bench - (persons who administer justice) → management - (those in charge of running a business) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → body - (a group of persons associated by some common tie or occupation and regarded as an entity; "the whole body filed out of the auditorium") ▶ gathering, assemblage - (a group of persons together in one place) ▶ social group - (people sharing some social relation) → group, grouping - (any number of entities (members) considered as a unit).

FIGURE 2.2: Example of the WordNet entry for *administration*

synonyms or antonyms might be a mentally fixed property. If so, we could either know them because of innately programmed knowledge, or because we learned that those two words are related and we added such information to our mental representation of them. Thus, having an innate mental representation of every relation for every language is almost impossible, given the infinite number of possible languages.

So, we may know the relation because we learned it as a fact, the very same way we learn other facts such as the pronunciation of a word. For example, one might know that *hot* and *cold* are antonyms because of them being always used in contrast, this information becoming part of one's mental representation of these words.

Semantic relations could be instead generated. In this case, knowing that two words are antonyms implies that a generated mental representation based on rules exists; so the knowledge of *hot* and *cold* being antonyms is something that is generated every time the need arises.

Neither of these theories, alone, is sufficient to explain our linguistic performance, with respect to semantic relations.

All semantic relations among words can be generated using a single relational principle, this does not mean that such relations should be generated every time they're needed.

There are different approaches in studying those kind of relations, each of them having its limitations. Corpus studies frequently over-rely on written forms, assuming that the form of a lexeme is graphic rather than phonemic. Dictionaries reflect conscious reasoning about language but usually have a commercial mission which interferes with the contingent descriptive usefulness. Computational and neurological studies often fail to distinguish between linguistic and non-linguistic knowledge, using words to represent concepts.

In literature, paradigmatic semantic relations are often called semantic relations or lexical relations, those two terms sometimes being used contrastively. The common element, relation, is vague, but it describes co-membership in a definable set, together with the types of criteria used to define such a set.

In our case, relation mean paradigmatic relation, that is relations in which every set of words forms a paradigm of some sort, as a semantic paradigm that contains members of the same grammatical category (i.e. names or adjectives) that share some semantic characteristics but fail to share others.

Paradigmatically related words can be substitutable one for another. For example, each member of the color paradigm (*blue*, *red* and such) can occur in the same spot in the same sentence. This way, paradigmatic relations stand in contrast to syntagmatic relations (relations between words that go together in a syntactic structure - such as *eat* and *dinner*). While paradigmatic relation holds between members of the same grammatical category, syntagmatic relations involve members of different grammatical categories.

The main types of paradigmatic relation are:

- **synonymy**: *sofa=couch=davenport* (the equal = sign is used to represent synonymy)
- **antonymy**: *good/bad, life/death* (the slash / sign implies the semantic incompatibility of contrasting words)
- **contrast**: *sweet/sour/bitter/salty*
- **hyponymy**: or class inclusion *cat<mammal<animal*
- **meronymy**: or the part-whole relation as in *line<stanza<poem* (the less than sign here means that such relations are hierarchical and asymmetrical).

Antonymy is a subtype of contrast, being a contrast with binary paradigm.

As already said, the hyponymy and the meronymy relations are asymmetrical. For example, *cat*, does not have the same relation to *mammal* (*cat<mammal*) as *mammal* has to *cat* (*mammal>cat*). In one direction, this represents the relation between a category and its superordinate, while in the other it represents the relation between a category and its subordinate. On the other hand, synonymy and antonymy are non-hierarchical relations, usually characterized as symmetric relations; for example the relation between *couch* and *sofa* is not distinguishable from the one that undergoes between *sofa* and *couch*. So, it possible to say that *couch* and *sofa* are synonyms of each other, while it is not possible to say that *cat* and *mammal* are hyponyms of each other. *Cat* is a hyponym of *mammal*, while *mammal* is a hypernym of *cat*. Meronymy too is a unidirectional relation, so that *stanza* is a meronym of *poem*, and *poem* is the holonym of *stanza*. [Lyons](#)

[1977] discuss co-hyponymy, but this relation could just as well be considered a contrast set. This way *cat/dog/horse* is considered a contrast set or co-hyponym of *animal*.

Most lexical semantic theories assert that relations are not really relations among words, but relations among word senses.²

2.2 Properties of Semantic Relations

A unified approach to the different semantic relation types seems elusive, since all of them (and instances of a relation between the very same type) have different characteristics, such as:

- **Productivity:** New relational links among words can be generated.
- **Binarity:** Some relations relate pairs of words, even though *larger* set of words may be semantically available for the relation.
- **Variability:** Words to which another word is related to vary according to the sense of the words that is used and the context it is used.
- **Prototypicality:** There are word sets that represent a relation better than others, and there are words sets (especially antonyms) that seem to have a special status as canonical example of a relation.
- **Semi-semanticity:** Semantic properties of words are not the only factors at work in relating words and judging semantic relations.
- **Uncountability:** The number of semantic relations types is not determinable in a objective way.
- **Predictability:** Relations among words comply to general patterns, thus indicating that semantic relations are rule governed.
- **Universality:** The same semantic relations can be relevant for describing any language.

2.2.1 Productivity

If semantic relations are generated using rules, the fact that two words are related should not be included as arbitrary information in the lexicon. A tangible clue of the fact that relations are rule generated is the fact that relations are productive, in fact new instances

²Some of these texts call such relations sense relations (as in Lyons [1977]) or meaning relations (Keith [2014]) instead of lexical relations.

of the relations can be produced at any time. If it's possible to create new instances of synonymy or antonymy, there must be a mechanism that predicts that certain words can be related, instead of a fixed mental lexicon containing records of any word possible relative.

We can clearly observe the productivity of synonymy. If a new word, that represents to some extent the same thing an already existing word represents, is invented it means that the new word becomes automatically a synonym for the older word.

For example, every time we introduce a new slang term for the word *automobile*, a synonymy relation is predicted for the new slang term and all the standard and slang terms already existing. The new word does not need to be added as a member of the synonymy set (i.e. it does not need to be specified that the new word has the same meaning of the original word) in order for the synonym relation to be understood. What happens is, the new word is used and understood to mean the same as the old one.

Thinking about antonymy, oppositional morphology allows the creation of new antonyms from existing words. The verbal prefixes *dis-* and *de-*, for example, are used to create new reversionary antonyms in English. Murphy [2003] cites the following sentences as example of this phenomenon:

- (1) a. Increased sophistication in analyzing biochemical and manipulating genetic stocks allowed bioscientists to “**disendanger**” species. (“Putting the ‘servant’ back in ‘public servant,’ ” *The Manoa Journal of Fried and Half-Fried Ideas* 4, 1994)
- b. o determine exactly how much feed to use we need to **defuzzify** the rules. (Fuzzy Expert System Tutorial, <http://ag.arizona.edu/AREC/>)

The same way, the prefix *un-* allows for productivity in antonymy making standard form adjectives. Again, Murphy [2003] provides an interest example of this:

- (2) Spawn is the work of an **unheavenly** creator (J.Seavor in *Providence Journal*, 1 August 1997)

Anyway, the productivity of these prefixes is not unlimited.

Adjectival *un-* is semantically restricted, while the prefix *non-* is completely productive; this allows any noun or adjective to have an antonym. Antonyms created with the apposition of the prefix *non-* are more akin to phrasal negation than other cases of lexical opposition, since it does not contrast two properties of an object, but rather just a property and its absence.

Morphology provides means for making new antonyms from existing words, anyway the morphemes and morphological processes could be not entirely productive, or not representative of all the varieties of semantic opposition described by the term antonyms (as we will see in depth in the following section of this chapter). Because of its binary nature, antonymy seems less productive than synonymy.

One word's sense can have two easily recognized (canonical) antonyms, like, for example *happy/sad* or *happy/unhappy*. The productivity of antonymy could be better seen while analyzing words that do not have canonical antonyms. The color red, for example, could have different antonyms according to the different domain we are talking about. While discussing *wine*, for example, the opposite of *red* is *white*. While talking about *pigments*, the opposite of *red* (as in the color, red) can be *green* or *blue*.

A theory of semantic relations must account for the fact that we can recognize or propose words that are semantically related even though we may not have experienced such words occurring in relations.

2.2.2 Binariness

A theory of semantic relations must account for the fact that antonymy is binary, while other relations (like, for example, synonymy or co-hyponymy) are not, since they cannot limit the number of items that are related.

One approach to binariness in antonymy would hold that antonymy arises where words are in complementary, contrary or converse relation, which are necessarily binary. A couple like *dead/alive*, represents complementarity (since not being in one state entails being in the other), *hot/cold* are contrary (since they are collocated at the opposites extreme of a scale) and *buy/sell* are converse (if X buys from Y, Y sell to X). Contrary sets are not necessarily binary, given that some semantics fields include more than two extremes. Within these larger sets, there are some canonical binary pairs, but binariness arises when it is not logically necessary. Contrast sets (defined as mutually exclusive - while usually jointly exhaustive - sets of terms that are organized under an inclusive covering term) do not always include privileged pairs. So, outside from a particular context, one would be hard pressed to find a particular antonymy. A theory of semantic relations should then be able to say something about the privileged position of binary pairs in some contrastive contexts instead of others.

2.2.3 Variability

Despite of the canonical examples of antonymy noted here, the antonym (or synonym etc.) of any words can vary according to context. Since words are polysemous, different senses for the very same word may require different synonyms or antonyms.

Murphy and Andrew [1993], provided experimental evidence that people recognize different antonyms for adjectives given the different names that the adjectives modify. For instance, the antonym sense of *fresh* in *fresh bread* is different from that in *fresh shirt*. Since the polisemy of words is limitless, the full array of word senses cannot be intralexically represented. This means that the number of possible antonyms, synonyms, hyperonyms for a single word is also potentially limitless, so relations cannot be represented in the lexicon.

If we look at a single sense of a word, its antonyms (or contrast sets) can vary by context. For example, the sense of *blue* is the same wherever it acts as a simple color descriptor. Depending on context, though, other colors may contrast with it. If talking about photographic positives and negatives, the opposite of *blue* is *orange*. If the context is the color of the sky, *blue* can be opposite of *gray*.

A theory of semantic relations must be sensitive to the variability of any word's relation to other words. Semantic relations vary, not only by word sense, but also by context, regardless of sense variations.

2.2.4 Prototypicality and Canonicity

Semantic relations are variable, so some word pairs seem to be “better” examples of relations than others, thus indicating prototypicality effects for semantic relatedness (Cruse [1994]).

Prototypicality judgments are not limited to judging which words is the closest relative of another. Prototypicality is also used in judging sets of words against each other, as examples of the relation under examination. So, *hot* is not only considered the best antonym for *cold*, but the pair *hot/cold*, is perceived as a better antonym pair than, for example, *cruel/kind*. This effect can be observed while asking people for examples of antonymy, since they would often provide couples like *good/bad* or *big/little*. Still, even among the canonical or non-canonical antonyms, some pairs are perceived as more prototypical than other.

Herrmann et al. [1986] asked subjects to rate the antonymy degree of word pairs using a scale that goes from one to five. The average reported score was 4.60 for all the proposed couples, indicating that subjects agreed on the fact that the couples under examination were all highly antonymous. Anyway, the average scores vary, so that some canonical examples were judged more antonymous than others, as well as some *non*-canonical antonyms were judged more antonymous than other. Although being both canonical pairs, *love/hate* was judged a better case of antonymy than *big/little*. Anyway, displaying a high degree of antonymy, does not mean being a canonical antonym.

An antonymy canon seems to exist, and we are expected to know it as speakers of a language. We may learn the canon by explicit teaching, but a even more common source of information about canonical pairs is their co-occurrence in set phrases, like *cruel to be kind* and *different as night and day*. Those phrases favor the relation of two particular words, over all other possibilities (e.g. *kind/unkind* or *morning/night*). Canonicity can then be measured in terms of a pair's co-occurrence in natural language, where juxtaposition of semantically related terms occurs, both in set phrases and in creative language, as proved by corpus studies. Canonical antonyms co-occur at greater expected rates, as shown by Justeson and Katz [1991, 1992] with respect to pairs like *long/short* or *hot/cold*, as in the following examples (from the Brown Corpus):

- (3) a. He must work long hours in the **hot sun** or **cold rain**
b. The **pain** seems **short** and the **pleasure** is **long**

Canonical antonyms also co-occur far more often than similar non-canonical pairs. For example, [Charles and Miller \[1989\]](#) show that *big/little* and *large/small* occur together more than three times as often as *large/little* or *big/small* do.

Word association tasks show that some relations between words are automatic and constant across speakers, while others are not. In these experiments, subjects hear or read single-word stimuli and give an automatic one-word response. School-aged children and adults respond using words related to the stimulus in a paradigmatic way, mostly by antonymy, synonymy or hyponymy.

Evidence that some instantiation of relations are canonical is the fact that the less-common words elicit more syntagmatic responses than more-common ones. If learning canonical relations involves repeated exposure to the co-occurring words, than it would stand to reason that common antonymic words have greater chance of being “canonized”, than less common ones. Evidence of canonicity can also be retrieved in the fact that some antonym pairings are stable across word senses, while others are not. If we posit that each word sense has its own relation to synonyms and antonyms, we miss important generalizations for some words that have the same synonyms or antonyms for a number of senses. The color senses of *black* and *white* are opposed, just as their racial senses and their perceived ‘good’/‘evil’ senses as in *white magic* and *black magic*.

Canonicity of antonym relations also plays a role in context-specific antonymy. If a frequent or basic sense of a word is in a semantic relation with another word, such relation can be extended to other senses of that word. For example, [Lehrer \[2002\]](#) noted that the basic temperature sense of *hot* contrasts with *cold*. While *cold* does not usually mean ‘legally acquired’, it can have that meaning if contrasted (with enough context) with *hot* in its ‘stolen’ sense, as in the sentence “He traded in his *hot* car for a *cold* one” ([Lehrer \[2002\]](#)).

2.2.5 Semi-semanticity

Semantic properties of words are not the only properties to determine semantic relations, even if they are the most important ones. While looking for a word’s “closest” relatives, we often consider *non*-semantic properties of the words. For instance, a *non*-semantic factor for paradigmatic relations is the part of speech. Even if *happy* and *joy* denote two really similar emotional state, they could not be synonyms, since one is an adjective and the other one is a noun. This could lead to the assumption that semantic relations might relate lemmata (the syntactic and semantic portions of lexical entires) instead of the wordsense or full lexical entry (including information about the word form). However, while [Justeson and Katz \[1991\]](#) found out that canonical antonyms co-occur at greater than expected rates, [Fellbaum \[1995\]](#) found that morphologically related variants of such

forms also co-occur at greater than expected rates. So the definition of paradigmatic relation is stretched out in order to call the noun *dead* (as in *the dead*) and the verb *live* antonyms. Fellbaum's data show that these words are used contrastively, much like the pair *live/die*.

Semantic relatedness is the core requirement for semantic relations, so similarity of grammatical category is less central to these relations. While semantic properties are sufficient to explain some of the preferences for one antonym over another, the *non*-semantic factors may still play a role in making the words seem more similar. For example, *maximize/minimize* could be perceived as better antonyms than *hot/cold*, and this perception might not be based on purely semantic grounds. But *maximize/minimize* are alliterative, rhyming, parallel in their metrical structure, so these *non*-semantic aspects are the ones affecting the perception of how antonymous the pair is.

Sometimes semantic relations are applied to items without any reference to their semantic qualities. A theory of semantic relations must then explain why *non*-semantic factors play a role in semantic relations. Word relations need to have access to the form and grammatical properties of the words, together with their semantic properties.

2.2.6 Uncountability

There are a lot of approaches to semantic relations that have tried to define taxonomies of such relations. Lyons [1977] and Cruse [1986] provide taxonomies of opposition that divide equivalent sets of antonymic pairs into different numbers of types and subtypes.

Lyons defines four basic types: complementary (*masculine/feminine*), contrary (*small/large*), directional (*up/down*) and converse (*buy/sell*) and divides the directional type further into two subtypes: orthogonal (perpendicular: *north/east*) and antipodal (diametrical: *north/south*). On the other hand Cruse divides the same variety of relations into three basic types: contrary (*light/dark*), complementary (*hit/miss*) and directional (*male/female*) and divides these three into multiple subtypes: contraries have three subtypes and one sub-subtype, complementaries include three subtypes and directionals have four subtypes: antipodals (*top/bottom*), directions (*north/south*), counterparts (*male/female*) and reversives (*appear/disappear*).

Anyway there is no way of determining when the types have been reduced to a perfect taxonomy. Considering directional and converse antonymy as different types of relations, misses the generalization that they are both simple opposition. The difference between these relations is the types of words they oppose.

The number of ways in which two or more words can be semantically related is more than just what we had named so far (that would be antonymy, synonymy, hyponymy and meronymy). It is difficult to determine how many semantic relation types and subtype exist, and it is also difficult to determine the semantic relations linking any two words in a context-independent way. The same words are not always in the same relation. Some words may have meronymic and synonymic relation to each other (for example,

flower \geq *blossom*), this usually happens with near synonyms which can be used as antonyms in certain contexts. For example, the italicized pair in the following sentence is interpreted as opposites in virtue of their association with other opposites (in bold): “a rather clinical building which is **easy** to *respect* and **difficult** to *love*”

2.2.7 Predictability

Semantic relations are productive (since we can invent new pair of synonyms, antonyms, hyponyms and such). This means that language users have knowledge on how to recognize or devise relations among words.

Demonstrating productivity shows that semantic relations are not arbitrary, being rule-based. The fact that some semantically available antonym pairs are better than others had led some to propose that antonymy relations are not predictable. If so, this information must be represented in the words' lexical entries.

If it can be shown that differences between “good” and “not so good” antonym pairings are predictable, relational information does not need to be specified in the lexicon since the relations can be derived by a grammar of semantic relations.

It has been noted that antonymy can be defined in terms of minimal difference. To be perceived as minimally different, two words must share all the crucial semantic properties but one. In language use, a word used in a single sense may carry connotations that depend on its other conventional senses, or those senses may exist more on a continuum than as separate entities (Cruse [1986]; Taylor [2003]). Even when *big* and *large* are used to describe the size of three-dimensional object, *big* may communicate importance of some sort, in a way that *large* does not. For example, while talking about nicknames, *big* is favored because it indicates *large* size but also make some sort of affective contribution. We then might call the larger of two Johns in a group *Big John*, but it would not be the same to call him *Large John*. Referring to someone's size in a nickname is only socially acceptable if the used word carries connotation of importance. *Big* is then the only proper antonym for *little*, since they similarly occur in nicknames (*Little John*)(as thoroughly explained by Murphy [2003]).

Given that *big* and *large* are not equivalent (neither are *little* and *small*, for example) there is not a case of two synonyms taking different antonyms. Considering *non*-semantic factors in antonymy choice, Murphy and Andrew [1993], as well as Cruse [1994], point out that, while the basic size adjectives are similar in sense, they can still be different in register.

Considering both semantic and *non*-semantic factors, the preference for *large/small* over *large/little* is hardly idiosyncratic or arbitrary. Posing the basic definition according to which antonyms must be minimally different, we can rule out the possibility that *large/little* would be acceptable antonyms. Given that canonical antonym pairings are also predictable, we can wonder whether canonicity is really a property of semantic

relations. So are canonical pairs simply the most predictable? The two properties certainly interact, but canonicity describes the property of being learned through repeated encounters of the pairs, which is different from predictability.

2.2.8 Universality

Semantic relations are universal, at both the general and the particular level. On the general level, the same type of relations are available to speakers of any languages. On the particular level, the same concepts enter into the same semantic relations in different languages.

Many types of evidence show that speakers of different languages recognize (and use) the very same relations. Speakers across languages respond paradigmatically in free word-association tasks. In many cultures metalinguistic commentary or language play reveals awareness of these relations. In Australia, for example, Walbiri men use a ritual language that involves replacing words with their antonyms ([Postman and Keppel, 1970]). Many cultures invent synonyms in order to avoid taboo terms. Cross-linguistic experimentation has established that similar categories relations are recognized across cultures. Raybeck and Herrmann [1990] investigated relation recognition in speakers of various languages. In those experiments, subjects were asked to sort pairs of words into groups related in the same way. They looked for five relation types: opposite, similar, part-whole, representational (*map/city*) and categorical (cause-effect, as in *joke/laughter*). For the opposite category (which can overlap with the antonymy relation described here) people from all cultures agreed to three subtypes - contradiction, directional opposites and reverses. Subjects also agreed that object-proper part (*car/tire*) and object-stuff (*table/wood*) are similar relations fitting with the already given definition of meronymy. Speakers of different languages seem to have the same ideas regarding which meanings can stand with which relations. Word-association tests have shown similarities in the type of associations made by speakers of various languages.

Associations may differ across cultures, differences can often be attributed to lexical or cultural differences, rather than differences in the semantics of the different languages. Most typical antonym pairings occur cross-culturally (the opposite of the word for hot can be translated as *cold*), indicating that the meanings are primary in determining the relations. The relations are not arbitrary. We can then note that the more general types of relation are universal, and that the language-specific differences in the relational subtypes found in a semantic field do not entail the fact that different languages have different relations.

The above properties of semantic relations place constraints on a theory of semantic relations. First of all, semantic relations are productive, variable, predictable and universal, they do not constitute arbitrary information belonging to the lexicon. If they are not represented in the lexicon, nor they are relevant to the grammatical competence, they must be represented as *non-linguistic* knowledge. Secondly, given that they can

relate words, instead of just relating meanings, they are not just relations among the concepts represented by the words. Semantic relations must then be represented in the realm of *non*-linguistic knowledge, but they still constitute knowledge about language. Knowledge of semantic relations is a part of our metalinguistic knowledge about words in our language. Thirdly, semantic relations among words are productive, predictable and universal, so we must have some mental means for deriving semantic relations. They are not necessarily fixed in our mind but can be generated when needed. Fourthly, since some relational pairs are canonical, we must have means for storing some relations among words, and such fixed representation must not interfere with the generation of new relations involving the same words. Lastly, given that the number of semantic relation types is indeterminable, the principles involved in predicting semantic relatedness should be general and adaptable. It would be better to have a single principle that predicts all semantic relations.

If we consider words related by semantic relations as a group, we found them to have a lot in common. In each semantic relation, in fact, the related items are required to be very similar. In case of synonymy, for example, words are expected to be similar in meaning. Antonymy too, requires similarity of meaning (antonyms *up/down* describe directions in the same dimension). Hyponyms and meronyms are semantically similar to their hypernyms and holonyms in that each refers to a part of the larger thing. So, when we say that two things are related, we are saying they are similar, and thus similarity requirements must be central to any principle of semantic relatedness.

While the different types of semantic relations involve various types of difference among the relation set members, the relations as a group are the same in the amount of difference required within the relational sets. In each of these cases, the members of the relational set can be said to be minimally different, that is, for the purpose of semantic relations, the words involved should only differ on one relevant criterion. For synonymy, the relevant difference is form; for hypernymy it is level of categorization. If two words differ on more than one of these levels, they are not a relational set of any of the types here described. *Cat*, for example, is not normally in a contrast relation with *dalmatian*. These two items could be perceived as contrastive, since their being referentially incompatible but their difference in categorization level prevents them from being a “good” contrast set in a neutral context. Minimal difference is then the underlying principle of semantic relations.

The Relation by Contrast (RC) principle (Murphy [2003]) defines relations on the basis of minimal difference.

Relation by Contrast: The contrast relation holds among the members of a set of words if they have all the same contextually relevant property but one.

Contrast is a general category for semantic relations, that includes all relations, including synonymy, antonymy, co-hyponymic contrast, hyponymy and others.

Relation by contrast does not refer to criteria for judging similarity or difference, except for saying that “relevant” criteria are applied. Because of this, RC is then general enough to account for any lexical relation mentioned thus far. So, all relations are cases of minimal difference, but they vary in what objects they relate and on what criteria they contrast those object. Semantic Relations are then those in which the information that is relevant to minimal difference is semantic in nature. Synonymy, antonymy and other semantic relations can be seen as applications of RC. Binary instantiation of RC involve two-member sets and can be referred to as oppositional relations. *Brother/sister* are then opposite because they are two co-hyponyms of *sibling*. Given that the basic criterion for the relation is minimal difference, the more similar two items are, better they suit an oppositional relation.

Treating lexical relations as relations among word-concepts, implies that both linguistic form and semantic properties are available as material for choosing “better” antonyms. The form of the word becomes relevant for antonymy in order to exclude other potential antonyms. Here *antonym* refers specifically to the opposition of words while *opposite* applies to binary relation. *Gin* and *Tonic* can be considered antonyms based on the fact that they are two noun members of the set phrase *gin and tonic*, or they can be considered to represent opposite concepts since they refer to things that are similar by virtue of being liquids in the same drink.

Regarding hyponymy and meronymy, although a word might have many hyponyms or meronyms, the relationship regards two levels, opposing a set of one to a set of many. Hyponymy and meronymy can be considered as non-binary contrast relation if we extend relations to more than two levels. In such case *animal* > *bird* > *eagle* would be a set of words in hyponymic relation. Since RC requires the items in a relation to be as similar as possible (based on the context), the best hyponyms are only one level of categorization away from their hyperonyms, and parts are better meronyms than subparts. So *bird* > *eagle* is a better example of hyponymy than *animal* > *eagle*.

In the following two subsections I will describe the properties of two specific paradigmatic relations: hyponymy and antonymy. This work focus on those two relations, because of the difficulties they present in being identified and treated using distributional methods. Moreover, the properties of these relations can be used to resolve some of the difficulties in using distributional methods for their classification, as will be further explained in Chapter 5.

2.3 Antonymy

Antonymy (referring to binary opposition in general) is arguably the archetypical lexical semantic relation. Not only does antonymy exist, but it is robustly evident in natural language. Unlike hyponymy and meronymy, it can be a relation among words as much

as it is a relation among concepts. While inclusion and part-whole relations are acknowledged in lexical semantics texts, they are rarely relation among words and almost always relations among concepts. Synonymy and antonymy are lexicologically interesting (even if we assume that the lexicon includes no paradigmatic relational information) as metalexical relations, that is relations among word-concepts. There is little evidence, anyway, that hyponymy and meronymy are relation among word-concepts rather than relations among the things (or concepts) that those words denote. For example, *dog* is a hyponym of *animal* because the meaning of *dog* includes the features (or other representations of meaning) that constitute the meaning of *animal*. Antonymy is also the focus of much of the debate as to whether semantic relations are stored or derived and whether they are intralexically or metalexically represented.

The Relation-by-Contrast definition should be easy to formulate for antonyms since contrast is part of the game. If we presume antonymy to be the opposite of synonymy, then the similarities of synonymy (their meanings) should be dissimilarities in antonyms. So we would fashion a version of RC that states that all semantic contrast relation holds between words that have all the same relevant properties except for their meanings. As Lyons [1977] notes, “opposition are drawn along some dimension of similarity”. Oppositions are usually drawn on the basis of semantic similarity. The question is what must be similar in opposition, and what should be different.

Relation by Contrast-Lexical Contrast (RC-LC) (Murphy [2003]) states the following: A lexical contrast set includes only words-concepts that have all the same contextually relevant properties but one.

Antonymy is the most robust of the semantic relations, even though one might argue it should be more specifically defined. Antonymy tends to be characterized using diagnostic tests, which require that sentential minimal pairs involving antonymous predicates are mutually contradictory.

While diagnostics may identify incompatible pairs, they fail in distinguishing between pairs that simply have incompatible reference (*cat/mineral*) and those whose contrast seems more antonymous. Such tests reflect semantic incompatibility, but does not measure lexical contrast of canonical antonymy, according to which *alive/dead* are “good” antonyms, but the morphologically dissimilar *alive/expired* are not.

Proposed criteria for antonymy or contrast set are usually defined in terms of componential semantic analysis. This means that contrast sets are words that share a set of semantic features but contrast in one feature or feature specification. For example, *red/yellow/blue* form a contrast set since they share features that indicate they are primary colors, but fail to share feature specification for HUE. Those criteria rely on semantic features, and they predict that if a word’s antonym has a synonym, then the word has two equivalent antonyms, but this prediction rarely holds. This criticism has been most vigorously favored by those encouraging an associationist model of the lexicon. Their favorite example involves the basic size adjectives: since *large/little* are not perceived as good an antonymic fit as *big/little*, antonymy is a relation between words

rather than between meanings (Gross et al. [1989]). According to Cruse [1994]’s prototype approach to opposition, the “goodness” of an opposed pair depends on its having these properties: diametric opposition (*black/white* are diametrically opposed in color-based scale), binarity (*true/false* are binary antonyms because to deny that something is *true* amounts to affirming it is *false*), exhaustiveness of the superordinate domain and symmetry (the opposition of two words is symmetric around the centre of the dimension). For example, a binary exhaustive set of synonyms (*deep-fry=French-fry* in US English) would be judged as antonymous as a diametrically opposed pair that do not exhaust the superordinate domain (*sweet/sour*) because they both have three features of antonymy. To get around this problem, Cruse proposes that, for each relation, there are some necessary conditions for membership in that relation type, and features that contribute to making the word pair “better” or “worse”. Complementary antonyms like *alive/dead* better fit this definition than examples like *warm/cold*. The best examples of minimal difference are those that are diametrically opposed and symmetrical, since otherwise more than minimal difference is involved. Being exhaustive of the superordinate term guarantees that there are no other competitors for antonymy status. Binarity makes it easier to identify minimal differences, since in those cases a single difference is made salient by the lack of competing potential antonyms.

The “good” antonyms are those that contrast on a single, most relevant, property and that match on their other relevant properties. The “best” antonyms are those that go beyond matching on the most obviously relevant property and extend their similarity to as many properties as possible while maintaining a single relevant difference. *Maximize/minimize* was judged the most antonymous pair by subject in Herrmann et al. [1986]’s experiment because the two words have a symmetrical semantic relation as well as extremely similar form. The pair *maximize/minimize* is then judged a slightly better case of antonymy than *large/small* because the two words are maximally similar. In contrast with the artificial task in Herrmann et al. [1986]’s experiment, the “goodness” of antonym fit when looking for the best antonym for a particular word, which involves comparing pairs of antonyms with a member in common. In neutral contexts, a word has more than one potential “good” antonym when a larger contrast set is available (*sweet/sour* vs. *sweet/bitter*) or if a group of synonyms are semantically opposed to the target word (*big/little* vs. *big/small*), or if different facets of the target word can be opposed (*girl/boy* vs. *girl/woman*).

While synonymy has been claimed to be reflexive, symmetric and transitive, antonymy has been claimed to be irreflexive in that a lexical unit cannot be antonym of itself. Antonyms are logically symmetric (if A is antonym of B, then B is the opposite of A) but they don’t necessarily have symmetric distribution (some of this asymmetry is due to the asymmetry between the things that words describe). Transitivity does not hold among antonym pairs. For example, *tall* is the opposite of *short* and *short* is the opposite of *long* but this does not make *tall* the opposite of *long*.

Antonymy relations are defined by their binarity. Larger contrast sets are numerous, but there is something special about the one-on-one opposition of antonymy, and any binary set can seem oppositional.

Binarity in lexical contrast can arise in a number of ways. The simplest is binarity by coincidence. If it just so happens that only two items belong to a contrast set, then they are antonymous. For example, since humans have only two types of limb, *arm* and *leg*, they automatically contrast by virtue of being the only members of the category HUMAN LIMB. Other lexical relations, instead, are unlikely to coincidentally fail into binary pairs. For the asymmetrical relations (like hyponymy) there is no point in having a one-to-one relation. Contrast sets that are coincidentally binary are not considered to be prototypically opposite by Cruse [2000] who maintains that opposites are inherently binary, that is binary by some logical necessity. That is the case for scalar opposition, in which more or less of some properties are measured. Scalar opposites describe opposite directions on a one-dimensional scale. Since a single dimension only allows for two directions, binary opposition arises naturally, as it happens in *tall/short* or *warm/cool*. The binary nature of negation allows for the third type of binary contrast. For morphologically rich languages, opposite words can be created through negative morphology, as in *logical/illogical* or *safe/unsafe*. This opposition are well accounted for by RC, since the words are very similar in that they share the semantic and phonetic material of the stem. The last type of possible binarity is binarity for binarity's sake. In this case, at least three items are available for contrast, but two among those are privileged as antonyms. We can account several examples, including taste (*sweet/sour*) and emotion (*happy/sad*). RC-LC accounts for the privileging of certain pairs among others through its requirement of maximal similarity and minimal difference. While *happy* contrasts with *sad* and *angry*, it seems to have the most in common with *sad*, given that *happy* and *sad* reflect states with reversed facial expressions (smile/frown) and postures (up/down). While *happy/angry* is useful contrast for some contexts, in a neutral context *happy* and *sad* have these obvious characteristics in common and thus are favored as opposites.

While the antonym relation is reciprocal, the members of an antonym pair may not show symmetrical distribution in linguistic contexts or in speakers' behaviors. Some of this asymmetry is due to the asymmetry between the things that the world describe. *Table* elicits *chair* because *chairs* are often used together with a *table*. *Chair* is less likely to elicit *table* because *chairs* can be used without *tables* (for example in waiting rooms).

Theorists have capitalized upon the tendency for antonyms to co-occur in constructions in order to account for the acquisition of the knowledge that two words are antonyms. Fellbaum [1995] identifies a number of likely constructions, like the following:

- (4) **x and y** → public (private) and private (public) corporations
- (5) **from x to y** → from back (front) to front (back)

(6) **x or y** → dead (alive) or alive (dead)

In these constructions, *x* and *y* are symmetrically placed and, to some extent, they can be reversed. If they cannot be reversed it may be because the phrase is lexicalized as an irreversible binomial, or it may be that one of the terms is semantically marked in relation to the other.

Markedness is a major source of distributional asymmetry in antonymic relations. Some (Vendler [1963], Givón [1970], Handke [1995] among others) have defined antonymy as the relation between marked and unmarked items. Markedness distinction feature heavily among gradable adjectives, where marked (*young, short, bad*) and unmarked (*old, long, good*) adjectives are subject to distributional asymmetries.

Different theorists use different criteria for determining which member of a pair is marked and which is unmarked. The most common criterion is that the unmarked items have to be used naturally, without the specific semantic context needed by the marked item.

Theorists differ as to whether markedness theory explains or describes distributional differences. Some of them (Cruse [1986], Lehrer [1985]) have presented arguments that markedness could be lexically idiosyncratic, while others have treated markedness as a lexical feature without making any motivating arguments. This solution is tantamount in representing antonymy in the lexicon, since words are not marked or unmarked in and of themselves but could be marked or unmarked in relation to one another. Anyway, there is no reason to believe that the asymmetries noted in markedness theory are represented in linguistic knowledge, just as there is no reason to believe that binarity is a lexical or linguistic property. If words are semantically in marked/unmarked contrast, it is because the concepts or referents they represent are not in an absolutely symmetric relation. For example, among the measurement adjectives, the ones expressing greater quantities (height, width, size..) are unmarked while the one expressing lesser quantities are marked. The asymmetrical distribution of these antonym pairs is predictable from the nature of the measurement scales they describe. Whether something is *tall* or *short* depends on whether its height is in the *tall* or *short* direction of the scale, with reference to the contextually determined neutral point. *Tall* describes the point that goes away from the zero point, while *short* describes the direction that goes towards the zero point.

The antonymy relation is logically symmetric, but word-association evidence indicates that specific antonym relations may be mentally stored in directional way. For canonical antonyms, this could be represented as the directional link from *table* to *chair* to be stronger than the one from *chair* to *table*. The asymmetric distribution of marked/unmarked pairs indicates their asymmetric semantic structure and their unequal cultural status. Much of the work on lexical opposition developed in the last century has focused on defining and differentiating subtypes of opposites. Taxonomies of opposition vary in the number of subtypes they identify.

Logical definitions have little value in accounting for speakers judgments of antonymy

and contrast. While understanding the nature of these subtypes could be important in order to understand certain kinds of entailment, it is not particularly relevant to the understanding of lexical relations as metalinguistic concepts. Lyons and Cruse's taxonomies of antonyms are the most cited in literature, so their categories and definitions are represented as "the standard". Many theorists restrict the term antonym to the subset of antonyms that are gradable and contrary. Gradable contraries, (like *big/little* or *good/bad*) seem particularly representative of the phenomenon of lexical contrast.

We could call a predicate "gradable" if it describes properties that can be hold to a greater or lesser degree. Such words could take degree modifiers and occur in comparative and superlative constructions.

Gradable opposites are typically in contrary opposition, so that asserting one of them implies negating the other. The entailment can then be made from an assertion of p to the denial of q , but not the other way around. For example:

- (7) a. The morpheme is long \rightarrow The morpheme is not short
- b. The morpheme is not long \nrightarrow The morpheme is short

In this last example, the entailment falls because the saying that morpheme under examination is not long doesn't necessary imply for it to be short, since it might be of average length. Gradable contraries then, do not strictly bisect a domain, as said by Cruse [1986].

Antonymy is focused on contrasts that are symmetrically placed on a scale, such as *hot/cold*, rather than those that are contrary but not symmetrically placed. Lehrer [1992] refers to symmetrical gradable contrasts as perfect antonyms. In adjective-heavy languages, such English, gradable contrariety is typically associated with adjectival contrast. While there are verbs (like *love/hate*) that show the hallmarks of gradable contrariety, it is more difficult to find nouns that are gradable contraries. The obvious place to look for them would be among nouns that describe states or properties, especially those derived from gradable adjectives or verbs. Anyway, contrary relations among property-describing nouns are far less common than those among adjectives in English because the nominalization of these concepts is subject to markedness asymmetries. Examining nouns that are not derived from gradable adjectives, we can find some gradable contrary nominal pairs, like *hero/coward* or *genius/dolt*. These pairs are, however, rarely canonical.

It is not surprising that gradable adjectives provide some of the best examples for antonymy. They are words describing the same continuum in a symmetrical way. The properties that gradable adjectives describe are relatively simple, so there are not as many semantic relations available to them, making them more straightforwardly antonymous. The things and actions that nouns and verbs describe are complex, and there is much to know about them and much that can be similar or different to other things or actions (and the nouns and verbs that describe them). The basic gradable adjectives

are also in starkest contrast because they rarely have enough synonyms to compete for the antonym position.

Among gradable contraries, it is possible to distinguish and describe various subtypes, on the basis of the involved scales. For example [Ogden and Richards \[1967\]](#), distinguish between antonyms on a “true scale” (as *black/white*) which are those which rise “continually in physiological and psychological form from minimum to maximum”, from those in which two properties are mutually exclusive and gradable but not simply different intensities on a single scale (like *red/green* or *acid/alkali*). There is a point in the scale that goes from black to white, in which we can say that the color is “*more black*” than the whitest point on the scale. The same does not apply for the scale that goes from *green* to *red*, where it does not make sense to say that the color at a certain point is *more red*” than an extreme green. [Ogden and Richards \[1967\]](#) holds that *green/red* counts as opposites since they oppose each other in the color wheel.

[Cruse \[1986, 1980, 1976\]](#) defined his taxonomy of contrary types on the basis of their linguistic distribution. The three subtypes he defines (polar, overlapping, equipollent) occur in different pattern of distribution and interpretation of each other. Polar antonyms have one member that can occur in a “*how*” question, and one member that can not.

For example:

- (8) How *long* is that string? [impartial]
- (9) #How *short* is that string?

The adjective occurring in a “how question” then, receives an impartial reading, meaning the string in the previous example does not imply that the string is actually long.

The overlapping antonymy subtype involves more asymmetry in distribution and interpretation. For example:

- (10) How *good* is that book? [impartial]
- (11) How *bad* is that book? [committed]

While the first sentence does not imply that the *book* is *good*, the second one presuppose that it is *bad*. The equipollent antonyms are symmetrical in their distribution and interpretation, since both the members of a couple are committed in how questions and neither comparative is acceptable.

[Ogden and Richards \[1967\]](#) differentiates between contrary and complementary antonymy by noting that “opposites may be either the two extremes of a scale or the two sides of a cut. [Lyons \[1977\]](#) defines the type on the basis of entailments relations among the members of an antonym pair: if X is p then X is *not* q and if X is *not* q , then X is p .

For example:

- (12) The monster is *alive* \rightarrow The monster is *not dead*

(13) The monster is *not alive* → The monster is *dead*

This test is easy to use with adjectives, but complementaries also includes nouns and verbs.

Identifying complementary antonyms and contrast sets in language is made difficult by the fact that complementaries could sometimes be treated as contraries, and contraries sometimes can be used as complementaries. We can, for example, say that someone is *more dead* than *alive*, so ungradable adjectives become gradable in such context, not allowing for the clear segmentation of the field assumed in the definition of complementarity.

Some pairs are gradable, but the denial of one is usually taken to be the assertion of the other. Cruse [1986] categorizes them as gradable complementaries. In many cases, one of them is more gradable than the other. On the other hand, both members of pairs like *honest/dishonest* or *clean/dirty* are gradable. Cruse notes that they are not really complementary since they do not perfectly bisect the domain. This problem is solved by Cruse by maintaining that such words must have two senses, one in complementary opposition and the other in contrary opposition to its antonym.

The privative nature of pairs like *clean/dirty* and *honest/dishonest* allows for the two interpretations, since in privative opposition one term of the pair is defined by the absence of something and the other is defined by the presence of that something. But absence or presence can be either relative or absolute states. So if we think about *clean* when it means *absolutely free of filth*, its complementary opposition results because there are only two possible states to describe: something has *filth*, or it does not. If we consider *clean* to mean *relatively free of filth*, then it is opposed to a meaning of *dirty* close to *relatively full of filth*, and the result is a contrary opposition.

Taxonomies of antonymy always include contrariety and complementarity, even if they might be divided into smaller categories. The identification of other types of antonymy is more irregular.

Converse opposition is one of Lyons [1977] major types, characterized as follows: if X is p to Y , then Y is q to X and if Y is q to X , then X is p to Y .

Examples to this could be *parent/child*, *buy/sell* and such. To Lyons comparative forms of gradable adjectives (*older/younger*) are converses too (if X is *older* than Y , Y is *younger* than X). There are scholars that consider converse opposition as a subtype of directional opposition. Converses are the purest examples of directional opposition, since they allow to view the same relation from different sides. Lyons [1977]'s contrasts converseness with directional opposition, in which p and q are directionally opposed if they are in opposite direction with respect to a place P (thus including pairs like *north/south* or *zenith/nadir*). There could be a problem in treating directional opposition as an equal member in a taxonomy that includes contraries, complementaries and converses since members of these categories could be opposed as well. Cruse [1986], gives more subtype of directional opposition. Reversive opposition involves the undoing of some action, state or quality. Common examples in English are morphologically related

(*do/undo, establishment/disestablishment*), while other examples include *build/demolish* and *color/bleach*. Like converses these can be considered mirror images, given that the activity described by one member of the pair is the backward performance of the other. These are treated as a subtype of directional opposition, and further divides them into independent reversives (*raise/lower*), restitutives which involve the return of an early state (*kill/resurrect*), and counterparts (*hill/valley*) which might be an instantiation of contrariety.

Lyons [1977] and Miller [1998] have claimed that while the most common canonical opposites are morphologically distinct words, most antonyms in English and many other languages have a morphological base in common. English provides many opportunities for morphological opposition. *non-* creates complementary antonyms for adjectives and nouns, which perfectly bisect the domain. *un-* and *in-* often produce contrary oppositions among adjectives and adverbs. *un-*, *dis-* and *de-* can make reversible antonyms of verbs. Other, less productive, negative morphemes include *contra-*, *a(n)-* and so forth. Sometimes positive and negative morphemes contrast, as in *pro-union/anti-union*.

Natural language use seems to favor conventional words instead of neologisms like those made using a morpheme. Neologistic morphological negation is not rare, but the abundance of other means for describing contrast limits its use and the general preference for conventional lexemes is usefulness. Different negative morphemes signal different kinds of opposition, such as contrariety, complementarity and reversal, so a single word might have more than one morphologically derived antonym. Morphologically unrelated antonyms may also give different information than their morphologically related counterparts. Even when they are quite synonymous, their meanings can be differentiated.

To sum up, the universality and pervasiveness of antonymy underscores the human cognitive bias toward binary contrast. Linguistic and philosophical interest in antonymy has tended to emphasize the logical properties for antonym subtypes, the ways in which people use and interact with antonyms indicate that even if the opposition is psychologically real (as a process and as a category), more particular relations like contrariety and complementarity are not well distinguished by language users. As shown, this is clear in psycholinguistic experiments and in language use, where antonym subtypes are irrelevant to their discourse functions.

Since words differ in their semantic properties (as well as in other properties, of course), different semantic classes of words contrast in several ways, giving rise to the several antonym types here described.

2.4 Hyponymy

Hyponymy is defined as the TYPE<TOKEN relation, its converse hypernymy is thus defined as the TOKEN>TYPE relation. It is regarded as one of the most fundamental structural relations in the lexicon, rivaled only by incompatibility (Lyons [1968], Cruse [2002]) and is the most studied lexical relation in the computational community. Hyponymy is central in many models of the lexicon, because of its inference-invoking nature, its importance in definition and its relevance to selectional restriction in grammar. Entailments are strongly associated with this relation, to the point that a statement entails an equivalent statement that includes one of its words' hyperonyms. For example, the sentence "a *dog* came in" entails the sentence "an *animal* came in". Definitions like this, which are typical of both standard dictionaries and folk definitions, consist of genus and differential, where the first is the hyperonym itself and the second the qualities that distinguish the defined hyponym from the larger class. The hyponym relation plays a role in the way we think about what a word means. Selectional restriction of the object of a verb can be phrased in terms of a hyperonym and all hyponym of the word are then selected as potential object (Resnik [1993]). *Drinks*, for instance, selects for *beverage* all its possible hyponym (*water, beer, wine* and such). Because of its link to language behavior and its relevance to models of lexical knowledge, hyponymy is the relation that is most relevant to the question of whether the lexicon is semantically organized.

Hyponymy is defined as the "kind of" relation. *Dog* is a hyponym of *animal* because a dog is a kind of animal. In computational models, it is frequently represented as an IS-A or IS-A-MEMBER-OF function. Logical definitions for this relation are usually stated in terms of inclusion. If hyponymy relates extensions, the extension of the hyponym is included in the extension of the hyperonym (*paperbacks* are a subset of the set of *books*). If hyponymy relates intensions, the inclusion is reversed: the intension of a hyponym includes the intension of its hyperonym. *Paperback* is a hyponym of *book* because the meaning of *paperback* includes all the features that make up the meaning of *book* (*has pages, is bound on one side, is made up of paper* and such). Also, the inclusion is unidirectional. If the inclusion were bidirectional, it would have been a synonymy relation. Cruse noted another problem with set-inclusion definition of hyponymy: they allow many more inclusions relations that can be related by the natural language definition of hyponymy *X* is a *type/sort of Y*. While the sentence "a *dog* is a type of *animal*" is a good example of this relation, the same cannot be stated for "a *puppy* is a sort of *dog*", for which the label "sort of" seems odd. Cruse labeled these relations as taxonyms and proposes that taxonyms are subspecies of hyponyms.

Cruse proposes that hyponymy should be treated as prototype category and that taxonyms are central members of the HYPONYM category. He notes that this definition of hyponymy is only superior to a logical inclusion definition because it predicts goodness-of-exemplar judgments.

Taxonomic relations are the IS-A-KIND-OF relation, whereas functional relations are

the IS-USED-AS-A-KIND-OF relation. *Cow* is in taxonomical relation to *animal* (a *cow* is an *animal*), but in a functional relation to *livestock* (since a *cow* functions as a *livestock*). The functional relation is not a logically necessary relation: not every *cow* is *livestock*.

Chaffin and Herrmann [1984] define their hyponymic types in accord to the types of words involved. They also hold that items defined by perceptual cues have a special type of hyponymy relation, which they call perceptual subordination and exemplify with *animal*>*horse*. **Functional subordination** (*vehicle*>*car*) relates items defined by their function. The other four types of subordination are, likewise, defined by how the items in the relation are individually defined: **geographical** (*country*>*Russia*), **activity** (*game*>*chess*), **state** (*emotion*>*fear*) and **action** (*cook*>*fry*). The subordination “types” here seem to name the highest superordinate levels (e.g. *activity*>*game*>*chess*). What is less clear is how the subtypes reflect the different ways in which words are related. This kind of taxonomic organization includes hyponymic subtypes that correspond to parts of speech other than nouns, in particular the action type is illustrated by verbs and the state type might include properties described by adjectives.

Hyponymy/Hypernymy is the most frequently encoded relation using semantic networks. In particular, it is essential in WordNet. It links more general synsets like *furniture.piece_of_furniture* to increasingly specific ones like *bed* and *bunkbed*. Thus, WordNet states that the category *furniture* includes *bed*, which in turn includes *bunkbed*; conversely, concepts like *bed* and *bunkbed* make up the category *furniture*. All noun hierarchies ultimately go up the root node *entity*. Hyponymy relation is transitive: if an *armchair* is a kind of *chair*, and if a *chair* is a kind of *furniture*, then an *armchair* is a kind of *furniture*. WordNet distinguishes among Types (common nouns) and Instances (specific persons, countries and geographic entities). Thus, *armchair* is a type of *chair*, *Barack Obama* is an instance of a *president*. Instances are always leaf (terminal) nodes in their hierarchies.

From a cognitive point of view, hyponymy/hypernymy lexical relation is a process of categorization, which implies that these relations allow recognizing, differentiating and understanding entities according to a set of specific features. Following the works of Rosch [1978], Smith and Medin [1981], as well Evans and Green [2006], hypernyms are associated to basic levels of categorization. If we considered a taxonomy, the basic level is a level where categories carry the most information, as well they possess the highest cue validity, and are the most differentiated from one another Evans and Green [2006]. In other words, as Murphy [2002] points out, basic level (e.g., *chair*) can represent a compromise between the accuracy of classification at a higher superordinate category (e.g., *furniture*) and the predictive power of a subordinate category (e.g., *rocking chair*). However, as Tanaka and Taylor [1991] showed, in specific domains experts primarily use subordinate levels because of they know more distinctive features of their entities than novices do.

Hyponymy is not a reflexive relation. Hyponymy and hypernymy are anti-symmetrical,

since saying that “*p* is a hyponym of *q*” entails “*q* is not a hyponym of *p*”) but hyponymy and hypernymy could be considered symmetrical with respect one to the other. This means that saying the following “*p* is a hyperonym of *q*” entails that “*q* is a hyponym of *p*”. Taxonomic hyponymy is also transitive, and its transitivity is responsible for the “deductive power” this relation holds. The relation between transitivity and deduction is reflected in the classical syllogism, which involves entailment based on inclusion relations. Because of their being anti-symmetrical and transitive, hyponymy relations are often represented in taxonomical tree diagrams.

Cruse [1995, 2002] points out that many words have different hyponymic relations depending on the facet of the meaning which is deemed relevant to the context. He exemplifies this by saying that a *book* has a *TOME* and *TEXT* facets, which have hyponyms like *paperback* and *novel*, respectively. The approach described here is intended to allow items like *book* to stand in different types of relations without multiplying the number of senses (and the number of nodes in the hierarchy) each word has. An attempt at a complete taxonomy requires some proliferation of senses (even what Cruse calls microsenses).

Young children’s lexicons usually start out unorganized and later (around the age in which they acquire the paradigmatic shift) take on hierarchical organization. This obviously does not mean that young children do not know or understand taxonomical organization. It just means they do not always prioritize it. Young children then develop conceptual taxonomic hierarchies, relating superordinate and subordinate categories, but they do not make use of these categories in the same tasks that adults do. Then, their shift toward taxonomical sorting and use of hyponyms indicates a growth in cognitive and metalinguistic abilities, but does not indicate a change in the linguistic system itself.

If semantic relations among words (instead of the concept they denote) are represented as metalexical relations among word-concepts, there is the need for evidence that it is words and not just meanings to be related. Both lexical form and meaning are then relevant to the relation if it is both a lexical and a semantic relation. Anyway form is less relevant to hyponymy than antonymy and synonymy. *Cat* seems a better answer to the question “what is a kind of *animal*?” than *kitty* seems. This could induce us to conclude that register similarity is important to hyponymy decisions. But using a word from a marked register in the question, does not mean that the answer would be considered better if we match register. This contrasts with antonymy, in which form is more usually relevant. The existence of canonical antonyms provides evidence for lexical opposition, but canonical hyponyms are rare, if they exist at all.

Hyponymy relations exist where named categories have named subcategories. There is no reason to think that hyponym relations among word-concepts cannot be derived and there is *little* reason to believe that they generally are, since word form is rarely relevant to hyponym selection. It seems instead that hyponymy relations simply reflect

taxonomical relations among *non*-lexical concepts.

Chapter 3

Distributional Semantics

The term “distributional” can be used (as well as *context-theoretic*, *statistical* or *corpus based*) in order to qualify a family of approaches to semantics that assume that the statistical distribution of words in contexts plays a significant role in defining their semantic behavior. This hypothesis, namely the fact that word co-occurrence statistics derived from text corpora can provide a basis for semantic representation, has lately gained attention in computational linguistics, as well as in cognitive science. Obviously, many differences exist according to the different adopted computational techniques, the semantic properties associated with text distributions, the definition of the linguistic context used to compute the combinatorial spaces of lexical items etc.

As already said, the computational analysis of word distributional properties is based on methods developed both in computational linguistics and in psychology. Since the two fields have different aims, the two research lines have proceeded in parallel. This situation led to the impossibility of carrying out in-depth analyses of the real impact that distributional methods can have while dealing with semantic research and to achieve a better understanding of the foundations of such methods, as well as of their effectiveness and limits. A major issue for the study of word meaning is to recognize identity criteria for the semantic content of words. Therefore, it is not possible to investigate lexical meaning if it is not possible to identify the conditions under which two words can be said to be semantically similar. Semantic similarity has, in fact, a critical role in any investigation (either linguistic or psychological) on meaning. Lately, empirical evidence has been gained and matured on how semantic similarity between words affect the way such words are stored and processed in the mental lexicon. For instance, much evidence comes from so-called semantic priming effects. The semantic priming paradigm has traditionally provided a powerful tool for the investigation of cognitive processes related to memory and language, perception or attention (e.g., [Ochsner et al. \[1994\]](#)). In a typical version of this paradigm, participants are required to make any kind of response (e.g., naming, lexical decision, semantic judgement) to a target stimulus, which is preceded by either an unrelated word or a semantically (and/or associatively) related word prime.

Semantic priming is observed when responses to the target are faster and/or more accurate for the related than for the unrelated prime-target pairs. The typical interpretation of semantic priming (e.g., [Collins and Loftus \[1975\]](#)) is that presenting a prime stimulus (e.g., *cat*) would activate its corresponding internal representation (node) in memory, and such an activation would spread to other related nodes, thus facilitating the processing of related targets (e.g., *dog*). That spread of activation in memory has often been regarded as a fast-acting automatic process, occurring without intention or awareness (e.g., [Posner and Snyder \[1975a,b\]](#)).

The assumption behind all the models of distributional semantics is that the notion of semantic similarity can be defined in terms of linguistic distributions. This is known as the “Distributional Hypothesis” (further on DH) which is stated as follows: “The degree of semantic similarity between two linguistic expressions A and B depends on the similarity of the linguistic contexts in which A and B can appear”. According to this definition, certain aspects of the meaning of lexical expressions depend on the distributional properties of such expressions, or better, on the contexts in which they are observed. The semantic properties of a word should then be defined by inspecting a significant number of linguistic contexts, representative of the distributional behavior of such word.

Recently, distributional semantics has gained consensus, especially in computational linguistics. Despite this fact, it is a theory that pertains to the linguistic tradition, since the history of DH actually begins in the context of Zellig Harris’ proposal of distributional analysis as the bedrock of linguistics as a scientific discipline:

In both the phonologic and morphologic analyses the linguist first faces the problem of setting up relevant elements. To be relevant these elements must be set up on a distributional basis: x and y are included in the same element A if the distribution of x relative to the other elements B, C, etc. is in some sense the same as the distribution of y . Since this assumes that the other elements B, C, etc., are recognized at the time when the definition of A is determined, this operation can be carried out without some arbitrary point of departure only if it is carried out for all the elements simultaneously. The elements are thus determined relatively to each other, and on the basis of the distributional relations among them. ([Harris \[1951\]](#))

Harris’ distributional proposal was conceived for phonemic analysis and later turned into a general methodology to be applied to every linguistic level. He regarded the distributional procedure as a way for linguists to give a methodological base to their analyses. Not only did he extend his theory to meaning, but he also assumed that meaning identity could actually be explained on distributional grounds. According to Harris, the semantic similarity between two words is a function of the degree of the similarity of their “linguistic environments” or better, the degree to which they can occur in similar contexts. Semantic analysis might therefore receive a solid empirical foundation by the

distributional approach.

Structuralist distributional methodology have then been abandoned in favor of generative linguistics, thus determining a downplay of the interest in contextual distributions as a primary key for investigating meaning. Also, there was a great attention towards the internalized competence of an ideal speaker. These two facts implied that the explanans for linguistic structures - including semantic ones- had to be found in cognitive principles, rather than in the distributional constraints of linguistic constructions. Corpus-based statistical distributions were dismissed as a reliable source of linguistic evidence, as well as a suitable formal model for grammar description.

Cognitive linguistics has stressed a conceptualist view of semantics, according to which the meaning of a lexical expression is a conceptualization of an entity it is able to evoke.

The distributional constraints to which linguistic construction obey are intended to receive a functional explanation in terms of the principles governing our conceptualizing of the world. Embodied conceptualization is, then, the source of meaning and has to explain linguistic distributions.

Formal approaches to language studies have emphasized a denotational approach to semantics, The basic tenet of this view is best described through the words of [Lewis \[1972\]](#) “Semantics with no treatment of truth-conditions is not semantics”. Here the target is any semantic analysis that tries to analyze meaning in terms of some combination of symbols claimed to be conceptual primitives. Lewis’ statement indirectly concerns distributional approaches to meaning, like those discussed by Harris. Distributional analysis might tell us something interesting about languages, but this does not mean they tell us something about meaning, since grammar are “abstract semantic systems, whereby symbols are associated with aspects of the world”. This is actually coherent with Charles Morris’ definition of semantics as the study of the “relations of signs to the objects to which the signs are applicable” ([Morris \[1938\]](#)). So, both cognitive and model-theoretic approaches refuse distributional semantics since meaning can not be explained in terms of word-distributions but needs to anchor them onto conceptual representations in the speaker’s mind (for cognitive models) or objects in the world.

Within the corpus linguistics tradition, there was no need to motivate DH as a methodological principle for semantic analysis. This is better summarized in the well mentioned slogan by [Firth \[1957\]](#) “You shall know a word by the company it keeps”. In corpus linguistics, DH is often claimed to be the only possible source of evidence for the exploration of meaning.

Distributional Semantics has gained popularity in computational linguistics starting from the late 80’s, when there was the progressive predominance of corpus-based statistical methods for language processing. Within this new paradigm, statistical methods were naturally applied not only to part of-speech (POS) tagging or to syntactic parsing, but also to lexical semantic analysis. In psychology, the Distributional Hypothesis finds one explicit assertion (defined Contextual Hypothesis) in the work by [Miller and](#)

Charles [1991], who argue for a “usage-based” characterization of semantic representations. Miller and Charles, tried to turn Wittgenstein’s claim that “the meaning of a word is its use in the language” into a even more “context-based” characterization of word meaning, by arguing that repeated encounters of a word in the various contexts eventually defines the formation of a contextual representation. They defined it by stating it was an abstract cognitive structure that accumulates from encounters with the word in various (linguistic) contexts. Although a direct parallel exists with Harris’ distributional analysis, yet there is a crucial element of difference between the two positions, given that Harris is a strong anti-psychologist. His distributional analysis is meant to be a scientific method for linguistic research. For Miller and Charles, instead, the Distributional Hypothesis is a specific assumption about the cognitive format and origin of semantic representations. Their primary goal is to use contextual representations to provide an empirical characterization of semantic similarity as a central notion in psycholinguistic research. Semantic similarity is then perceived by Miller and Charles as a dependent variable of the contexts in which words are used. This idea was previously explored by Rubenstein and Goodenough [1965] who carried out empirical investigations to test the hypothesis of a correlation between word synonymy and similarity of contexts, the latter was formalized as the proportion of words appearing in the contexts of the two synonyms. Miller and Charles point out that the mechanisms leading to the formation of contextual semantic representations can be viewed as a specific instance of general cognitive associative mechanisms that record the statistical co-occurrence between stimuli. This is consistent with the importance assigned in neo-behaviorist psychology to word associations (the first word produced by a subject in response to a word stimulus), as evidence to analyze the organization of language. Word associations are interpreted by Jenkins [1954] as the result of the distribution between stimulus and response in linguistic context and the association strength between stimulus and response, is related to the distributional similarity between the two words. Pulman [2013] gives a detailed account of how the historical use of distributional contexts in linguistics relates to modern distributional semantics, particularly in relation to the possibility of compositional distributional models The fortune of the Distributional Hypothesis in cognitive science was affected by the strong correlation with associative learning.

To sum up, the ups and downs of the Distributional Hypothesis as a methodological hypothesis to investigate meaning, have followed the fortune of empiricists approaches in linguistics and in cognitive science. Context-based distributions can be used as the basis for semantic representations only within the perspective of admitting that the probabilistic analysis of linguistic distributions has a meaningful role for language organization and its dynamics.

The names that better represents this kind of approach to meaning are *distributional semantics* and *context-theoretic semantics*. The essence of such models resides in the idea that word meaning depends on the contexts in which words are used and that word content can be characterized by its contextual representation, that should be defined as

an abstraction over the linguistic contexts in which a word can be found. Corpora are then connected to distributional semantics. They can be used as repositories of linguistic usages, then representing the primary source of information to identify the world distributional properties. Their role has been enhanced by the current availability of huge collection of texts, contextually with increasingly sophisticated computational linguistics techniques to process them and extract the relevant context feature to build distributional semantic representations. Anyway, the relationship between textual data and context-based representations might be strong, but not exclusive. The contextual hypothesis then is not restricted to features extracted from linguistic contexts alone. Contextual representations of words may contain a wider array of information about the contexts and situations in which such word is used. The use of linguistic contexts in current distributional approaches should be considered as an approximation of a wider notion of language usage, because our computational techniques to extract and model features from linguistic contexts are more advanced than those used to extract features from the extralinguistic contexts. Anyway, the fact that most methods for distributional semantics are mostly applied to data extracted from corpora does not preclude the possible integration of contextual information, mixing linguistic and extralinguistic information in contextual representations. Distributional semantics should then not be automatically reduced to a kind of corpus linguistics. Indeed, the scope of contextual semantic representations is potentially broader than simply recording linguistic distributions. Currently, distributional semantics is indeed corpus-based but this does not prevent it to underline aspects of the format and origin of word meaning and the issue of how and to what extent features extracted from the linguistic input actually shape meaning.

The goal of computational methods adopting the Distributional Hypothesis, are various: terminology extraction, models of semantic priming and for vocabulary learning, word-sense disambiguation, etc. Given this broad variety of applications, it is important to distinguish between two versions of the Distributional Hypothesis: the weak and the strong one. These versions share the basic methodology they are based upon while they diversify each other for the status assigned to contextual representations in the analysis of meaning. In its weak version, DH is a quantitative method for semantic analysis. Word distributions in contexts are investigated in order to identify the semantic paradigmatic properties of these expressions. The idea behind it, is that word meaning determines the combinatorial behavior of words in contexts and the semantic features of lexical expressions behave as constraints ruling their syntagmatic behavior. This implies that, inspecting a significant number of distributional contexts, one should be able to identify the aspects of meanings shared by words with similar contextual distributions and can be used to explain those distributions. Accepting this weak version of the DH does not imply that word distributions are constitutive of the semantic properties of lexical items, at a cognitive level. Weak DH is, then, compatible with many research programs in theoretical linguistics. [Levin \[1993\]](#) defines Classes of English Verbs, claiming that

the semantic properties of verb argument structures determine the way in which such structures are realized at the syntagmatic level and the array of possible syntactic alternations that a verb participate in. Those Classes of verbs are identified on distributional basis, while the contexts are the possible alternations in which verbs are found. Verbs are then grouped into equivalence classes according to the types of alternations they share. Classes are inspected to identify the common semantic elements shared by their elements and that may be regarded as an explanation for that particular class. Similarity in distribution is considered to be a consequence of some semantic properties that explain it. [Fazly and Stevenson \[2008\]](#) argue that various properties of multiword expressions, such as *non-compositionality*, *rigidity*, etc., can receive a distributional interpretation. In fact, corpus-based statistical methods have long been used to automatically identify multiword expressions (together with collocations, as their closest relatives). Now, [Fazly and Stevenson \[2008\]](#) prove that distributional indicators can also be used to discriminate between different semantic classes of multiword expressions. The results of their experiments show that the DH can successfully be applied to achieve a better understanding of the internal structure of that complex phenomenon represented by multiword expressions. [Pustejovsky and Jezek \[2008\]](#) apply the DH within the theory of the Generative Lexicon ([Pustejovsky \[1991, 2001\]](#)), and provide interesting examples of the advantages of using the DH in close cooperation with a solid theory of lexical semantics. They use use distributional data to investigate various aspects of lexical coercion phenomena in English and Italian. This work succeed in showing that the combinatorial properties of lexemes can be used to give a more robust empirical foundation to various GL theoretical constructs, such as the Qualia Structure, the compositional operations proposed in [Pustejovsky \[1991\]](#) and [Pustejovsky \[2013\]](#), and the “dot-type” that represent regular polysemy alternations. Generative Lexicon is able to provide interesting interpreting keys for distributional information, and progresses in semantic research will be achieved by enhancing the synergies between distributional methods and formal theoretical analysis.

In its strong version, the DH is a cognitive hypothesis about the form and origin of semantic representations, as countenanced by [Miller and Charles \[1991\]](#). Repeatedly find a word in different linguistic contexts lead to the formation of a contextual representation as an abstract characterization of the most significant contexts in which the each word is used. Assuming the strong DH implies assuming that word distributions in context have a specific causal role in the modeling of the semantic representation for that words. The distributional behavior of a word in contexts is not just a way to get at its semantic behavior, but a way to explain its semantic content at the cognitive level. Distributional semantic representations have been used to model a variety of psychological phenomena, such as similarity judgments, semantic priming, semantic memory deterioration etc. ([Miller and Charles \[1991\]](#), [Vigliocco et al. \[2004\]](#), [Rogers et al. \[2004\]](#), [Jones et al. \[2006\]](#)). Distributional techniques have also been applied to model child

lexical development as a bootstrapping process in which lexical and grammatical categories are extracted from the statistical distributions in the adults' input (Li et al. [2004], Baroni et al. [2007]). Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA; Landauer and Dumais [1997]) and Hyperspace Analogue to Language (HAL; Lund and Burgess [1997]) are two of the most influential models for distributional semantics, initially developed for cognitive and psychological research and claimed to represent cognitively plausible models for the way semantic representations are learned extracting regular co-occurrence patterns from the linguistic input. Farkaš and Li [2001] and Li et al. [2004] propose an incremental version of HAL with a recurrent neural network trained with Hebbian learning. Borovsky and Elman [2006] also model word learning in a fairly incremental fashion, using as word representations the hidden layer activation vectors produced by a Simple Recurrent Network. The network is probed at different training epochs and its internal representations are evaluated under a gold standard ontology of semantic categories to monitor the progress in word learning. Although Borovsky and Elman [2006] claim to be able to simulate relevant aspects of child word learning, a major shortcoming of their work is represented by the fact that the training corpus is formed by simple artificial sentences, with a potential negative impact on the cognitive realism of the simulation. In fact, using naturalistic corpus data for training appears as a necessary condition to test distribution-based word learning under realistic conditions, avoiding any unwarranted abstraction from the noise and fragmentary character of adult-child interactions. All these models adhere to the strong DH, and assume that the encounters of a word in different linguistic environments have an effect on the semantic representations of these words.

The contextual representations advocated by Miller and Charles and the strong version of the DH commit to the cognitive plausibility of distributional semantic structures. So, word meaning is determined by its combinatorial behavior in linguistic contexts. Empirical evidence has shown that different semantic phenomena can be modeled using the assumption that cognitive semantic representations have a distributional basis, anyway the idea that meaning might consist of abstractions from linguistic co-occurrence patterns has raised many critiques. Plausibility of the DH had many skeptics, who did not support the possibility it provide an empirical foundation for semantics, by claiming that all that distributional information can tell us about a word, can not be considered its meaning. The main reason for such consideration resides in the difficulty for distributional semantics to satisfactorily address core issues concerning semantic representations, above all compositionally, inference and reference. We should investigate whether these weak points depend on contingent features of the current models implementing the DH or are related to the structure of distributional representations, thereby impairing their adequacy for meaning and its dynamics. The consequences gathered from the fact that distributional models are unable to tackle one or more of these aspects is usually that

distributional semantics is not semantic, at all.

Current implementations of the DH are not able to account for the different lexical inferences that words can or can not license. State of the art Distributional Semantics Models (DSMs) are able to account for similarity relations from the distributional point of view, these same models can not represent the fact that these words are similar, but under different semantic respects. Distributional models place words in a common semantic space depending on their contextual representations, and measure the distance among them to account for their semantic similarity. We will examine this phenomenon in depth in the next chapter, but the distance between the words in a distributional semantic space, is a symmetric relation. Therefore, the notion of distance in vector space can be at most a proxy for a general, unspecified notion of semantic similarity, but it can not account for the fact that the space of relations linking word meanings is a highly structured one. Distributional models have a descriptive adequacy that goes below those of semantic models, like WordNet (Fellbaum [1998]) and semantic networks in general (Collins and Quillian [1969]).

Harris conceived distributional analysis as a method to establish linguistics as a scientific enterprise. Distributional semantics alongside with all its different implementations (to be further described), is a research program that adopts mathematical and computational methods to investigate meaning in a scientific way. Current state of the art models of distributional semantics suffer of various shortcomings that I'm partially trying to overcome with this work, but such shortcomings are not enough to dismiss the semantic information that can be extracted with distributional analyses. Psychological research has emphasized the role of experience in shaping our semantic memory. Experience is considered to consist of sensory-motor information extracted from perception and action we make in the world. Language is, however, part of our experience, of our acting in the world and of our trying to know it. We can imagine, then, that the structures of the language to which we are exposed may actually contribute to shape our semantic competence. Distributional Semantics can then also be a tool intended to investigate the extent to which linguistic categories may have a distributional basis and may then be used to provide new contributions even to cognitive sciences.

3.0.1 Word-space Models

The word-space model is a spatial representation of word meaning. Its core idea is that semantic similarity can be represented as proximity in *n-dimensional* space, where *n* can be any integer ranging from 1 to some very large number. In these geometric representations, spatial proximity between words indicates how similar their meanings are. As an example, the word space in Figure 3.1 depicts *cat* as being closer to *feline* than to

FIGURE 3.1: A 2 dimension vector space

dog, which should be interpreted as a representation of the meaning similarities between these words: the meaning (of) *cat* is more similar to the meaning (of) *feline* than to the meaning (of) *dog*.

The word-space model is a model of semantic similarity. [Padó and Lapata \[2003\]](#) note that the notion of semantic similarity has rendered a considerable amount of criticism against the word-space model. The critique usually consists of arguing that the concept of semantic similarity is too broad to be useful, in that it encompasses a wide range of different semantic relations, such as synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, meronymy, and so forth. The critics claim that it is a serious liability that simple word spaces cannot indicate the nature of the semantic similarity relations between words, and thus does not distinguish between, e.g., synonyms, antonyms, and hyponyms.

This criticism is arguably valid from a prescriptive perspective where these relations are a priori given as part of the linguistic ontology. From a descriptive perspective, however, these relations are not axiomatic, and the broad notion of semantic similarity seems perfectly plausible. There are studies that demonstrate the psychological reality of the concept of semantic similarity. For example, [Miller and Charles \[1991\]](#) point out that people instinctively make judgments about semantic similarity when asked to do so, without the need for further explanations of the concept; people appear to instinctively understand what semantic similarity is, and they make their judgments quickly and without difficulties. The distributional methodology only discovers differences (or similarities) in meaning, and the geometric metaphor only represents differences (or similarities) in meaning. If we want to claim that we represent some particular type of semantic relation in the word-space model, we need to modify either the distributional hypothesis or the geometric metaphor, or perhaps even both.

3.0.2 Mathematical Models implementing the Distributional Hypothesis

In the previous section I've introduced the fact that statistics is a crucial component of distributional semantics, because it is used to abstract the significant features of the contexts that enter into forming the contextual representations of words. Statistical analysis is, therefore, one of the main mathematical tools that are currently used to single out the most salient contextual features to characterize a word distributional behavior. Other mathematical techniques are used, as well.

3.0.2.1 Context Vectors

The way in which we could proceed in order to infer a geometric representation starting from distributional information can be originated from Zellig Harris, who writes that “the distribution of an element will be understood as the sum of all its environments” [Harris \[1970\]](#).

The first thing to decide is what we define as environment. In linguistics, an environment is called a context. Again, a context can be anything from the surrounding words to the socio-cultural circumstance of an utterance.

We here assume a context to be the setting of a word, phrase etc., among the surrounding words, phrases, etc., often used for helping to explain the meaning of the word, phrase, etc.

One way to collect this information is to tabulate the contextual information, so that for each word we provide a list of the co-occurents of the word, and the number of times they have co-occurred. In a second step, we take away the actual words, and only leave the co-occurrence counts. Also, we make each list equally long by adding zeroes in the places where we lack co-occurrence information. We also sort each list so that the co-occurrence counts for each context come in the same places in the lists, so that the result would look something like the one depicted in the following table:

WORD	dog	animal	television	water	cat
dog	0	4	0	1	2
animal	4	0	0	3	4
television	0	0	0	2	0
water	1	3	0	0	1
cat	2	4	0	1	0

TABLE 3.1: Term-term co-occurrences matrix

As an example, the co-occurrence-count list for “cat” is (0, 4, 0, 1, 2), and the list for “cat ” is (2, 4, 0, 1, 0). Such ordered lists of numbers are also called vectors. Formally, a vector \vec{v} is an element of a vector space, and is defined by n components or coordinates $\vec{v} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. The coordinates effectively describe a location in the n -dimensional space. An example of a 2-dimensional vector space with two vectors $\vec{v}_1 = (1, 2)$ and $\vec{v}_2 = (3, 2)$ is depicted in Figure 3.2.

FIGURE 3.2: A 2-dimensional space with vectors $\vec{v}_1 = (1, 2)$ and $\vec{v}_2 = (3, 2)$.

Another way of looking at context vectors is to say that they describe locations in context space. Thus, the concept of a context vector is the solution to our problem of how to go from distributional statistics to a geometric representation.

The idea of context vectors has its earliest origins in work on feature space representations of meaning in psychology. The pioneer in this field is Charles Osgood and his colleagues, who in the early 1950s developed the semantic differential approach to meaning representation [Osgood \[1952\]](#), [Osgood et al. \[1957\]](#). In such approaches words are represented by feature vectors where the elements are human attitudinal ratings along a seven-point scale for a number of contrastive adjective pairs such as “soft-hard” “fast-slow” and “clean-dirty.” The idea is that such feature vectors can be used to measure the psychological distance between words. A very simplified example of the feature vectors for the words “mouse” and “rat” based on three contrastive pairs is given in [Table 3.2](#)

	small–large	bald–furry	docile–dangerous
mouse	2	6	1
rat	2	6	4

TABLE 3.2: Feature vectors based on three contrastive pairs for the words mouse and rat.

The arguably most influential work from this period comes from Schütze [1992, 1993], who builds context vectors (which he calls “term vectors” or “word vectors” in precisely the manner described in Section 3.1 above: co-occurrence counts are collected in a words-by-words matrix, in which the elements record the number of times two words co-occur within a set window of word tokens. Context vectors are then defined as the rows or the columns of the matrix (the matrix is symmetric, so it does not matter if the rows or the columns are used).

3.0.2.2 The co-occurrence matrix

The approach pioneered by Schütze has become standard practice for word-space algorithms: data is collected in a matrix of co-occurrence counts, and context vectors are defined as the rows or columns of the matrix. Such a matrix of co-occurrence counts is called a co-occurrence matrix, and is normally denoted by F (for frequency). As we have already seen, the matrix can either be a words-by-words matrix $w \times w$, where w are the word types in the data, or a words-by-documents matrix $w \times d$, where d are the documents in the data. A cell f_{ij} of the co-occurrence matrix records the frequency of occurrence of word i in the context of word j or in document j .

In the traditional vector-space model described above, a cell f_{ij} of matrix F is the weight of term i in document j . When building words-by-documents matrices, the weight is usually composed of three components (Robertson and Jones [1994]):

$$f_{ij} = \text{TF}_{ij} \cdot \text{DF}_i \cdot S_j \quad (3.1)$$

where TF_{ij} is some function of the frequency of term i in document j (TF for *term frequency*), DF_i is some function of the number of documents term i occurs in (DF for *document frequency*), and S_j is some normalizing factor, usually dependent on document length (S for *scaling*). The point of the first component TF_{ij} is to indicate how important term i is for document j . The idea is that the more often a term occurs in a document, the more likely it is to be important for identifying the document. The observation that frequency is a viable indicator of the quality of index terms originates in the work of Hans Peter Luhn in the late 1950s (Luhn [1958]).

The second component DF_i indicates how discriminative term i is. The idea is that terms that occur in few documents are better discriminators than terms that occur in

many. The arguably most common version of the document frequency measure is to use the inverse document frequency (IDF) computed as:

$$\text{IDF} = \log \frac{D}{\text{DF}_i} \quad (3.2)$$

where D is some constant—usually the total number of documents in the document collection. The third component S_j is normally a function of the length of document j , and is based on the idea that a term that occurs the same number of times in a short and in a long document should be more important for the short one. That is, we do not want long documents to end up at the top of the ranking list in an information-retrieval system merely because they are long. There are many variations of document-length normalization, ranging from very simple measures that just count the number of tokens in a document, to more complex ones, such as pivoted document-length normalization).

An alternative to the previously described *tf-idf* is Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI) (Church and Hanks [1990]; Turney [2001]). While *tf-idf* works only for term-document matrices, PMI works well for both word-context matrices (Pantel and Lin [2002a]) and term-document matrices (Pantel and Lin [2002b]). We will give the formal definition of PMI here, as an example of an effective weighting function. Let \mathbf{F} be a word-context frequency matrix with n_r rows and n_c columns. The i -th row in \mathbf{F} is the row vector $f_{i:}$ and the j -th column in \mathbf{F} is the column vector $f_{:j}$. The row $f_{i:}$ then corresponds to a word w_i and the column $f_{:j}$ corresponds to a context c_j . The value of the element f_{ij} is the number of times that w_i occurs in the context c_j . Let \mathbf{X} be the matrix that results when PMI is applied to \mathbf{F} . The new matrix \mathbf{X} has the same number of rows and columns as the raw frequency matrix \mathbf{F} but the value of an element x_{ij} in \mathbf{X} is defined as follows:

$$p_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_r} \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} f_{ij}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$p_{i*} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_c} f_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_r} \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} f_{ij}} \quad (3.4)$$

$$p_{*j} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_r} f_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_r} \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} f_{ij}} \quad (3.5)$$

$$pmi_{ij} = \log \left(\frac{p_{ij}}{p_{i*}p_{*j}} \right) \quad (3.6)$$

In this definition, p_{ij} is the estimated probability that the word w_i occurs in the context c_j , p_{i*} is the estimated probability of the word w_i , and p_{*j} is the estimated probability of the context c_j . If w_i and c_j are statistically independent, then $p_{i*}p_{*j} = p_{ij}$ (by the definition of independence), and thus pmi_{ij} is zero (since $\log(1) = 0$). The product $p_{i*}p_{*j}$ is what we would expect for p_{ij} if w_i occurs in c_j by pure random chance. On the other hand, if there is an interesting semantic relation between w_i and c_j , then

we should expect p_{ij} to be larger than it would be if w_i and c_j were independent; hence we should find that $p_{ij} > p_{i*}p_{*j}$, and thus pmi_{ij} is positive. This follows from the distributional hypothesis. If the word w_i is unrelated to the context c_j , we may find that pmi_{ij} is negative. PMI is designed to give a high value to x_{ij} when there is an interesting semantic relation between w_i and c_j ; otherwise, x_{ij} should have a value of zero, indicating that the occurrence of w_i in c_j is uninformative.

The log of the ratio corresponds to a form of correlation, which is positive if there is an interesting semantic relation between w_i and c_j , and negative otherwise. A variation of PMI is Exponential PMI (EPMI) which is the exponential function of PMI, resulting in the equation that only measures the ratio.

$$EPMI_{ij} = \frac{p_{ij}}{p_i \cdot p_j} \quad (3.7)$$

Another variation is Positive PMI (PPMI), in which all PMI values that are less than zero are replaced with zero (Niwa and Nitta [1994]).

$$PPMI_{ij} = \begin{cases} PMI_{ij} & \text{if } PMI_{ij} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

A well-known problem of PMI is that it is biased towards infrequent events, since it has higher information content than contexts that occur together with a lot of words. Consider the case where w_i and c_j are statistically dependent (i.e., they have maximum association). Then $p_{ij} = p_{i*} = p_{*j}$. Hence (3.6) becomes $\log(1/p_{i*})$ and PMI increases as the probability of word w_i decreases. Then, another approach is taken to take the observed frequency of co-occurrence into account. This variant of PMI is called Local Mutual Information (LMI) (Evert [2005]) which is an approximation to the log-likelihood ratio (LLR) measure (Dunning [1993]).

$$LMI_{ij} = f_{ij} \log \frac{p_{ij}}{p_i \cdot p_j} \quad (3.9)$$

Similar with PMI, there is also a variation of LMI called Positive LMI (PLMI) which replaces all the negative values in the matrix with zero:

$$PLMI_{ij} = \begin{cases} LMI_{ij} & \text{if } LMI_{ij} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

3.0.2.3 How to compute similarity?

A *n-dimensional vector* effectively identifies a location in an n-dimensional space. However, the locations by themselves are not particularly interesting knowing where a word is located in a real-valued n-dimensional space does not tell us anything. Rather, it is the relative locations that are interesting knowing that two words are closer to each other

than to the another word is the kind of information we are interested in. The principal feature of the geometric metaphor of meaning is not that meanings can be represented as locations in a (semantic) space, but rather that similarity between (the meaning of) words can be expressed in spatial terms, as proximity in (high-dimensional) space.

Context vectors do not only allow us to go from distributional information to a geometric representation, but they also make it possible for us to compute (distributional, semantic) proximity between words. Thus, the point of the context vectors is that they allow us to define (distributional, semantic) similarity between words in terms of vector similarity.

There are many ways to compute the similarity between vectors, and the measures can be divided into similarity measures and distance measures. The difference is that similarity measures produce a high score for similar objects, whereas distance measures produce a low score for the same objects: large similarity equals small distance, and conversely. A similarity measure can therefore be seen as the inverse of a distance measure. Generally, we can transform a distance measure $dist(x, y)$ into a similarity measure $sim(x, y)$ by simply computing:

$$sim(x, y) = \frac{1}{dist(x, y)} \quad (3.11)$$

The arguably simplest vector similarity metric is the scalar (or dot) product between two vectors \vec{x} and \vec{y} , computed as:

$$sim_s(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = x \cdot y = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + \dots + x_ny_n \quad (3.12)$$

Another simple metric is the Euclidian distance, which is measured as:

$$dist_E(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (3.13)$$

[Widdows \[2004\]](#) points out, these measures are not ideal to use for word-space algorithms. The reason is that the scalar product favors frequent words (i.e. words with many and large co-occurrence counts will end up being too similar to most other words). A solution to this problem is to factor out the effects of vector length, which can be done by normalizing the vectors by their length (or norm), given by:

$$|x| = \sqrt{x \cdot x} \quad (3.14)$$

A convenient way to compute normalized vector similarity is to calculate the cosine of the angles between two vectors \vec{x} and \vec{y} , defined as:

$$sim_{\cos(\vec{x}, \vec{y})} = \frac{x \cdot y}{|x||y|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2}} \quad (3.15)$$

The cosine measure corresponds to taking the scalar product of the vectors and then dividing by their norms. The cosine measure is the most frequently utilized similarity metric in word-space research, and the one that will be used throughout this dissertation. It is attractive because it provides a fixed measure of similarity it ranges from 1 for identical vectors, over 0 for orthogonal vectors, to -1 for vectors pointing in the opposite directions. It is also comparatively efficient to compute [Widdows \[2004\]](#).

Chapter 4

Relation Extraction: State of the Art

Information Extraction (IE) is an important unresolved problem in natural language processing (NLP). It is a type of information retrieval whose general goal is to automatically extract structured information (i.e. categorized and contextually and semantically well-defined data from a particular domain), from unstructured or semi-structured machine-readable documents. Basically it is a shallow form of text understanding that extracts substrings about pre-specified types of entities or relations between them from documents and web pages. Example of **entities** could be *people*, *organizations* and *locations*, while **relations** could be *part-of*, *location* or *hyperonymy*.

Such information can be directly presented to an end user or can be used by other computer systems (such as search engines) in order to provide better services. Information Extraction has applications in a wide range of domains, the type and structure of information to extract depending on the need of the particular application.

The extraction of structured information from text dates back to the '70s (e.g. [DeJong \[1979\]](#)), but it only started to gain attention when DARPA started the Message Understanding Conference (MUC) in the '90s ([Grishman and Sundheim \[1996\]](#)).

Since then, research efforts on this topic have not declined. Early MUCs defined IE as “filling a predefined template that contains a set of predefined slots”. Template filling is a complex task and systems developed to fill one template cannot work to directly fill another different template. In MUC-6, a number of template-independent subtask for IE were also defined. Such tasks serve as building blocks to support full-fledged, domain-specific information extraction systems.

There are different ways of extracting relations from text: supervised methods, semi-supervised methods and unsupervised methods. For example, early information extraction systems such as those participating in the MUCs are often rule-based systems, aka supervised systems. They use linguistic extraction patterns developed by humans to match text and locate information units. They can achieve good performance on their

target domain but it might be really labor intensive to design good extraction rules. Moreover, the developed rules are usually highly domain dependent. Given the limitations of these manually developed systems, researchers turned to statistical machine learning approaches. Decomposing information extraction systems into components such as *Named Entity Recognition (NER)* and *Relation Extraction (RE)*, many information extraction subtasks can be transformed into classification problems, thus allowing to solve them by using standard supervised learning algorithms. Because IE involves identifying segments of texts that play different roles, sequence labeling methods such as Hidden Markov Models have also been used.

IE tasks traditionally assume that the structures to be extracted, e.g. the *types of named entities*, the *types of relations* or the template slots are well defined. Sometimes the structures of the information to be extracted are not known in advance. Therefore it is necessary to extract and mine such structures from large corpora. Suppose, for example, that we want to gather information such as *date, time, epicenter magnitude* (namely, the most important pieces of information) from a set of earthquake news articles. There have been recent studies on this kind of unsupervised information extraction problems (this work tries, in fact, to explore an unsupervised approach to relation extraction), but overall work along this line remains limited.

Another new direction is *open information extraction*, where the system is expected to extract all useful entity and relations from a large, diverse corpus (such as the Web). The output of such systems includes the arguments involved in a relation together with a description of the relation gathered from the text, as in the following example:

- (14) a. **Calcium prevents osteoporosis**
- b. **Google and Apple are headquartered in Silicon Valley**
- c. **Chicago was founded in 1833**

Advances in this direction include systems like TEXTRUNNER (Yates et al. [2007]), WOE (Wu and Weld [2010]) and REVERB (Fader et al. [2011]). Information Extraction from semi-structured Web pages has also been an important research topic in Web mining. A major difference of Web Information Extraction from classical Information Extraction, lies in the fact that web pages often contain structured or semi-structured text (e.g., tables and lists) whose extraction is based on HTML tags rather than on linguistic features.

In this chapter, we are going to focus on Relation Extraction (RE) only, and we are going to cover RE from purely unstructured natural language texts. Relation extraction is the task of detecting and characterizing the semantic relations between entities in text. For example, from the following sentence fragment,

- (15) *Apple* co-founder *Steve Jobs*

we can extract the following relation,

(16) FounderOf(Steve Jobs, Apple).

Much of the work on relation extraction is based on the task definition from the Automatic Content Extraction (ACE) program (Doddington et al. [2004]). ACE focuses on binary relations, i.e. relations between two entities. The two entities involved are also referred to as *arguments*. A set of major relation types and their subtypes are defined by ACE. Examples of ACE major relation types include **physical** (e.g. an entity is physically near another entity), **personal/social** (e.g. a person is a family member of another person), and **employment/affiliation** (e.g. a person is employed by an organization). ACE makes a distinction between *relation extraction* and *relation mention extraction*. The former refers to identifying the semantic relation between a pair of entities based on all the evidence we can gather from the corpus, whereas the latter refers to identifying individual mentions of entity relations. Because corpus-level relation extraction to a large extent still relies on accurate mention-level relation extraction, we are not going to take this difference into account.

Various techniques have been proposed for relation extraction. The most common and straightforward approach is to treat the task as a classification problem: Given a pair of entities co-occurring in the same sentence, can we classify the relation between the two entities into one of the predefined relation types? Although it is also possible for relation mentions to cross sentence boundaries, such cases are less frequent and hard to detect. Existing work therefore mostly focuses on relation extraction within sentence boundaries, and this is exactly the way we are going to deal with relation extraction in this work.

There have been a number of studies following the classification approach. Supervised approaches for extracting lexical relations fall into two other categories: pattern-based or cluster-based. Another major line of work on relation extraction is weakly supervised relation extraction from large corpora that does not rely on the availability of manually labeled training data. One approach is the bootstrapping idea to start with a small set of seed examples and iteratively find new relation instances as well as new extraction patterns. Representative work includes the Snowball system (Agichtein and Gravano [2000]). Another approach is distant supervision that makes use of known relation instances from existing knowledge bases such as Freebase (Mintz et al. [2009]).

4.1 Supervised Methods

Supervised approaches for extracting lexical relations fall into two other categories: pattern-based or cluster-based. Pattern-based approaches are more common; using a pattern-based approach means searching the corpus for specific lexical relations, expressed in very prototypical ways. The majority of published work on relation extraction describe pattern-based approaches. We will take a better look at pattern-based approach

later on. The clustering approach, which is not as common, uses clustering algorithms to group words according to their meaning in text, labeling the clusters using its members' lexical or syntactic dependencies, and then extracting relations between each cluster member and the cluster label. Caraballo [1999] first proposed this approach, which used conjunction and apposition features to build noun clusters. Pantel and Ravichandran [2004] extended this approach by making use of all syntactic dependency features for each noun. The advantage of clustering approaches is that they permit algorithms to identify *is-a* relations that do not explicitly appear in text. However they generally fail to produce coherent clusters from fewer than 100 million words; hence they are unreliable for small corpora. We here describe pattern-based approaches.

Hearst [1992] described a method for the automatic acquisition of the hyponymy lexical relation from unrestricted text. As described in Chapter 2, hyponymy (or *is-a*) relation exists when a event, entity, state, is a subclass of another. For example, *daisy-flower* are related by a hyponymy relation, because the daisy is a flower. Two goals motivated Hearst and her approach: avoidance of the need for pre-encoded knowledge and applicability across a wide range of text. At that time, there was much interest in the automatic acquisition of lexical syntax and semantics, with the goal of building up large lexicons for natural language processing. Extracting lexical information from machine readable dictionaries was a great success but was limited, because the set of entries within a dictionary is fixed. Interpreting unrestricted domain-independent text made it difficult to determine in advance what kind of information would be encountered and how it would be expressed. Instead of interpreting everything in the text in detail, Hearst used a pattern-based approach, that is, she searched for specific lexical relations that were expressed in well-known ways. She discovered that useful information could be found with only a very simple understanding of a text. Given the sentence:

- (17) The bow lute, such as the Bambara ndang, is plucked and has an individual curved neck for each string.

Most fluent readers of English who never encountered the word “Bambara ndang” would nevertheless infer that a “Bambara ndang” is a kind of “bow lute”, even if they had a fuzzy conception of what a “bow lute” was. The sentence above did not deliberately defined the term, as a dictionary would have done, however the semantics of the lexico-syntactic construction indicated by the pattern:

$$NP_0 \text{ such as } \{NP_1; NP_2 \dots \text{and } (and|or)\} NP_n$$

were such that they implied:

$$\text{for all } NP_i; 1 \leq i \leq n; \text{hyponym}(NP_i; NP_0)$$

Thus from the sentence it was possible to extract the following semantic relation:

hyponymy(“Bambara ndang”, “bow lute”)

Hearst used the term hyponym as in the following definition: a concept represented by a lexical item L_1 if native speakers of a certain language accept sentences constructed from the frame “An L_0 is a (kind of) L_1 ”. Here L_1 is the hypernym of L_0 . As specified in Chapter 2, the relation is reflexive and transitive, but not symmetric. The Example in (17) shows a way to discover a hyponymic lexical relationship between two or more noun phrases in a naturally-occurring text. According to Hearst, there were many ways in which the structure of a language could indicate the meanings of lexical items, but the difficulty lied in finding constructions that frequently and reliably indicate the relation of interest. Lexical relations are often not mutually exclusive, therefore, a pattern could be ambiguous and consequentially could be found to contain a certain relation upon further examination. Thus it might not be a reliable representative for that relation. It may seem that, because free text is so varied in form and content, it is not possible to find such constructions. However, Hearst identified a set of lexico-syntactic patterns that indicate the hyponymy relation and that satisfy the following criteria:

1. they occur frequently and in many text genres
2. they (almost) always indicate the relation of interest
3. they can be recognized with little or no pre-encoded knowledge.

The first condition indicated that the pattern would result in the discovery of many instances of the relation, the second condition that the information extracted would not be misleading, and the third condition that making use of the pattern would not require predefined knowledge, thus it would not require the tools that it was intended to help build, since knowledge is what is meant to be obtained by such system. Finding instances of the hyponymy relation was useful for several purposes like lexicon expansion, noun phrase semantics (that is, the identification of the general meaning of unfamiliar nouns, based on their hyponymy relations) and semantic relatedness information (that is, approaches aimed at inferring relations among lexical terms by looking at a very large text samples and determining which one are related in a statistically significant way).

How did Hearst’s system discover patterns? Initially she discovered patterns (1) – (3) by observation, looking through text and noticing the patterns and the relations they indicated. In order to find new patterns automatically, she sketched the following procedure:

1. Decide on a lexical relation, R , that is of interest, e.g., “group-member” (in her formulation this was a subset of the hyponymy relation).

2. Gather a list of terms for which this relation was known to hold, e.g., “England-country” . This list could be found automatically using the method described here, bootstrapping from patterns found by hand, or by bootstrapping from an existing lexicon or knowledge base.
3. Find places in the corpus where these expressions occurred syntactically near one another and record the environment.
4. Find the commonalities among these environments and hypothesize that common ones yield patterns that indicated the relation of interest.
5. Once a new pattern had been positively identified, use it to gather more instances of the target relation and go to Step 2.

Overall, Hearst’s results were encouraging, although the number of relations she found was small compared to the size of the text used, *Grolier’s American Academic Encyclopedia (Grolier 1990)*. Indeed, she found that, in 8.6 M words of encyclopedia text, there were 7607 sentences that contained the lexemes “such as” contiguously. Out of these, 152 relations fitted the restriction of the experiment, namely that both the hyponyms and the hypernyms were un–modified. In fact, the experiment was set to extract relations consisting of unmodified nouns in both the hypernym and hyponym roles (although determiners were allowed, as well as a very small set of quantifier adjectives like “some” “many” “certain” and “other”). When the restrictions were relaxed, so that seeds consisting of two nouns or a present/past participle plus a noun were allowed, 330 relations were found. She suggested that this situation might be improved using less stringent restrictions, that would increase the number of retrieved relations.

[Berland and Charniak \[1999\]](#) presented a method for extracting parts of objects from the whole (e.g. *speedometer* from *car*). Given a single word denoting some entity that has recognizable parts, the system found and ordered other words that might denote parts of the entity in question, or given [Cruse \[1986\]](#) definition, a meronymy relation. Berland and Charniak based their work on Hearst’s, using a similar methodology and applying that to the “part-of” relation instead than the “is-a” relation analyzed by Hearst. While she failed in trying to apply her theory to the “part-of” relation, they succeeded by implementing some differences that were particularly important. Berland and Charniak’s first goal was to find lexical patterns that tend to indicate part–whole relations. Once again they followed Hearst and found possible patterns by taking two seed words that were in a part-whole relation and finding sentences in a corpus (the North American News Corpus) that had those words within close proximity. For the couple of words *basement* and *building* the first few sentences were:

- (18) a. The **basement** of the **building**

- b. The **basement** in question **is in** a four-story apartment **building**
- c. The **basement** of the apartment **building**
- d. From the **building's** **basement**
- e. The **basement** of **a building**
- f. The **basements** of **buildings**

From these examples, they constructed the following patterns:

- (19)
- a. **whole NN[-PL] 's POS part NN[-PL]** as in *building's basement*.
 - b. **part NN[-PL] of PREP the—a DET mods [JJ—NN]* whole NN** as in *basement of a building*
 - c. **part NN in PREP the—a DET mods [JJINN]* whole NN** as in *basement in a building*
 - d. **parts NN-PL of PREP wholes NN-PL** as in *basements of buildings*
 - e. **parts NN-PL in PREP wholes NN-PL** as in *basements in buildings*

They assumed here that parts and wholes were represented by individual lexical items (as head nouns of noun-phrases) as opposed to complete noun phrases, or as a sequence of “important” noun modifiers together with the head. This could cause some problems, e.g., *conditioner* was marked by their informants as not part of *car*, whereas *air conditioner* probably would have made it into a part list. Nevertheless, in most cases head nouns had worked quite well on their own. Berland and Charniak evaluated these patterns by observing how they performed in an experiment on a single example (with the seed word *car*). The following Example shows the 20 highest ranked part words for each of the patterns in Example 19.

- (20)
- a. **Pattern 19a:** headlight windshield ignition shifter dashboard radiator brake tailpipe pipe speedometer converter hood trunk visor vent wheel occupant engine tyre.
 - b. **Pattern 19b:** trunk wheel driver hood occupant seat bumper backseat dashboard jalopy fender rear roof windshield back clunker window shipment reenactment axle
 - c. **Pattern 19c:** passenger gunmen leaflet hop houseplant airbag gun koran cocaine getaway motorist phone men indecency person ride woman detonator kid key
 - d. **Pattern 19d:** import caravan make dozen carcass shipment hundred thousand sale export model truckload queue million boatload inventory hood registration trunk ten

- e. **Pattern 19e:** airbag packet switch gem amateur device handgun passenger
fire smuggler phone tag driver weapon meal compartment croatian defect
refugee delay

Patterns 19a and 19b outperformed patterns 19c, 19d, and 19e. Although parts occurred in all five patterns, the lists of gathered words for 19a and 19b were predominately parts-oriented. The relatively poor performance of patterns 19c and 19e was anticipated, as many things occur “in” *cars* (or *buildings*, etc.) other than their parts. Pattern 19d was not so obviously bad as it differed from the plural case of pattern 19b only in the lack of the determiner “the” or “a”. However, this difference proved critical in that pattern 19d tended to pick up “counting” nouns such as *truckload*. On the basis of this experiment they decided to continue using only patterns 19a and 19b.

The developed algorithm was composed of three phases. The first identified and recorded all occurrences of patterns 19a and 19b in the corpus. The second filtered out all words ending with the suffixes “ing”, “ness”, or “ity”, since these suffixes typically occur in words that denote a quality rather than a physical object. The extracted words, which possibly represent instances of the meronymy relation, were ordered according to how likely they represented the meronymy relation, according to some appropriate metric selected. Then, they tested five subjects (all of whom were unaware of their goals) for their concept of a “part”. They asked the subjects to rate sets of 100 words, 50 of which were in their final results set. The score of individual words varied greatly but there was relative consensus on most words. Lacking a formal definition of part, and considering the ambiguity of the meronymy relation, they could only define as correct the words there were marked as part of the concept by the testing subjects, marking the rest as wrong. While the scoring was not perfect, it provided an adequate reference result. Overall, about 55% of the top 50 words for each seed were parts, and about 70% of the top 20 for each seed. One ambiguous word, “plant” was used. The program founds parts corresponding to both senses, though given the nature of the text, the industrial use was more common. As a baseline, the authors also tried using the head nouns that immediately surround their target word as their “pattern” and then applied the same “strong conditioning, sigdiff” statistical test to rank the candidates. This performed quite poorly. Of the top 50 candidates for each target, only 8% were parts, as opposed to the 55% for the program. Berland and Charniak’s program could find parts of objects, given a word denoting the whole object and a large corpus of unmarked text. The program was about 55% accurate for the top 50 proposed parts for each of six examples upon which they tested it. A few problems were identified. Idiomatic phrases like “a jalopy of a car” or “the son of a gun” provided problems that were not easily weeded out. Depending on the data, these phrases could be as prevalent as the legitimate parts. In some cases problems arose because of tagger mistakes. The program had also some tendency to find qualities of objects. They tried to weed out most of the qualities by removing words with the suffixes “ing” “ness” and “ity”, like Hearst did. The most persistent problem was sparse data, which was the source of most of the noise.

More data would almost certainly allow them to produce better lists, both because the statistics would be more accurate, but also because larger numbers would allow to find other reliable indicators.

Hearst tried to find parts in corpora but did not achieve good results. According to the authors their program worked better than Hearst's because of their very large corpus and the use of more refined statistical measures for ranking the output.

4.2 Semi-supervised Methods

Classification methods for relation extraction rely on a large amount of training data, which is expensive to obtain. A solution to this problem is weakly supervised learning methods that work with much less training data. The most notable weakly supervised method for relation extraction is *bootstrapping*, which starts from a small set of seed relation instances and iteratively learns more relation instances and extraction patterns. This bootstrapping approach has been widely explored (Brin [1999], Agichtein and Gravano [2000]). More recently, another learning paradigm called *distant supervision* has been proposed to make use of a large number of known relation instances in existing large knowledge bases to create training data Mintz et al. [2009]. For both bootstrapping and distant supervision, noisy training data is automatically generated. To achieve good performance, careful feature selection and pattern filtering need to be carried out.

Jones et al. [1999] noticed that when applying text learning algorithms to complex tasks, it was tedious and expensive to manually label the large amounts of training data necessary for good performance. Text learning algorithms at the time were reasonably successful when provided with enough labeled or annotated training examples. However, as more complex domains were considered, the requisite size of these training sets got prohibitively large. Creating these training sets became tedious and expensive, since typically they must be labeled by a person. This led to a search for learning algorithms that do not require such large amounts of labeled data. While labeled data is difficult to obtain, unlabeled data is readily available and plentiful. Castelli and Cover [1995] showed that unlabeled data could be used in some settings to improve classification, although it was exponentially less valuable than labeled data.

Riloff and Jones tried to use a bootstrapping framework for text learning tasks that would otherwise require large training sets. The input to the bootstrapping process was a large amount of unlabeled data and a small amount of seed information to inform the algorithm about the specific task at hand. Seed information took the form of keywords associated with classes. Bootstrapping initialize a learner with the keywords which are then applied by the learner to suggest labels for unlabeled data which in turn builds a new learner, with each iterative process refining on the results. There were two instantiations of the bootstrapping approach for different text learning tasks. The first case study was performed by Riloff and Jones [1999]. Their goal was to automate the construction

of both a lexicon and extraction patterns for a semantic category using bootstrapping. The heart of their approach was based on mutual bootstrapping, that is, the observation that extraction patterns can generate new examples of a semantic category, which in turn could be used to identify new extraction patterns. Their goal was to automate the construction of both a lexicon and extraction patterns for a semantic category using bootstrapping. The mutual bootstrapping process began with a text corpus and a handful of predefined seed words for a semantic category. Before bootstrapping began, the text corpus was used to generate a set of candidate extraction patterns. They used AutoSlog (Riloff [1996]) to generate extraction patterns for every noun phrase in the corpus. Given a noun phrase to extract, AutoSlog used heuristics to generate a linguistic expression that represented relevant context for extracting the noun phrase. Because of the exhaustive application of AutoSlog, the complete set of extraction patterns produced was capable of extracting every noun phrase in the training corpus. Then, Riloff and Jones applied the extraction pattern to the corpus and recorded their extractions. Using these data, the mutual bootstrapping procedure identified the extraction pattern that was most useful for extracting known category members. This extraction pattern was then used to propose new phrases that belonged in the same lexicon. At each iteration, the algorithm saved the best extraction pattern for the category examined into a list. All extractions were assumed to be category members and were added to the semantic lexicon. Then the next best extraction pattern was identified, based on both the original seed plus the new words that were just added to the lexicon, and the process repeated. Since the semantic lexicon was constantly growing, the extraction patterns were re-scored after each iteration, using a scoring heuristic based on how many lexicon entries were extracted by a pattern. A pattern that extracted a variety of category members would be scored higher than a pattern that extracted only one or two different category, no matter how often. Scoring was also based on “Head phrase” matching, instead of requiring an exact match. Riloff and Jones tested this approach by generating dictionaries for locations from corporate web pages used in the WebKB project (Craven et al. [1998]). Meta bootstrapping identified 191 location phrases in the web pages. After 50 iterations, 76% of the hypothesized location phrases on the web pages, were true locations.

Agichtein and Gravano [2000] noticed that text documents often contain valuable structured data that is hidden in regular English sentences. This data is best exploited if available as a relational table that could be used for answering precise queries or for running data mining tasks. They explored a technique for extracting such tables from document collections that required only a handful of training examples from users. These examples were used to generate extraction patterns that in turn resulted in new tuples being extracted from the document collection, in a process called Snowball. Snowball introduced novel strategies for generating patterns and extracting tuples from plain-text documents. At each iteration of the extraction process, Snowball evaluated the quality of these patterns and tuples without human intervention, and kept only the most reliable

ones for the next iteration. Agichtein and Gravano also developed a scalable evaluation methodology and metrics for the task, presented thorough experimental evaluation of Snowball and comparable techniques over a collection of more than 300,000 newspaper documents. Text documents often hide valuable structured data. For example, a collection of newspaper articles might contain information on the location of the headquarters of a number of organizations. If we need to find the location of the headquarters of, say, Apple Computers, we could use traditional information-retrieval techniques to find documents that contain the answer to the query. Alternatively, we could answer such a query more precisely if we somehow had available a table listing all the organization-location pairs mentioned in our document collection. A tuple $\langle o; l \rangle$ in such table would indicate that the headquarters of organization o are in location l , and that this information was present in a document in their collection. Tuple $\langle Apple; Cupertino \rangle$ in their table would then provide the answer to the query. The web contains millions of text pages with hidden data that would be best exploited in structured form. Build structured tables from the information hidden in unstructured text, then would mean being able to run more complex queries and analysis of these tables, and report precise results.

Brin [1999] introduced the DIPRE method, where DIPRE means Dual Iterative Pattern Expansion to extract a structured relation (or table) from a collection of HTML documents. DIPRE worked best in an environment like the World-Wide Web, where the tables and tuples to be extracted tend to appear in uniform contexts repeatedly in the collection documents (i.e., available HTML pages). DIPRE exploited this redundancy and inherent structure in the collection to extract the target relation with minimal training from a user. In fact, DIPRE required the user to just provide a handful of valid tuples of the target relation, with no other training. Hence, in this context DIPRE's goal was to extract a table with all the organization-location tuples that appeared in a given document collection. Initially, DIPRE was provided with a handful of instances of valid *organization-location* pairs. For example, we may indicate that $\langle Apple; Cupertino \rangle$ is a valid pair, meaning that *Apple* is an organization whose headquarters are located in *Cupertino*. Similarly, DIPRE was provided with a few other examples. In addition, the user could provide a general regular expression that the entities must match. For example, a potential organization value must match a regular expression:

$$[A-Z0-9][A-Za-z0-9;:;:0#!?;]{4, 45}[A-Za-z0-9]$$

This is all the training that DIPRE required from the user. After this initial training phase, DIPRE looked for instances of the example organizations and locations in the text documents. Then, DIPRE examined the text surrounding the initial tuples. For example, DIPRE inspected the context surrounding *Apple* and *Cupertino* in, say, “computer servers at Apple’s headquarters in Cupertino” to construct a pattern “ $\langle STRING1 \rangle$ ’s headquarters in $\langle STRING2 \rangle$ ”. The algorithm represented an occurrence of a seed tuple as a seven-tuple: $\langle o; l; order; url; left; middle; right \rangle$, where *url* is the URL of

the source document in which $\langle o;l \rangle$ was found. After generating a number of patterns from the initial seed tuples, DIPRE scanned the available documents in search of segments of text that match the patterns. As a result of this process, DIPRE generated new tuples and used them as new “seeds”. DIPRE then started the process all over again by searching for new tuples in the documents to identify new promising patterns.

It can be seen that, unlike most machine-learning systems for information extraction, DIPRE required no training other than providing a handful of initial seed tuples and specifying the general pattern that the elements of the extracted tuples must match. By acquiring additional training examples automatically, DIPRE aimed at capturing most of the tuples mentioned in the collection. The Snowball architecture followed the general DIPRE outline except that Snowball introduced key ideas that results in substantially better performance. More specifically, Snowball presented a novel technique to generate patterns and extract tuples from text documents. In addition, Snowball introduced a strategy for evaluating the quality of the patterns and the tuples that are generated in each iteration of the extraction process. Only tuples and patterns that were regarded as being “sufficiently reliable” would be kept by Snowball for the following iterations of the system. These new strategies for generation and filtering of patterns and tuples improved the quality of the extracted tables significantly. A key improvement of Snowball from the basic DIPRE method is that Snowball’s patterns included named-entity tags. An example of such a pattern is: $\langle LOCATION \rangle$ -based $\langle ORGANIZATION \rangle$. This pattern would not match any pair of strings connected by “-based”. Instead, $\langle LOCATION \rangle$ would only match a string identified by a tagger as an entity of type LOCATION. Similarly, $\langle ORGANIZATION \rangle$ would only match a string identified by a tagger as an entity of type ORGANIZATION. A key step in generating and later matching patterns, was finding where $\langle ORGANIZATION \rangle$ and $\langle LOCATION \rangle$ entities occurred in the text. For this, Snowball used a state of the art named-entity tagger, The MITRE Corporation’s Alembic Workbench. In addition to ORGANIZATION and LOCATION entities, Alembic could identify PEOPLE entities, and could be trained to recognize other kinds of entities. To define patterns precisely, Snowball followed DIPRE’s approach, and have a pattern consist of a left, a middle, and a right string. More specifically, Snowball represented the left, middle, and right “contexts” associated with a pattern analogously as how the vector-space model of information retrieval represented documents and queries.

The pattern and tuple evaluation was the key part of Snowball, as well as not to include many noisy patterns during the extraction process. This was also responsible for most of the improvement over the DIPRE scheme. For example, from the seed entity pair $\langle Google, MountainView \rangle$ we may also find “Google, Mountain View” in the corpus. However, the pattern “ORGANIZATION, LOCATION” is not a reliable one and thus should not be used. Heuristic methods have been proposed to judge the quality of an extraction pattern. Usually two factors are considered: coverage and precision. Coverage is related

to the percentage of true relation instances that can be discovered by the pattern. Precision is related to the percentage of correct relation instances among all the relation instances discovered by the pattern.

In bootstrapping only a small set of seed entity pairs is used. With the growth of the social Web, much human knowledge has been contributed by a large crowd of users and stored in knowledge bases. A well-known example is Wikipedia. Another example is Freebase, a knowledge base that stores structured human knowledge such as entity relations [Bollacker et al. \[2008\]](#). With such freely available knowledge, it becomes possible to use a large set of entity pairs known to have a target relation to generate training data. [Mintz et al. \[2009\]](#) proposed distant supervision for relation extraction based on this idea. They assume that if two entities participate in a relation, any sentence that contain these two entities express that relation. Because this assumption does not always hold, [Mintz et al. \[2009\]](#) use features extracted from different sentences containing the entity pair to create a richer feature vector that is supposed to be more reliable. They define lexical, syntactic and named entity tag features. They use standard multi-class logistic regression as the classification algorithm. Their experiments show that this method can reach almost 70% of precision based on human judgment.

4.3 Unsupervised Methods

A large amount of labeled training data is also required in order to learn a good named entity recognizer or relation extractor. However, both defining the structures for the information to be extracted and annotating documents according to the defined structures require human expertise and are time consuming. To alleviate this problem, recently there has been an increasing amount of interest in unsupervised information extraction from large corpora. The key idea is to cluster entities or entity pairs based on their lexico-syntactic contextual features. Open information extraction's goal is to extract any type of relation from a large, diverse corpus such as the Web.

In previous sections, we analyzed relation extraction when the types of relations to be extracted are known in advance. There are also cases where we do not have any specific relation types in mind but would like to discover salient relation types from a given corpus. For example, given a set of articles reporting hurricane events, it would be useful if we could automatically discover that one of the most important relations for this domain is the *hit* relation between a hurricane and the place being hit. [Shinyama and Sekine \[2006\]](#) first proposed to study this problem, which they referred to as Unrestricted Relation Discovery. They started by collecting a large number of news articles from different news sources on the Web. They then used simple clustering based on lexical similarity to find articles talking about the same event. This way they could enrich the feature representation of an entity using its multiple occurrences in different articles. Next they performed syntactic parsing and extracted named entities from these

articles. Each named entity could then be represented by a set of syntactic patterns as its features. For example, a pattern may indicate that the entity is the subject of the verb *hit*. Finally, they clustered pairs of entities co-occurring in the same article using their feature representations. The final results were tables in which rows corresponded to different articles and columns corresponded. They were able to achieve around 75% of accuracy for the discovered tables.

Rosenfeld and Feldman [2007] formulated unsupervised relation discovery in a more general way. They assumed that the input of the problem consists of entity pairs together with their contexts. An unsupervised relation discovery algorithm clusters these entity pairs into disjoint groups where each group represents a single semantic relation. There is also a garbage cluster to capture unrelated entity pairs or unimportant relations. The contexts for each entity pair consist of the contexts of each entity and the contexts of the two entities' co-occurrences. An entity pair can be represented by a set of features derived from the contexts. Rosenfeld and Feldman considered only surface pattern features. For example, "arg1, based in arg2" is a pattern to capture a co-occurrence context between the two entities. For clustering, Rosenfeld and Feldman considered hierarchical agglomerative clustering and K-means clustering. Their method was able to discover relations such as *DesMoines CityOfState Iowa* and *staff EmployedIn clinical departments*.

While relation discovery considers binary relations only, a more complex task is to automatically induce an information extraction template, which may contain multiple slots playing different semantic roles. The most straightforward solution is to identify candidates of role fillers first and then cluster these candidates into clusters. However, this simplified clustering approach does not consider an important observation, which is that a single document tends to cover different slots. To remedy this problem, Marx et al. [2002] proposed a cross-component clustering algorithm for unsupervised information extraction. The algorithm assigns a candidate from a document to a cluster based on the candidate's feature similarity with candidates from other documents only. In other words, the algorithm prefers to separate candidates from the same document into different clusters. Leung et al. [2011] proposed a generative model to capture the same intuition. Specifically, they assume a prior distribution over the cluster labels of candidates in the same document where the prior prefers a diversified label assignment. Their experiments show that clustering results are better with this prior than without using the prior.

The aforementioned two studies assume a single template and do not automatically label the discovered slots. Chambers and Jurafsky [2011] presented a complete method that is able to discover multiple templates from a corpus and give meaningful labels to discovered slots. Specifically, their method performs two steps of clustering where the first one groups lexical patterns that are likely to describe the same type of events and the second one groups candidate role fillers into slots for each type of events. A slot can be labeled using the syntactic patterns of the corresponding slot fillers. For example,

one of the slots discovered by their method for the bombing template is automatically labeled as “Person/Organization who raids, questions, discovers, investigates, diffuses, arrests”. A human can probably infer from the description that this refers to the police slot.

Relation discovery and template induction usually work on a corpus from a single domain, e.g. articles describing terrorism events, because the goal is to discover the most salient relations from such a domain-specific corpus. In some cases, however, the goal is to find all the potentially useful facts from a large and diverse corpus such as the Web. This is the focus of open information extraction (OIE), first introduced by [Banko et al. \[2007\]](#).

Open information extraction does not assume any specific target relation type. The sole input to an OIE system is a corpus, and its output is a set of extracted relations. It makes a single pass over the corpus (thus guaranteeing the scalability with the size of the corpus) and tries to extract as many relations as possible. Because no relation type is specified in advance, part of the extraction results is a phrase that describes the relation extracted. In other words, open information extraction generates $\langle arg1, rel, arg2 \rangle$ tuples. The following example describes 2 distinct relations R1 (*location relation*) and R2 (“called” relation) between *Bletchley Park* and *Station X* :

- (21) a. R1: Bletchley Park, *was location of* , Station X
- b. R2: Bletchley Park, *being called* , Station X
- c. R2: Bletchley Park, *known as* , Station X
- d. R2: Bletchley Park, *codenamed* , Station X

[Banko et al. \[2008\]](#) introduced an unlexicalized CRF-based method for open information extraction. Conditional random fields (CRFs) are a class of statistical modelling method often applied in pattern recognition and machine learning, where they are used for structured prediction. Whereas an ordinary classifier predicts a label for a single sample without regard to “neighboring” samples, a CRF can take context into account; e.g., the linear chain CRF popular in natural language processing predicts sequences of labels for sequences of input samples. Banko’s method is based on the observation that although different relation types have very different semantic meanings, there exists a small set of syntactic patterns that cover the majority of semantic relation mentions.

- (22) a. E1 Verb E2 e.g. X *established* Y
- b. E1 NP Prep E2 e.g. X *settlement with* Y
- c. E1 Verb Prep E2 e.g. X *moved to* Y
- d. E1 to Verb E2 e.g. X *plans to acquire* Y
- e. E1 Verb E2 Noun e.g. X *is* Y *winner*
- f. E1 (*and* or *,* or *–* or *:*) E2 NP e.g. X-Y *deal*

- g. E1 (*and* or *,*) E2 Verb e.g X , Y *merge*
- h. E1 NP (*:* or *,*)? E2 X *hometown* : Y

According to [Banko et al. \[2008\]](#), the syntactic patterns reported in example 22 covers nearly 95% of semantic relation mentions.

It is therefore possible to train a relation extraction model that extracts arbitrary relations. The key is not to include lexical features in the model. Later work on open information extraction introduced more heuristics to improve the quality of the extracted relations. For example, [Fader et al. \[2011\]](#) proposed the following two heuristics:

1. A multi-word relation phrase must begin with a verb, end with a preposition, and be a contiguous sequence of words in the sentence (e.g. *is the author of*, *has a cameo in*, *made a deal with*, *took control over*, *gave gave birth to*).
2. A binary relation phrase (arg1, relation phrase, arg2) ought to appear with at least a minimal number of distinct argument pairs in a large corpus.

It is found that the two heuristics can effectively lead to better extraction results.

As I thoroughly explained in this chapter, Relation Extraction is a fundamental task in Natural Language Processing. There are NLP applications (i.e. ontology engineering, question answering) that need to turn unstructured text into structured text by annotating semantic information. We would like to have a computer annotate all data with the structure of our interest. Normally, we are interested in relations between entities, such as person, organization, and location. Examples of relations are *is-a* and *location*. Current state-of-the-art named entities recognizers (NER) can automatically label data with high accuracy. However, the whole relation extraction process is still not a trivial task. The computer needs to know how to recognize a piece of text having a semantic property of interest in order to make a correct annotation. Thus, extracting semantic relations between entities in natural language text is a crucial step towards natural language understanding applications. We here described the evolution in Relation Extraction techniques, starting from supervised methods (that require a great amount of pre-encoded data), to unsupervised methods.

As already explained in the Introduction, the purpose of this whole research work is to evaluate the capability of Distributional Models (that we introduced and described in Chapter 3) in extracting and classifying paradigmatic relations. Applying Distributional Models to this task would result in a unsupervised method for Relation Extraction, with all the advantages that it would imply (i.e. avoiding the necessity of human expertise and being less time consuming). Also, this task could be very interesting from a research point-of-view. As we explained in Chapter 2, there are paradigmatic relations (such as hypernymy and antonymy) that, for their intrinsic linguistic properties, presents challenges in being extracted with Distributional Methods. We then would like to prove

that Distributional Methods are an efficient way to perform unsupervised Relation Extraction, even when dealing with hypernymy and antonymy.

Chapter 5

Collecting data about Semantic Relations

5.1 Collecting data Using Amazon Mechanical Turk

During the development of this thesis we conducted an experiment aimed at collecting data about semantic relations using Amazon Mechanical Turk¹. The experiment was carried out in collaboration with the “Institute for Natural Language Processing” of the University of Stuttgart. Data were collected for the German language (University of Stuttgart) and for the English language (University of Pisa).

The adopted methodology was that of elicitation experiments (Paradis et al. [2009]). The purpose of the experiment was that of gathering antonyms, synonyms and hypernyms with respect to a list of target words. Users on Amazon Mechanical Turk were proposed with sets of stimuli and were asked to provide the most appropriate antonym, hypernym and synonym according to their intuition.

5.1.1 Stimuli Selection

This experiment was carried out in collaboration with the “Institute for Natural Language Processing” of the University of Stuttgart. Data for this experiment were collected both for German and English. In order to make it possible to use the very same selection criteria for both languages, we used aligned WordNet for the two languages as the data source. For English, data selection was performed using WordNet² (Fellbaum [1998]), in its later version, 3.01. WordNet is made of 155287 unique strings, 117659 synsets and 206941 total word–sense pairs. For German, experiments were carried out

¹<https://www.mturk.com>

²<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

on GermaNet³ (Hamp and Feldweg [1997], Henrich and Hinrichs [2010]), which at the time contained 93246 synsets 121810 unique strings 110738 word–sense pairs.

First, German data were collected by Sabine Schulte Im Walde at the University of Stuttgart. She set up a list of criteria for the selection of data, so that data contained a balanced amount of instances across word categories (noun, verbs and adjectives), also taking into account corpus frequency, degree of ambiguity and semantic classes. For the English data, we followed the same criteria used for German, in order to maintain comparability.

We worked on Wordnet Databases file, publicly available on the WordNet website⁴. First of all, we generated a list for all names, adjectives and verbs contained in the English WordNet database. Once these lists were available, we computed the total number of different senses for each word in the lists.

For each word in each list, we computed its frequency in a reference corpus. Reference corpora for both languages were members of the WaCky corpora collection (Baroni et al. [2009]), made of very large corpora of English (ukWaC), German (deWaC) and Italian (itWaC). These corpora were built by web crawling, they contain basic linguistic annotation (part-of-speech tagging and lemmatization) and aim to serve as general-purpose resources for the target languages. For German, the reference corpus was deWac. It is made of approximately 880 million words and built using text extracted from web pages with the “.de” domain. For English, the selected reference corpus was ukWac, a corpus made of approximately 2 billion words, built using text extracted from web pages with the “.co.uk” domain. We then computed the exact number of stimuli needed for the experiment. 99 stimuli were used for each class of words.

The number of stimuli was chosen according to the following criteria: we decided to set up three frequency ranges for each Part of Speech (thus obtaining $3 \times 3 = 9$ total categories) and then selected 11 stimuli for each category, for a total of 99 stimuli. The three frequency window have been selected as follows: 200 to 2999, 3000 to 9999 and >10000 . The first frequency window then consists of words with a frequency higher of 200, but under 3000; the second frequency range consists of words attested in the corpus with a frequency included between 3000 and 10000 (words that have a frequency of 10000 are not included in this range). In the third frequency range there are words with a frequency equal or greater than 10000.

We also selected three different polisemy ranges: 1, 2 and >2 . The first group included all those words which had only one synset in WordNet, the second group words which had two synsets in WordNet and the third group words that had three or more synsets in WordNet.

We determined the number of words that should be selected with respect to each semantic class (*adjective/noun/verb*) of each word class. We performed this selection accounting for 2 semantic classes for adjectives (*all* and *pert*—that is general and pertonym

³<http://www.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/GermaNet/>

⁴<http://wordnet.princeton.edu/wordnet/download/current-version/>

adjectives), 15 semantic classes for verbs and 23 semantic classes for nouns, as represented in Appendix A. The selected number has been fixed by computing a proportion over the number of words of each semantic class. For example, the German adjective class contains 996 different words, while the total number of adjectives, pertaining to all the semantic classes is 8582. Since we fixed 99 to be the maximum number of stimuli to gather, we would like to have

$$99 \times 996/8582 = 11 \tag{5.1}$$

adjectives for this semantic class.

Then, we performed a random choice of the stimuli for each of the groups. Obviously, this selection has been performed accounting of the different semantic classes (names, verbs and adjectives), the frequency and polysemy ranges.

5.1.2 Data Collection

The data collection experiment has been carried out using Amazon Mechanical Turk (MTurk).

MTurk is an online crowdsourcing service that enables individuals and companies (known as *Requesters*), to coordinate the use of human intelligence to perform tasks that computers are currently unable to do. The *Requesters* post tasks known as *HITs* (Human Intelligence Tasks), such as choosing the best among several photographs of a storefront, writing product descriptions, or identifying performers on music CDs. *Workers* (called *Providers* in Mechanical Turk’s Terms of Service, or, more colloquially, *Turkers*) can then browse among existing tasks and complete them for a monetary payment set by the *Requester*.

In our experiment, human associations were collected for different semantic relation types, where AMT workers were asked to propose suitable synonyms, antonyms, and hypernyms for each of the targets. Our experiment consisted in various HITs, organized as follows. For each of our 3×99 adjective, noun, and verb targets, we asked 10 participants to propose a suitable synonym, antonym, and hypernym. Targets were bundled randomly in 9 batches per word class, each including 9 targets plus two ‘non-words’. The experiment consisted of separate runs for each relation type to avoid confusion between them, with participants first generating synonyms, then antonyms, and finally hypernyms for the targets, resulting in $3 \text{ word classes} \times 99 \text{ targets} \times 3 \text{ relations} \times 10 \text{ participants} = 8,910$ target–response pairs. To control for non-native speakers of English and spammers, each batch of HITs included two examples of ‘non-words’ (invented words following English morphotactics such as *ahsence* or *cerries*) in a random position. If participants did not recognize the invented words, we assumed they were not English speakers, and so we excluded all their ratings from consideration.

For each target, the *turkers* were invited to provide the answer that, according to

their native speaker knowledge, appeared to be the better suited synonym, antonym and hyponym of the provided word. An example of this is represented in Figure 5.1. The figure represents one of the eleven stimuli proposed in a HIT aimed at gathering synonyms of English words. We explained what we mean with the term *synonym*, providing a definition and some examples, we also highlighted the conditions we imposed for the experiments.

The *Turker* that is conducting the experiment is invited to write what he thinks it is the better suited synonym for the word under examination, in the blank space and then submit it. If the target word is one of the two *non-words* and the *Turker* does not recognize it, he should check the “I don’t know” box. In order to have a good feedback (useful in case there might be the need for developing new experiments like the one described here), we also implemented a “comment box” in which the *Turkers* could write doubts and suggestions about the target.

In order to consider a HIT as *completed*, the *Turker* had to provide an answer for each of the eleven proposed target.

Synonyms of English Nouns

Synonyms are words that have the same meaning to a large extent

Examples of synonyms:

- *enemy - foe*
- *help - aid*
- *trash - garbage*

Task: ***Suggest a synonym for a target noun***

Important Notes:

- Only for **native English Speakers**
- Please, complete **all the 11 HITs**.
- The test also contains some items that native speakers can identify as “invented words”. In such case, please select the “I don't know” field below.

Synonym of cat :

I don't know *cat* !

Comments?

Submit

FIGURE 5.1: Screenshot of a proposed stimulus for synonym selection using AMT

The only restriction applied for *Turkers* selection was their being English native speakers. So, the system (AMT) proposed the experiments only to those *Turkers* who set English as their mother tongue while registering their profile on the Amazon Mechanical Turk website.

Generated word pairs distribute across word classes and relations in this way: the

total number per class and relation is 990 tokens ($99 \text{ targets} \times 10 \text{ participants}$). From the maximum number of generated pairs, a total 439 tokens were discarded because the participants provided no response. For example, **nine** out of **ten** participants failed to provide an antonym for the adjective *corneal*. Also, for each stimulus, more than a user could have provided the same answer. For example, for the adjective *unrefined*, **5 users** provided the answer *refined*. The table reported in Figure 5.2 shows the number of answer types, for each word-class, compared to the number of total answers.

	ANT		HYP		SYN		<i>all</i>	
	types	tokens	types	tokens	types	tokens	types	tokens
ADJ	507	990	720	990	691	990	1918	2970
NOUN	649	990	607	990	546	990	1802	2970
VERB	674	990	641	990	588	990	1903	2970
<i>all</i>	1830	2970	1968	2970	1825	2970	5623	8910

FIGURE 5.2: Generated pairs across word-classes

Another interesting case to take into consideration, is that of pairs that were generated with regard to different relations but for the same target word. If more than one participant generates a pair with regard to the target relation x and more than one participant generated the same pair with regard to relation y , then exists a significant intersection between the tokens. When the intersection is only 1, that is when the pair is classified with regard to one of the two (or more) target relations just once, it might be the result of an erroneously generated pair, so we decided to consider only pairs of ambiguous responses with intersection > 1 .

The following are examples of ambiguous responses with intersection > 1 , generated for *noun* targets:

- (23) a. *leaflet-book* which is generated three times with respect to the antonymy relation and three times with respect to the hyponymy relation
- b. *audition-performance* which is generated twice with respect to the antonymy relation and twice with respect to the hyponymy relation
- c. *tomato-vegetable* which is generated twice with respect to the antonymy relation and twice with respect to the hyponymy relation
- d. *zebra-horse* which is generated three times with respect to the antonymy relation and twice with respect to the hyponymy relation
- e. *skyline-horizon* which is generated twice with respect to the antonymy relation, three times with respect to the hyponymy relation and seven times with respect to the synonymy relation

Examples of ambiguous responses with intersection > 1 , generated for *verb* targets, are the following:

- (24) a. *to contrast–to compare* which is generated four times with respect to the antonymy relation, four times with respect to the hyponymy relation and twice with respect to the synonymy relation
- b. *to park–to drive* which is generated eight times with respect to the antonymy relation and twice with respect to the hyponymy relation

In our data, there are no cases of adjectives target that generate ambiguous responses.

An analysis of the number of different antonyms, hypernyms and synonyms generated for a given target shows that, on average, 6.14 different antonyms were generated for the targets, and 6.13 synonyms were generated for the targets; while hypernyms received more (6.62) different responses on average. However, the distribution of the numbers of different antonym, hypernym, and synonym responses across the targets shows that the antonymy generation task resulted in more targets with a small number of different responses compared to the synonymy and the hypernym task. There are 5 targets for which all ten participants generated the same antonym, as in the following example:

- (25) a. impure–pure
- b. left–right
- c. maximum–minimum
- d. goodbye–hello
- e. to export–to import

For hypernyms, there is only one target for which each participant provided the same response:

- (26) a. kiwi–fruit

There are 3 targets for which all ten participants provided the same synonym as answer:

- (27) a. educator–teacher
- b. to scribe–to write
- c. maximum–minimum
- d. to try–to attempt

Figure 5.3, shows the number of targets against the number of different responses.

FIGURE 5.3: Number of targets against the number of different responses

Lastly, we compared the number of blank responses (types and tokens) regarding antonyms, hypernyms and synonyms. Across word classes, 102/233 targets (types/-tokens) received blank antonym responses, 50/78 targets received blank hypernym responses and 77/127 targets received blank synonym responses, as to indicate that participants find it harder to come up with antonyms responses.

Breaking the proportions down by word class, Figure 5.4, demonstrates that in each case the number of missing antonyms (top: types; bottom: tokens) is larger than those of missing hypernyms/synonyms. Figure 5.4 also shows that the difficulty to provide relation pairs varies across word classes. Also, there are more blank responses regarding adjectives and nouns, in comparison to verbs.

FIGURE 5.4: Blank responses

All the above described analysis have been carried out on German Data too. The results are available in [Scheible and Schulte im Walde \[2014\]](#).

5.2 Using collected data to verify the distributional properties of Paradigmatic Relations

The data we collected in the AMT experiment were used to perform a study aimed at exploring the distributional properties and the distributional behavior of the paradigmatic relations we decided to examine in this work (that is, in particular, *antonymy* and *hyponymy*). The distributional behavior of the antonymy relation has been examined not only per se, but also with respect to the distributional behavior of the synonymy relation, since, to date, there very few successful attempts in distinguishing the antonymy relation from the synonymy one, using standard distributional models.

[Mohammad et al. \[2008\]](#) discovered that distributional similarity measures typically fail to distinguish synonyms from contrastive pairs of words. They have in fact verified

this phenomenon by applying a semantic similarity measure to a set of pairs of highly contrasting antonyms, synonyms and to word pairs linked by a random relation. Word pairs linked by antonymy and word pairs linked by synonymy tended to distribute in a more similar way in texts, with respect to what happened between antonyms and word pairs linked by the random relation and synonyms and word pairs linked by random relation.

Miller and Charles [1991] performed a substitution experiment, in which the relation between semantic similarity and contexts has been investigated, for pairs of names. The results show that, on average, for words of the same language pertaining to the same syntactic and semantic categories, if two words can be replaced one with the other in the same contexts, their meaning is judged to be similar. Based on the results of this experiment, therefore, there must be contextual clues that allow speakers to distinguish between synonyms and antonyms. These differences, however, are not captured by the current semantic similarity measures, leading to the hypothesis that antonymy and synonymy are distributionally similar, making it difficult to use distributional methods for the classification of the antonymy relation.

The purpose of this research work, however, is to discover a way of distinguish antonyms from synonyms distributional. We then wanted to model the distributional behavior of both these relations and outline their similarities and their differences.

5.2.1 The Experiment

For this analysis we used a very large corpus, formed from the union of three corpora of contemporary, generic English. This corpus merge the British National Corpus (BNC), together with the ukWac corpus and the whole English Wikipedia. The BNC⁵ (Burnard [2007]) consists of 100 million words. The ukWaC corpus has been described in paragraph 5.1.1. It was collected with the purpose of being used as a corpus representative of common language, comparable, with regard to the heterogeneity of the documents, to the balanced traditional resources. The Wikipedia corpus was obtained by downloading the entire English Wikipedia online encyclopedia⁶, and consists of about 600 million words. All the corpora have been POS-tagged and lemmatized. As a test set, we decided to use pairs of antonyms, synonyms and hypernyms gathered using AMT, as described in the previous section. We decided to assume that the “best” answer for each target was the one that reported the highest frequency, that is the one that was produced by most subjects. For example, when asked to provide the most– suited antonym for the stimulus *unrefined*, five people agreed on the answer *refined*. We then chose *refined* as the antonym of *unrefined* in our analysis. We assumed that, if a consistent number of users agreed on a certain answer, that answer is perceived as the best one for the given target

⁵<http://www.natcorp.ox.ac.uk/>

⁶http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Main_Page

with respect to the semantic relation under consideration. We performed this selection with respect to all the provided stimuli, in order to obtain three lists, one containing the targets and the most frequent antonym for each target, one containing the targets and the most frequent synonym for each target and one containing the targets together with the most frequent hypernym for each target. Each of these lists contained targets belonging to the three different word classes we selected, that is adjectives, nouns and verbs.

Since the purpose of the experiment was to verify the distributional properties of paradigmatic relations, we searched in our corpus for the occurrences and contexts of each word composing the pairs for each semantic relation, in order to build, for each word, a word–context matrix following the criteria described in Chapter 3. We used PMI instead of raw frequency as association measure. For each pair of words, we computed both the PMI and the Cosine within the co–occurrence vectors representing the words.

We chose to analyze both these measures in order to have a more complete picture of the distributional properties and behavior of the paradigmatic relations under examination. In fact, PMI measures the degree of association between two words. Therefore it provides a good indicator of how frequently two words tend to occur together in the same context (or word–window). Cosine measures instead the degree of similarity of the contexts in which two words appear. We computed these measures using two different context–windows: a 5 words window context and a “sentence” window context. Using a 5 words window context means that each distributional vector is built measuring the strength of association between the target word and 5 full words (names, adjectives and verbs) that occur before and after it. Using a “sentence” window context means that, in order to build the distributional vectors, we measure the strength of association between each word under examination and all full words that co–occur with it in a sentence.

In order to evaluate how well the selected measures perform with respect to the three semantic relations we wanted to study, we performed a boxplot analysis on the reported results. Boxplots display the median of a distribution as a thick horizontal line within a box extending from the first to the third quartile, with whiskers covering 1.5 of the interquartile range in each direction from the box, and values outside this extended range - extreme outliers - plotted as circles (these are the default boxplotting option of the R statistical package).

As can be seen in Figure 5.5 PMI better classify antonyms and synonyms with respect to hypernymy, while Cosine better classifies synonyms and hypernyms with respect to antonymy.

An interesting fact that emerges from these data is that Cosine and PMI performs oppositely with respect to antonyms and synonyms. Indeed, the Cosine measure seems better suited to classify synonyms, while the PMI measure seems better suited to classify antonyms, since it reports slightly higher values for the antonymy relation than it does for the synonymy relation. These considerations subsist while dealing both with the 5 words windows and the sentence window, indicating that the size of the context does

FIGURE 5.5: Boxplot analysis performed on the values obtained using Cosine and PMI, for each of the three semantic relation.

not influence this behavior.

The fact that the PMI value is higher with respect to pair of words related by antonymy, implies that the words constituting those pairs tend to appear together in the specified context, more often than by chance. The PMI measures, indeed, the degree of probability of finding two words occurring together. From these results we can see that PMI values are also high for synonyms, implying that even synonyms tend to occur in the same contexts more often than chance. But still, according to our data, this phenomenon is less strong for synonyms than it is for antonyms.

The opposite phenomenon is reported while dealing with Cosine. The fact that the Cosine computed between the vectors representing synonyms word pairs is high, implies that synonyms tend to occur in similar contexts. Cosine values are instead lower for antonyms word pairs, implying that antonyms tend to occur in similar contexts less often than synonyms.

The above consideration on how synonyms and antonyms tend to behave in the distributional space might reveal itself useful for developing distributional measures to classify antonyms and discriminate them from synonyms in the semantic space. We then should develop a distributional measure that points out the fact that antonyms tend to occur in the **same** context, rather than in **similar** context, while synonyms behave in the opposite way.

In order to better understand how paradigmatic relations behave, we also repeated the same experiments with respect to the POS of the words constituting the pair under

examination.

FIGURE 5.6: Boxplot analysis performed on the values obtained using Cosine on a 5 words Window, for each of the three Part-Of-Speech.

We here reported only the analysis performed on the 5 words context windows, since the one performed on the sentence window context showed the very same behavior.

The cosine values reported in Figure 5.6 show that nouns and verbs confirm the antonymy–synonymy behavior previously described, while adjectives behave the opposite way, since they reported a higher value for antonym pairs than they have for synonyms.

While examining how PMI behaves with respect to the different parts of speech (Figure 5.7), we discovered that antonymic adjectives tend to frequently occur together in the same distributional space, while for synonymic adjective this co-occurrence trend is less strong.

For nouns, and verbs, this trend is inverted. Examining our results, we can see that the obtained PMI value is higher for pair of verb synonyms and noun synonyms, than the PMI value obtained with respect to verb and noun antonyms. This implies that

FIGURE 5.7: Boxplot analysis performed on the values obtained using PMI on a 5 words Window, for each of the three Part-Of-Speech.

antonym nouns and verbs tend to co-occur in the same distributional space less frequently than it happens for synonym nouns and verbs.

5.2.1.1 Additional Considerations about the experiment

All the results obtained from this experiment should be taken into account while developing distributional measures to classify hypernyms and antonyms and to distinguish antonyms from synonyms. We now have a better overview on how these semantic relations behave in the distributional space, of their similarities and differences, and we could use such information to achieve the goal we set at the beginning of this research work.

The in-depth analysis of the data gathered with the previous experiment also outlined an interesting fact. Indeed, they empirically verify the co-occurrence hypothesis, as described by [Justeson and Katz \[1991\]](#), whose work was the first to address the topic of antonymy explicitly from a corpus based perspective. Their experiment addressed

the textual underpinnings of antonymy between predicative adjectives, following up research reported by [Charles and Miller \[1989\]](#). They argued, contrary to more complex psycholinguistic theories, that the primary source of association between antonymous adjectives is the tendency for antonyms to co-occur within the same sentences in discourse. Justeson and Katz’s work supports and extends their hypothesis. The primary conclusion they draw was, indeed, that antonyms co-occur within sentences more often than would be expected by chance: 8.6 times times more often.

[Justeson and Katz \[1991\]](#) method involved searching for adjectival antonyms that [Deese \[1964\]](#) had found to be the most closely related in elicitation tests. They found that, on average, the less frequent of a pair co-occurs with the most frequent at a rate of about 7%. Their study also showed that antonyms co-occur in “parallel and often essentially identical phrases”. They offered no classificatory system, but cited sentences such as:

- (28) a. I don’t care wheter the books are **easy** or **hard**, **short** or **long**, as long as you enjoy them.
- b. To us and every nation of the Free world, **rich** or **poor**, these qualities are necessary today as never before
- c. To know is **easy** but to do is **hard**

Our results empirically verify Justeson and Katz’s assumption. Indeed, we discover that pair of words related by antonymy report an high PMI value. Having an high PMI value implies that words constituting antonym pairs tend to appear together in the specified context more often than by chance, as hypothesized by [Justeson and Katz \[1991\]](#).

Chapter 6

Distributional Semantics applied to the automatic extraction of the hyponymy and antonymy relations

As already explained in the previous Chapter, the distributional methodology is only concerned with semantic similarity. However, as [Padó and Lapata \[2003\]](#) note, the notion of semantic similarity is an easy target for criticism against distributional approaches, since it encompasses a wide range of different semantic relations, like synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, etc.

There are studies that demonstrate the psychological reality of the concept of semantic similarity. For example, [Miller and Charles \[1991\]](#) point out that people instinctively make judgments about semantic similarity when asked to do so, without the need for further explanations of the concept; people appear to instinctively understand what semantic similarity is, and they make their judgments quickly and without difficulties. Several researchers report high inter-subject agreement when asking a number of test subjects to provide semantic similarity ratings for a given number of word pairs ([Rubenstein and Goodenough \[1965\]](#), [Padó and Lapata \[2003\]](#)).

As already stated, Distributional Semantic Models (DSMs) appear to be not suited for automatically recognize paradigmatic relations, such as hyponymy or antonymy.

DSMs measure the semantic similarity between words in function of distributional similarity, which in turn can be measured by vector cosine ([Turney et al. \[2010\]](#)). However, these models are characterized by their being not able to discriminate among different kinds of semantic relations linking distributionally similar lexemes. For instance, the

nearest neighbors of “*dog*” in the vector space typically include hypernyms like “*animal*”, co-hyponyms like “*cat*”, meronyms like “*paw*”, together with other semantically related words. State of the Art DSMs account for these fact only partially. They might be able to correctly select the nearest distributional semantics neighbor of a word, but they are not able to characterize the different semantic properties of the relations existing between such words.

Distance is a symmetrical relation: the fact that a word, *A*, is close to a word *B* in the semantic space, immediately implies that *B* is close to *A*. Thus, measuring the distance between words is not very functional in describing asymmetric relations as hyponymy. Consider, for example, the pair *dog-animal*, linked by the hyponymy relation. It is possible to assume that if being a *dog* implies being an *animal*, being an *animal* does not imply being a *dog*, since *animal* is a broader term than *dog*. Hypernyms are semantically broader than their hyponyms at the extensional level, (that means that *animal* refers to a broader range of entities than *dog*). Taking into account the intensional level, however, the hyponym of a term appears to be more informative than its hypernym (properties referring to *dog* are more informative than those referring to *animal*, one can indeed assume that properties that are true for *dog* are not true for all *animals*, e.g. bark), then the concepts pertaining to the superordinate levels are less informative with respect to the concepts pertaining to the basic levels. Considering the concepts as being organized in a hierarchy of categories, ranging from the extremely generic to the more specific, we can assume that the generic class includes a higher number of elements. More specific categories allow greater accuracy in the categorization of the members: knowing that something is a *dog* allows us to infer a great number of properties of such element. Of all possible categories in a hierarchy, the basic level represents a compromise between the accuracy in the classification provided by the more generic level and the predictive power of the more specific levels (Murphy [2003]).

Recently, several models have been proposed for the distributional representation of asymmetric relations (Weeds et al. [2004], Clarke [2009]), based on the Distributional Inclusion Hypothesis, also used by Kotlerman et al. [2010] for the identification of Lexical Entailment (lexical implication). Lexical Entailment models relations like *refers to* and *implies* and is part of a more general theoretical framework for the semantic inference, called Textual Entailment.

Textual Entailment (textual implication) is a modeling paradigm for semantic inference appeared in recent years (Giampiccolo et al. [2007]). It can be used in a wide spectrum of applications, such as information extraction and document retrieval. Textual entailment is a directional relationship between two text fragments, *t* and *h*: *t* implies *h* if the speaker that reads *t* infer that *h* is very probably true (Dagan et al. [2006]) For example given the sentence “All the tickets for The Beatles concert in Liverpool have been sold”, we can deduce that the Beatles have held a concert in Liverpool.

Regarding the antonymy relation, at this time there have been very few attempts at distinguishing the synonyms from antonyms using standard distributional models.

This is probably due to the fact that antonyms and synonyms tend to occur in similar contexts. In Chapter 5, we briefly introduced the experiment conducted by [Mohammad et al. \[2008\]](#), who found that the standard distributional similarity measures typically fail to distinguish synonyms from contrastive pairs of words. They also found that, on average, antonymy pairs tend to have a higher degree of distributional similarity, with respect to synonym pairs.

Recently, researches have imposed a strict distinction between semantic similarity and semantic correlation (semantic relatedness). Semantic relatedness is a more general concept than that of semantic similarity; similar entities are semantically related by virtue of their similarity (*bank-trusting company*), but dissimilar entities might still be semantically related; they might be related by meronymy (*machine-wheel*), antonymy (*hot-cold*), by any other functional relation or frequent association in their contexts of use (*pencil-paper*) ([Budanitsky and Hirst \[2006\]](#)). Antonyms belong to the larger category of semantic relatedness and therefore, semantic similarity measures should not be used in order to identify this type of relation, as shown by [Lin et al. \[2003\]](#). These measures have proved effective in identifying pairs of words related by the synonymy relation while they proved to be even less accurate in classifying antonyms and dissimilar words, since they classified them repeatedly as semantically similar words.

However, despite the fact that all these difficulties make antonyms classification using DSMs a really challenging topic, only a few studies have been carried out with the purpose of distinguishing antonyms from synonyms. Instead, the majority of studies have focused exclusively on the synonymy relation (eg. [Edmonds \[1997\]](#)) or the antonymy relation ([De Marneffe et al. \[2008\]](#)).

Most of the work about the automatic antonymy identification is based on the co-occurrence hypothesis, proposed by [Charles and Miller \[1989\]](#), and relies on pattern based approaches (which, as stated on the previous chapter, are semi-supervised approaches).

6.1 Experiments on using Distributional Techniques for analyzing the hyponymy relation

The purpose of this experiment is to explore the possibility of identifying hypernyms in DSMs with directional (or asymmetric) similarity measures ([Kotlerman et al. \[2010\]](#)). These measures all rely on some variation of the Distributional Inclusion Hypothesis ([Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Dagan \[2005\]](#)), a refined version of the distributional similarity hypothesis which relate distributional behavior with lexical entailment. According to this theory, if the meaning of a word v entails another word w then it is expected that all the typical contexts (features) of v will also occur with w . That is, the characteristic contexts of v are expected to be included within all w 's contexts (but not necessarily amongst the most characteristic ones for w). Conversely, the theory envisages that if v 's characteristic contexts are included within all w 's contexts, then it is likely that the

meaning of v does entail w .

We can then assume that, if w is a semantically narrower term than v , a significant number of salient distributional features of w is included in the feature vector of v as well. Since hypernymy is an asymmetric relation and hypernyms are semantically broader terms than their hyponyms, then we can predict that directional similarity measures are better suited to identify terms related by the hypernymy relation. Fully unsupervised hypernym identification with DSMs is still a largely open field. Various models to represent hypernyms in vector spaces have been proposed during the years (Weeds and Weir [2003], Weeds et al. [2004], Clarke [2009], Santus et al. [2014a]), usually grounded on the Distributional Inclusion Hypothesis.

The same hypothesis has been adopted by Kotlerman et al. [2010] to identify (substitutable) lexical entailment. Within the context of the Textual Entailment (TE) paradigm, Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Dagan [2005, 2009] define (substitutable) lexical entailment as a relation holding between two words, if there are some contexts in which one of the words can be substituted by the other and the meaning of the original word can be inferred from the new one. This notion of lexical entailment is more general and looser than hypernymy. In fact, it encompasses several standard semantic relations such as synonymy, hypernymy, metonymy, some cases of meronymy, etc.

Differently from Kotlerman et al. [2010], in this experiment we focus on applying directional, asymmetric similarity measures to identify hypernyms. We assume the classical definition of a hypernymy, such that Y is an hypernym of X if and only if X is a kind of Y , or equivalently every X is a Y .

The main purpose of the experiment reported below is to investigate the ability of two directional similarity measures we implemented, in identifying the hypernyms of a given target noun, and in discriminating hypernyms from terms related by symmetric semantic relations, such as coordinate terms, comparing them with state of the art directional similarity measures.

Weeds and Weir [2003] and Weeds et al. [2004] proposed a precision measure, denoted here *WeedsPrec*, for identifying the hyponymy relation and other generalization/specification cases. It quantifies the weighted coverage (or inclusion) of the candidate hyponyms features (u) by the hypernyms (v) features.

$$WeedsPrec(u, v) = \frac{\sum_{f \in F_u \cap F_v} w_u(f)}{\sum_{f \in F_u} w_u(f)} \quad (6.1)$$

The assumption behind *WeedsPrec* is that if one word is indeed a generalization of the other then the features of the more specific word are likely to be included in those of the more general one (but not necessarily vice versa).

Szpektor and Dagan [2008] tried identifying the entailment relation between lexical-syntactic templates using *WeedsPrec*, but observed that it tends to promote unreliable relations involving infrequent templates. To remedy this, they proposed to balance the directional *WeedsPrec* measure by multiplying it with the symmetric LIN measure (Lin

[1998]), denoted here *balPrec*:

$$balPrec(u, v) = \sqrt{LIN(u, v) * WeedsPrec(u, v)} \quad (6.2)$$

In the experiment that is going to be described next, we use *cosWeeds*, a measure that is a close variant of *balPrec*. It corresponds to the geometrical average of *WeedsPrec* and the symmetric similarity between *u* and *v*, measured by their vectors cosine:

$$cosWeeds(u, v) = \sqrt{cos(u, v) * WeedsPrec(u, v)} \quad (6.3)$$

This is actually a variation of the previously described *balPrec* measure, the difference being that cosine is used as a symmetric similarity measure instead of the LIN measure ((Lin [1998])).

We also tested the measure henceforth called as *ClarkeDE*. In 2009 Clarke [2009] proposed a close variation of *WeedsPrec*:

$$ClarkeDE(u, v) = \frac{\sum_{f \in F_u \cap F_v} \min(w_u(f), w_v(f))}{\sum_{f \in F_u} w_u(f)} \quad (6.4)$$

Kotlerman et al. [2010] evaluated a set of directional similarity measure on a data set of valid and invalid (substitutable) lexical entailments (Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Dagan [2009]). We have represented lexical items with distributional feature vectors extracted from the *TypeDM* tensor (Baroni and Lenci [2010]). *TypeDM* is a particular instantiation of the *Distributional Memory* (*DM*) framework. In *DM*, distributional facts are represented as a weighted tuple structure *T*, a set of weighted word-link-word tuples $\langle\langle p1, l, p2 \rangle, w \rangle$ such that *p1* and *p2* are content words (e.g. nouns, verbs, etc.), *l* is a syntagmatic co occurrence links between words in a text (e.g. syntactic dependencies, etc.), and *w* is a weight estimating the statistical salience of that tuple. The weight *w* is the Local Mutual Information (LMI) (Evert [2005]) computed on link type frequency. A toy example of weighted tuple, as depicted by Baroni and Lenci [2010], is the following:

- (29) a. $\langle\langle marine, own, bomb \rangle, 40.0 \rangle$
 b. $\langle\langle marine, use, bomb \rangle, 82.1 \rangle$
 c. $\langle\langle marine, own, book \rangle, 3.2 \rangle$
 d. $\langle\langle sergeant, own, bomb \rangle, 16.7 \rangle$
 e. $\langle\langle sergeant, use, bomb \rangle, 69.5 \rangle$
 f. $\langle\langle sergeant, use, book \rangle, 10.1 \rangle$
 g. $\langle\langle teacher, use, bomb \rangle, 7.0 \rangle$
 h. $\langle\langle teacher, own, book \rangle, 48.4 \rangle$

We have evaluated the directional similarity measures on a subset of the BLESS data set (Baroni and Lenci [2011]). The set is populated with tuples expressing a relation between a **target** concept (henceforth referred to as **concept**) and a **relatum** concept (henceforth referred to as **relatum**). For instance, in the BLESS tuple *coyote-hyper-animal*, the **concept** *coyote* is linked to the **relatum** *animal* via the *hypernymy* relation (the **relatum** is a *hypernym* of the **concept**). BLESS focuses on a coherent set of basic-level nominal concrete concepts and a small but explicit set of semantic relations, each instantiated by multiple relata. Depending on the type of relation, relata can be nouns, verbs or adjectives. Moreover, BLESS also contains, for each concept, a number of random “relatum” words that are not semantically related to the concept. Thus, it also allows to evaluate a model in terms of its ability to harvest related words given a concept (by comparing true and random relata), and to identify specific types of relata, both in terms of semantic relation and part of speech.

BLESS includes 200 distinct English concrete nouns as target concepts, equally divided between living and non-living entities. Concepts have been grouped into 17 broader classes: AMPHIBIAN REPTILE (including amphibians and reptiles: *alligator*), APPLIANCE (*toaster*), BIRD (*crow*), BUILDING (*cottage*), CLOTHING (*sweater*), CONTAINER (*bottle*), FRUIT (*banana*), FURNITURE (*chair*), GROUND MAMMAL (*beaver*), INSECT (*cockroach*), MUSICAL INSTRUMENT (*violin*), TOOL (i.e., manipulable tools or devices: *hammer*), TREE (*birch*), VEGETABLE (*cabbage*), VEHICLE (*bus*), WATER ANIMAL (including fish and sea mammals: *herring*), WEAPON (*dagger*).

All 200 BLESS concepts are single-word nouns in the singular form.

While selecting terms, Baroni and Lenci [2011], chose concepts with a reasonably high frequency, avoided ambiguous or highly polysemous concepts and balanced inter- and intra-class composition. Classes include both prototypical and atypical instances (e.g., *robin* and *penguin* for BIRD), and have a wide spectrum of internal variation (e.g., the class *vehicle* contains wheeled, air and sea vehicles). The average number of concepts per class is 11.76 (median 11; min. 5 AMPHIBIAN REPTILE; max. 21 GROUND MAMMAL). For each concept noun, BLESS includes several relatum words, linked to the concept by one of the following 5 relations.

- (30)
- a. COORD: the **relatum** is a noun that is a co-hyponym (coordinate) of the concept, i.e., they belong to the same (narrowly or broadly defined) semantic class: alligator- coord-lizard;
 - b. HYPER: the **relatum** is a noun that is a hypernym of the concept: alligator-hyper- animal;
 - c. MERO: the **relatum** is a noun referring to a part/component/organ/member of the concept, or something that the concept contains or is made of: alligator-mero-mouth;
 - d. ATTRI: the **relatum** is an adjective expressing an attribute of the concept: alligator-attrib-aquatic;

- e. EVENT: the relatum is a verb referring to an action/activity/happening/event the concept is involved in or is performed by/with the concept: alligator-event-swim;

BLESS also includes the relations RAN.N, RAN.J and RAN.V, which relate the target concepts to control tuples with random noun, adjective and verb *relata*, respectively. The BLESS relations cover a wide spectrum of information useful to describe a target concept and to qualify the notion of semantic relatedness: taxonomically related entities (hyper and coord), typical attributes (*attri*), components (*mero*), and associated events (*event*). However, except for hyper and coord (corresponding to the standard relations of class inclusion and co-hyponymy respectively), the other BLESS relations are highly underspecified.

The **relata** of the non-random relations are English nouns, verbs and adjectives selected and validated by both authors using two types of sources: semantic sources (the McRae Norms (McRae et al. [2005]), WordNet (Fellbaum [1998]) and ConceptNet (Liu and Singh [2004]) and text sources (Wikipedia and the Web-derived ukWaC corpus). These resources greatly differ in dimension, origin and content and therefore provide complementary views on **relata**. As a result of the combined use of such different types of sources, the BLESS *relata* are representative of a wide spectrum of semantic information about the target concepts: they include domain-specific terms side by side to commonsense ones, very distinctive features of a concept (e.g., *hoot* for *owl*) together with attributes and events that are instead shared by a whole class of concepts (e.g., all *animals* have *relata* such as *eat*, *feed*, and *live*), prototypical features as well as events and attributes that are statistically salient for the target. For this experiment, we have used a BLESS subset formed by 14,547 tuples with the **relatum** attested in the TypeDM word set, and containing one of these relations: COORD, HYPER, MERO and RANDOM-N (corresponding to the previously described RAN.N category).

We adopted two different evaluation methods. The first is based on the methodology described in Baroni and Lenci [2011]. Given the similarity scores for a concept with all its *relata* across all relations in our test set, we pick the *relatum* with the highest score (that means the nearest neighbour of such *relata*) for each relation. This way, for each of the 200 BLESS concepts, we obtain 4 similarity scores, one per relation. In order to factor out concept-specific effects that might add to the overall score variance, we transform the 8 similarity scores of each concept onto standardized z scores (mean: 0; s.d: 1) by subtracting from each their mean, and dividing by their standard deviation.

After this transformation, we produce a boxplot summarizing the distribution of scores per relation across the 200 concepts. Boxplots for each of the above mentioned similarity measure are later on displayed.

FIGURE 6.1: Boxplot representing State of the Art distributional measures.

To identify significant differences between relation types, we also performed pairwise comparisons with the Tukey Honestly Significant Difference test, using the standard $\alpha = 0.05$ significance threshold.

In the boxplots (Figure 6.1) we can observe that all measures (either symmetric or not) are able to discriminate truly semantically related pairs from unrelated (i.e. random) ones. Crucially, *Cosine* shows a strong tendency to identify coordinates among the nearest neighbors of target items. This is actually consistent with its being a symmetric similarity measure. Instead, directional similarity measures significantly promote hypernyms over coordinates. The only exception is represented by *cosWeeds*, which again places coordinates at the top, though now the difference with hypernyms is not significant. This might be due to the cosine component of this measure, which reduces the effectiveness of the asymmetric *WeedsPrec*. From the boxplot analysis, we can therefore conclude that similarity measures based on the Distributional Inclusion Hypothesis do indeed improve hypernym identification in context-feature semantic spaces, with respect to other types of semantic relations, such as COORD.

The second type of evaluation we have performed is based on Kotlerman et al. [2010]. The similarity measures have been evaluated with Average Precision (AP), a method derived from Information Retrieval, which combines precision, relevance ranking and

overall recall. For each similarity measure, we computed AP with respect to the 4 BLESS relations. The best possible score (AP = 1) for a given relation (e.g., HYPER) corresponds to the ideal case in which all the relata belonging to that relation have higher similarity scores than the relata belonging to the other relations. For every relation, we calculated the AP for each of the 200 BLESS target concepts.

We here report the AP values averaged over the 200 concepts. On the one hand, these results confirm the trend illustrated by the boxplots, in particular the fact that directional similarity measures clearly outperform *Cosine* (or cosine-based measures such as *cosWeeds*) in identifying hypernyms, with no significant differences among them.

<i>measure</i>	COORD	HYPER	MERO	RANDOM-N
<i>Cosine</i>	0.79	0.23	0.21	0.30
<i>WeedsPrec</i>	0.45	0.40	0.31	0.32
<i>cosWeeds</i>	0.69	0.29	0.23	0.30
<i>ClarkeDE</i>	0.45	0.39	0.28	0.33

TABLE 6.1: Mean AP values for each semantic relation reported by the different similarity scores.

A whole different picture emerges by comparing the AP values for HYPER with those for COORD. In this case important distinctions among the directional measures emerge. In fact, even if *WeedsPrec* and *ClarkeDE* increase the AP for HYPER, still they assign even higher AP values to COORD.

These results show that using directional similarity measures is a promising technique for hypernymy classification; they also show that it is possible to improve. Therefore, we implemented two variations of the above measures, specifically designed to characterize the properties of the hyponymy relation.

The first implemented measure is based on the idea that we should be able to find occurrences of a broader term even in contexts in which a narrower term would not occur. The measure then takes into account not only the inclusion of u in v , but also the non-inclusion of v in u , both measured with *ClarkeDE*.

$$InvCL(u, v) = \sqrt{ClarkeDE(u, v) * (1 - ClarkeDE(v, u))} \quad (6.5)$$

The intuition behind *invCL* is that, if v is a semantically broader term of u , then the features of u are included in the features of v , but crucially the features of v are also not included in the features of u . For instance, if *animal* is a hypernym of *dog*, we can expect that a significant number of the *dog-contexts* are also *animal-contexts* (“to bark” is a feature that can easily be found among those of *animal*, but that is typical of *dogs*), and that a significant number of *animal-contexts* are not *dog-contexts* (the features of *animal* would probably include “to meow”, which is not a property of *dogs*). In fact, being a semantically broader term of *dog*, *animal* should also be found in contexts in which *animals* other than *dogs* occur.

The second measure is based on the intuition that superordinates terms apply to a

set of subordinate terms that belong to the same category. In other words, we assume that all the hyponyms of a common hypernym form a set of contrastive terms in relation with the hypernym itself. If we take into account, for instance, all the hyponyms of the term *animal*, words such as *dog*, *cat*, *horse* form a set of lower level terms with respect to *animal*. If a term v is semantically broader than a term u , then all the semantic features of u are included in those of v (for instance, the distributional features of *dog* are also present among the features of *animal*), it is also true that even the features of all the other hyponyms complementary to u with respect to v will be included among the features of v (if we consider *cat* to be complementary of *dog* with respect to their hypernym *animal*, we can assume that there are will also be many features of *cat* that appear among those of *animal*).

$$COL(u, v) = \sqrt{ClarkeDE(u, v) * (ClarkeDE(comp(u, y), v))} \quad (6.6)$$

In the previous formula, y represents the complementary term of u with respect to v . In order to compute y , we assumed that it is possible to approximate the complementary properties of a hyponym identifying its closest co-hyponym, distributionally speaking, and selecting all the features of this term (the co-hyponym) that are not included in the features of the hyponym we are examining. The hyponym's closest term was calculated using the *cosine* as the selected similarity measure (being the cosine similarity measure the one that better identifies symmetrical relations, such as that of co-hyponymy) that allowed us to identify, for each co-hyponym, its more similar hyponym. We then assumed that the hyponym under examination and its most similar co-hyponym, with respect to v , share many features. We assumed that selecting only the features of the co-hyponym that are not also present in those of the target hyponym, should provide us with a good approximation of the features of the complementary to that term is really made.

For the evaluation of these measures we used the two approaches described beforehand. The results confirmed the insights and expectations we had about directional measures.

FIGURE 6.2: Boxplot representing the new distributional measures.

The evaluation performed using the boxplot (Figure 6.2) shows the same trend as the analysis we performed on the state of the art directional measures. *invCL* and *COL* favor hypernyms significantly with respect to coordinates. In particular, analyzing *invCL* it is possible to note that, while it performs only slightly better in classifying hyponymy-hypernymy than *ClarkeDE* does, it significantly increases the ability to distinguish this relation from that of coordination, for which the performance decreases significantly. The same happens while examining the measure *COL*, that, not only increases significantly for the hyponymy-hypernymy relation, but contextually decreases with co-ordinates. *COL* then performs better the other directional measures (at least the ones at the state of the art that we analyzed in this experiment) in discriminating such relation from co-ordinates.

<i>measure</i>	COORD	HYPER	MERO	RANDOM-N
<i>Cosine</i>	0.79	0.23	0.21	0.30
<i>WeedsPrec</i>	0.45	0.40	0.31	0.32
<i>cosWeeds</i>	0.69	0.29	0.23	0.30
<i>ClarkeDE</i>	0.45	0.39	0.28	0.33
<i>invCL</i>	0.38	0.40	0.31	0.34
<i>COL</i>	0.36	0.42	0.32	0.30

TABLE 6.2: Mean AP values for each semantic relation reported by the different similarity scores, included the two directional measures developed for the hypernymy relation.

The evaluation we performed using Average Precision showed that the measures we implemented report significantly better results with respect to state-of-the-art-measures. State of the art measures report indeed high values for the hyponymy relation, but even higher values for the co-hyponymy relation. The measures we implemented, improve the reported AP value with respect to the hypernymy relation, and they can also distinguish the hypernymy relation from the co-hypernymy relation.

Both *invCL* and *COL* report higher AP scores with respect to state-of-the-art directional measures, and, most importantly, they report significantly lower values for the

co-hyponymy relation. Such values are even lower if compared to the values reported for the hyponymy relation. Among the two measures we here implemented, *COL* is the one that performs better, since it greatly increases the gap between the Average Precision score reported for the hyponymy relation and the score reported for the co-hyponymy relation.

These two measures then confirm our starting hypothesis, and prove that directional similarity measures are a good starting point for recognizing and classifying the hypernymy relation in a non-supervised way.

6.2 Introductory experiments for the distributional semantics processing of antonyms

As already pointed out in the previous chapters of this work, Distributional Semantic Models (DSMs) have often been exploited for their well known ability to identify semantically similar lexemes using corpus-derived co-occurrences encoded as distributional vectors (Santus et al. [2014a]; Baroni and Lenci [2010]; Turney et al. [2010]; Padó and Lapata [2007]). The automatic identification of semantic relations is a core task in computational semantics. These models represent lexical semantic similarity in function of distributional similarity, which can be measured by vector cosine (Turney et al. [2010]). As previously explained, these models are characterized by the difficulty to discriminate among different kinds of semantic relations linking distributionally similar lexemes. The identification of the antonymy relation adds another difficulty to the aforementioned problem: the fact that synonyms and antonyms tend to arrange themselves in texts in a similar way, or better, to occur in similar contexts. A good example of this fact could be represented by the pair of antonym adjectives “*new/old*”. The occurrence of a sentence like “I lost my new hat” it’s just as probable as the occurrence of “I lost my old hat” . This is the main reason why, using distributional methods does not reveal itself useful for extracting antonyms from text. In a context like the one described above, distributional methods would probably be inefficient also for distinguishing synonyms from antonyms. The following example shows, indeed, that the distributional neighbors of an adjective in the semantic space, could be both synonyms and antonyms. In fact, the closest neighbor of the word “good” in the semantic space here depicted, is its antonym, “bad” .

Good (window size=2)	
bad	0.68
excellent	0.66
superb	0.48
poor	0.45
improved	0.43
improve	0.43
perfect	0.42
clever	0.42
terrific	0.42
lucky	0.41
smashing	0.41
improving	0.41
wonderful	0.41

TABLE 6.3: Table showing the distributional neighbor of the word “Good”

One possible solution to this problem is to apply is to identify some distributional peculiarities of this relation and try to model them into a distributional measure (a similar approach has been carried out in order to recognize the hypernym/hyperonym relation). Recently, a similar idea has been exploited by Santus et al. [2014b]. They introduced APAnt, a new Average-Precision-based distributional measure that is able to successfully discriminate antonyms from synonyms, outperforming vector cosine and a baseline system, based on the co-occurrence hypothesis, formulated by Charles and Miller in 1989 and confirmed in other studies, such as those of Justeson and Katz [1991] and Fellbaum [1995]. The measure they implemented is based on a distributional interpretation of the so-called *paradox of simultaneous similarity and difference between the antonyms* (Cruse [1986]). According to this paradox, antonyms are similar to synonyms in every dimension of meaning except one. The hypothesis they investigated is that the different dimension of meaning is a salient one and it can be identified with DSMs and exploited for discriminating antonyms from synonyms.

Another well known problem when dealing with the unsupervised recognition of antonyms, is that people do not always agree on classifying word pairs as antonyms (Mohammad et al. [2013]), confirming that antonymy identification is a difficult task. antonymy is in fact a complex relation and opposites can be of different types, making this class hard to define (Cruse [1986]). Over the years, many scholars from different disciplines have tried to provide a precise definition of this semantic relation (as briefly introduced in Chapter 2 of this work). Since our main aim is to discriminate antonyms from synonyms, we do not focus our attention on distinguishing different types of opposites.

The foundation of most corpus-based research on antonymy is, instead, the *co-occurrence hypothesis*. This hypothesis mainly derives from an observation by Charles and Miller [1989], that antonyms tend to co-occur in the same sentence more often than expected by chance. Another large part of the research on antonym extraction has been focused on the study of lexical-syntactic constructions that can work as linguistic tests for antonymy definition and classification (Cruse [1986]). Starting from these observations, computational methods for antonymy identification were implemented. The majority of these methods rely on pattern based approaches (Schulte Im Walde and Köper [2013]; Turney [2008]; Pantel and Pennacchiotti [2006]; Lin et al. [2003]), which use specific patterns to distinguish antonymy-related pairs from others. As already explained in Chapter 4 of this work, pattern based methods are mostly semi-supervised. This implies that they require a large amount of data in order to work properly. Also, they can be applied only to frequent words, which would more probably occur with the selected patterns. Schwab et al. [2002], for example, used oppositeness vectors, which were created by identifying possible opposites relying on dictionary definitions. The approach was tested only on a few word pairs so it cannot be regarded as a general solution. Turney [2008] proposed a supervised algorithm for the identification of several semantic relations (synonyms and

opposites included). The algorithm relied on a training set of word pairs with class labels. These labels were assigned also to a testing set of word pairs. All word pairs were represented as vectors encoding the co-occurrence frequencies in textual patterns extracted from a large corpus of web pages. The system achieved an accuracy of 75% against a frequency baseline of 65.4%. [Mohammad et al. \[2008\]](#) proposed a method for determining what they have defined as the “degrees of antonymy” . This concept was aimed to reflect the results of psycholinguistic experiments, which show that some antonyms are perceived as ‘better’ (e.g. *big - small*) than others (e.g. *big - normal*). For each target word pair, they used thesaurus categories to decide whether a pair is an instance of antonymy or not. Their method then assigned the degree of antonymy using co-occurrence statistics. [Mohammad et al. \[2013\]](#) used an analogical method based on a given set of contrasting words to identify and classify different kinds of opposites by hypothesizing that for every opposing pair of words, **A** and **B**, there is at least another opposing pair, **C** and **D**, such that **A** is *similar* to **C** and **B** is *similar* to **D**. Their approach outperformed other measures. But, it is obviously not unsupervised. [Schulte Im Walde and Köper \[2013\]](#) proposed a vector space model relying on lexico-syntactic patterns to distinguish between synonymy, antonymy and hypernymy. Their approach was tested on German nouns, verbs and adjectives, achieving a precision of 59.80%, which was above the majority baselines.

[Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#) demonstrated that using suitable features, differences in the contexts of synonymous and antonymous German adjective pairs can be identified with a simple word space model. They experimented with two context settings (a simple ‘window-based model’ and a ‘co-disambiguation model’ aimed at approximate adjective sense disambiguation). Their best model achieved 70.6% accuracy in a synonym/antonym classification task, thus outperforming the 50% accuracy baseline.

The approach we have adopted is the one by [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#). Data gathered from the experiments presented in the previous Chapter, were then used as features in a classification task aimed at distinguishing antonyms from synonyms. As already proved by [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#), this approach provided interesting results, even when applied to English data (instead of German) and implemented with discriminating features that were different from those tested by the German scholars.

6.2.0.2 Uncovering Distributional Differences between synonyms and antonyms using Classification Tasks

The purpose of this work was that of repeating the experiment conducted by Scheible et al. [2013] and evaluate its performances on a different language (English instead of German), using different classification features. The goal of Scheible et al. [2013] research was to show that using suitable features antonyms and synonyms can be identified via a simple word space model, relying on contextual clues that govern the ability to distinguish the relations in context. For this purpose, they developed a word space model that exploits window-based features for synonymous and antonymous German adjective pairs. To investigate the contributions of the various parts-of-speech with regard to the word space model, they experimented with two context settings: one that takes into account all contexts in which the members of the word pairs occur, and one where they approximate context disambiguation by applying ‘co-disambiguation’: they identify the set of nouns that are modified by both members of the pair, and include only contexts in which the adjectives premodify one of the set of shared nouns.

The main goal of this research is to show that there are distributional differences between synonym and antonym pairs leading to an automatic distinction between them. The dataset they used is part of a collection of semantically related word pairs compiled via two separate experiments hosted on Amazon Mechanical Turk (AMT). The experiments were based on a set of 99 target adjectives which were selected according to the methodology described in Chapter 5.

Word space model where the members of the word pairs are represented as vectors in space, using contextual co-occurrence counts as vector dimension elements. The distributional similarity of two words is then calculated by means of the cosine function. Instead of simple co-occurrence frequencies, their model uses local mutual information (LMI) scores as vector values.

To establish whether there are significant distributional differences between synonyms and antonyms, and to assess the discriminative power of the different models, they experimented with several WEKA¹ classifiers and assessed their performance at synonym/antonym distinction using 10-fold cross-validation. They trained the classifiers using one single feature (*standard-cosine*, or *cosine-difference values*). *Cosine-difference* was computed as follows: for each synonym and antonym pair involving a target T, they calculated the difference between their cosine values and use these difference values as input to the classifier. For example, the cosine values for the synonym pair *süß* - *niedlich* and antonym pair *süß* - *sauer* are 0.94 (T:SYN) and 0.18 (T:ANT), respectively, and the difference value is calculated as (T:SYN - T:ANT). The resulting value (which may be positive or negative) is used as input for the synonym pair (here, 0.76), while the negated value is used as input for the antonym pair (-0.76).

¹Weka (Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis) is a popular suite of machine learning software written in Java, developed at the University of Waikato, New Zealand. Weka is free software available under the GNU General Public License at the following URL: www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka

The results they reported, clearly show that it is possible to automatically distinguish between synonymy and antonymy by means of a word space model, with significant improvements over the 50% baseline.

Given the results of the analysis performed in Chapter 5, we know that PMI and Cosine perform differently when used to classify antonyms and synonyms. As a brief recap, we basically discovered that PMI performed slightly better while classifying antonyms, while Cosine performed a little better in classifying synonyms. We then assumed that there could be a way of combining PMI and Cosine in order to discriminate antonyms from synonyms. We then assumed PMI and Cosine could be used as features in order to train a classifier to discriminate antonyms from synonyms.

We performed our experiment using the data collected according with the methodology described in Chapter 5. We ended up having 150 total pair of words (75 antonym pairs and 75 synonym pairs), 46 of which were made up by adjectives, 54 by names and 50 by verbs. As already explained in the previous Chapter, for each couple, we computed the distributional similarity of the two words with the cosine function. Our model uses LMI (Local Mutual Information) scores as vector values.

We consider two possible context settings: one that collects co-occurrence information from all contexts of the target words and one that investigates differences determined by having only adjectives, only nouns or only verbs as contexts of the words under examination. To establish whether there are significant distributional differences between synonyms and antonyms we experimented with all the classifiers implemented in WEKA, and assessed their performance at synonym/antonym distinction using 10-fold cross-validation.

For each of the experimental conditions described above, we have run all the classifiers five times. In the first scenario, we use two features for the classification: PMI and the Cosine. We then tested only the Cosine, and only PMI. Also, we test how the CosineDifference implemented by [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#) performs with our data and we implement a variation of it, which uses the PMI difference.

Figure 6.3 shows the results obtained for the first scenario (that is, using both PMI and Cosine as features for classification). We evaluate the performance for all the stimuli, independently of their part of speech, and for each different part of speech (nouns, adjectives, verbs) in order to try to understand if the POS of the stimuli could condition the classifiers' performances. The results are encouraging, since, like it happened for Scheible's experiments, there is more than a classifier that performs over the 50% baseline, thus confirming that is actually possible to distinct antonyms from synonyms using distributional methods. In order to affirm that these results verify our hypothesis (that is, the actual possibility to distinct antonyms from synonyms using DSMs) we need to be sure that they are statistically relevant, thus not casually obtained. In order to do that, we performed a Chi-squared test on the obtained results.

Chi-square is a statistical test commonly used to compare observed data with data

	ALL	NOUNS	ADJECTIVES	VERBS
ADTree	52,0%	46,3%	58,7%	68,0%
BFTree	56,1%	56,5%	46,7%	64,0%
DecisionStump	53,7%	54,6%	45,7%	53,0%
FT	47,6%	54,6%	42,4%	47,0%
J48	47,6%	51,9%	45,7%	55,0%
J48graft	47,6%	51,9%	45,7%	55,0%
LADTree	50,7%	51,9%	53,3%	59,0%
LMT	54,4%	55,6%	57,6%	57,0%
NBTree	47,6%	51,9%	45,7%	54,0%
RandomForest	45,6%	51,9%	55,4%	60,0%
RandomTree	47,6%	52,8%	52,2%	57,0%
REPTree	50,0%	50,9%	48,9%	60,0%
SimpleCart	55,7%	54,6%	43,5%	62,0%

FIGURE 6.3: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction using PMI and Cosine as features for training.

we would expect to obtain according to a specific hypothesis. For example, if, according to Mendel's laws, you expected 10 of 20 offspring from a cross to be male and the actual observed number was 8 males, then you might want to know about the "goodness to fit" between the observed and expected. Were the deviations (differences between observed and expected) the result of chance, or were they due to other factor? How much deviation can occur for the investigator to conclude that something other than chance is at work, causing the observed to differ from the expected? The chi-square test is always testing what scientists call the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the expected and observed result.

Chi-squared is computed as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(O_k - E_k)^2}{E_k} \quad (6.7)$$

That is, chi-square is the sum of the squared difference between observed (O_k) and the expected (E_k) data, divided by the expected data in all possible categories.

The obtained value should then be interpreted. First of all, we need to determine a relative standard to serve as the basis for accepting or rejecting the hypothesis. The relative standard commonly used in research is $p > 0.05$. The p value is the probability that the deviation of the observed from that expected is due to chance alone. In this case, using $p > 0.05$, you would expect any deviation to be due to chance alone 5% of the time or less, so for the data to be obtained in a statistically relevant way.

We performed this test on the results that are above the baseline, in order to check, as already specified, their statistical significance. The p-value we use for the test is the

FIGURE 6.4: Graphs representing WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction, with respect to the stimuli part of speech.

standard $p = 0.05$, while the assumed degree of freedom is 1.

The results of the Chi-squared test, conducted on the data obtained testing WEKA classifier using two features (Cosine and PMI) are reported in figure 6.5. While there are many reported values above the baseline, only a few of them pass the Chi-Squared test, thus being statistically significant.

The classification algorithm that performs better with all data is **BFTree**, which achieves a 56,1% of correct classification. This result is 6.1% points above the baseline, and statistically significant, thus proving our starting hypothesis, that it is actually possible to distinct antonyms from synonyms using distributional methods.

Figure 6.5 also shows that using both these two features performs even better when the test words are verbs. In this case, the best performing algorithm (which is LADTree)

	ALL	NOUNS	ADJECTIVES	VERBS
ADTree	52,0%	46,3%	58,7%	68,0%
BFTree	56,1%	56,5%	46,7%	64,0%
DecisionStump	53,7%	54,6%	45,7%	53,0%
FT	47,6%	54,6%	42,4%	47,0%
J48	47,6%	51,9%	45,7%	55,0%
J48graft	47,6%	51,9%	45,7%	55,0%
LADTree	50,7%	51,9%	53,3%	59,0%
LMT	54,4%	55,6%	57,6%	57,0%
NBTree	47,6%	51,9%	45,7%	54,0%
RandomForest	45,6%	51,9%	55,4%	60,0%
RandomTree	47,6%	52,8%	52,2%	57,0%
REPTree	50,0%	50,9%	48,9%	60,0%
SimpleCart	55,7%	54,6%	43,5%	62,0%

FIGURE 6.5: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction using PMI and Cosine as features for training - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

achieves a 68% correct answer, 18% above the designed baseline.

We then know that this two features are useful to train the classification algorithms to distinguish antonyms from synonyms. We also know that they make such algorithms perform even better when the pair of words they have to classify are constituted by verbs. Still, the performance could be improved.

How is it possible to improve the classification performance? Playing around with the features we use to train them could definitely be the answer to this question. We know, as we explained in Chapter 5, that for the majority of targets, the cosine values of their synonyms are significantly higher than those of their antonyms. We also know that PMI works the other way around, that is, for the majority of targets the reported PMI values of their antonyms is higher than those of their synonyms. We already highlighted that this situation indicates clear distributional differences. However, such information is lost when training the classifier on all cosine values (or PMI values) in cases where the cosine value of the antonym of a target **T1** is greater than the synonym value of another target **T2**, or when the synonym of a target **T1** is greater than the antonym value of another target **T2**, making it difficult to find an appropriate cut-off value to split the data in two classes. This is the reason why [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#) introduced *Cosine-difference*. In order to avoid the very same problem while dealing with PMI as a training feature, we here introduce *PMI-difference*.

PMI-difference is computed the same way as *Cosine-difference* - assuming $P:SYN$ as the PMI computed measuring the association of two words composing a synonym pair and $P:ANT$ the PMI computed measuring the association of two words composing an antonym pair, respectively, $P-DIFF=(P:ANT-P:SYN)$. Here the resulting value is used

	ALL	NOUNS	ADJECTIVES	VERBS
ADTree	48,99%	51,85%	49,32%	59%
BFTree	50,34%	50,00%	55,43%	59%
DecisionStump	55,41%	54,63%	50,00%	53%
FT	47,64%	50,93%	45,65%	50%
J48	47,64%	51,85%	45,65%	55%
J48graft	47,64%	51,85%	45,65%	55%
LADTree	49,32%	56,48%	55,43%	61%
LMT	55,07%	54,63%	50,00%	61%
NBTree	47,64%	51,85%	45,65%	54%
RandomForest	46,96%	49,07%	47,83%	54%
RandomTree	46,28%	49,07%	47,83%	54%
REPTree	51,69%	52,78%	53,26%	59%
SimpleCart	55,41%	53,70%	61,96%	63%

FIGURE 6.6: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction using Cosine as training feature - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

as input for the antonym pair, while the negated value is used as input for the synonym pair.

As we hypothesized, Cosine alone is not a good training feature to distinguish antonyms from synonyms. Figure 6.6 shows that, even if there are some algorithms that performs over the baseline using Cosine alone as a feature, they do not pass the Chi-Squared test. Cosine only perform over the baseline and pass the Chi-squared test while classifying pairs of antonyms/synonyms nouns using the Simple Cart classification algorithm and while classifying pairs of antonyms/synonyms verbs using LADTree, LMT and Simple-Cart. Also, those few algorithm that are significantly above the baseline, still report lower values than those achieved with Cosine and PMI combined.

Those data confirm the hypothesis we outlined in Chapter 5, that Cosine alone is not sufficient for distinguish synonyms from antonyms, probably due to their distributional similarity and the fact that they tend to occur in the same contexts.

A similar outcome is obtained when repeating the same test using PMI alone as feature. PMI alone is not a good training feature to distinguish antonyms from synonyms, as shown in Figure 6.7. Indeed, while trying to classify all data (i.e. pair of nouns, adjectives and verbs), there is not a single algorithm that performs over the baseline using PMI as the training feature. Things are definitely better when we use PMI to train algorithms apt to classify only nouns, or verbs. Still, these results confirms that PMI alone is not sufficient for distinguish antonyms from synonyms.

The reported data shows that pairs of verb antonyms and synonyms, could easily be

	ALL	NOUNS	ADJECTIVES	VERBS
ADTree	47,64%	50,00%	46,74%	65,00%
BFTree	45,61%	60,19%	47,83%	62,00%
DecisionStump	32,36%	48,15%	46,74%	47,00%
FT	49,32%	45,37%	45,65%	50,00%
J48	49,32%	45,37%	53,26%	50,00%
J48graft	49,32%	45,37%	53,26%	50,00%
LADTree	47,30%	57,41%	44,57%	66,00%
LMT	44,59%	53,70%	57,61%	54,00%
NBTree	49,32%	45,37%	45,65%	50,00%
RandomForest	47,64%	59,26%	50,00%	56,00%
RandomTree	47,64%	59,26%	50,00%	56,00%
REPTree	49,66%	51,85%	50,00%	58,00%
SimpleCart	47,30%	53,70%	63,04%	65,00%

FIGURE 6.7: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction using PMI as training feature - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

distinguished using Cosine-alone or, even better, PMI-alone. Each classification algorithm, trained using both Cosine-alone or PMI-alone performs significantly over the baseline while classifying antonyms/synonyms verb. This could indicate that antonym/synonym verbs have a particular distributional behavior with respect to other word-classes. Maybe the contexts they tend to occur with are less similar than it happens with other word-classes pairs, making it possible to use Cosine-alone and PMI-alone as a functioning classification feature. Anyway, we can observe that PMI still performs better than Cosine does, proving that their co-occurrence in the semantic space is determinant to distinguish antonyms from synonyms.

The results we obtain using Cosine-difference presents other peculiarities. All the algorithms we tested using this feature, seem to perform well in this task, thus confirming [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#). But just one, out of all the algorithms pass the Chi-squared test, indicating that the REPTree algorithm is the only one that, trained using Cosine-Difference as feature, could be effectively used for distinguish antonyms from synonyms.

Results shows that Cosine-Difference is a good feature to perform antonym/synonym distinction on noun pairs. Almost all the classification algorithms available in WEKA correctly classify them (reported values are, on average, 12% above the baseline) and almost all of them pass the Chi-squared test, proving that they are statistically significant. Cosine-diff is instead not suited for dealing with adjectives for which it performs poorly.

Up to now, all the features we tried seemed to work well only on particular POS. To this point, we have not yet found a measure that works well with every part of speech. Data reported in [Figure 6.9](#) contradicts this fact. This table reports all the results

	ALL	NOUNS	ADJECTIVES	VERBS
ADTree	52,70%	59,26%	48,91%	50,00%
BFTree	52,70%	62,04%	43,48%	56,25%
DecisionStump	54,39%	63,89%	42,39%	48,96%
FT	52,36%	65,74%	45,65%	47,92%
J48	52,03%	64,81%	45,65%	47,92%
J48graft	52,03%	64,81%	45,65%	47,92%
LADTree	53,38%	58,33%	56,52%	53,13%
LMT	58,45%	65,74%	44,57%	58,33%
NBTree	52,03%	63,89%	45,65%	47,92%
RandomForest	53,04%	49,07%	44,57%	70,83%
RandomTree	53,04%	49,07%	44,57%	70,83%
REPTree	55,74%	62,04%	44,57%	57,29%
SimpleCart	54,05%	63,89%	47,83%	57,29%

FIGURE 6.8: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction using COSDIFF as training feature - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

	ALL	NOUNS	ADJECTIVES	VERBS
ADTree	62,16%	48,15%	58,70%	62,50%
BFTree	59,80%	53,70%	63,04%	60,42%
DecisionStump	50,34%	52,78%	53,26%	54,17%
FT	49,32%	47,22%	44,57%	45,83%
J48	49,32%	45,37%	53,26%	44,79%
J48graft	49,32%	45,37%	53,26%	44,79%
LADTree	61,49%	54,63%	52,17%	62,50%
LMT	53,04%	61,11%	59,78%	58,33%
NBTree	49,32%	46,30%	53,26%	44,79%
RandomForest	55,74%	46,30%	71,74%	67,71%
RandomTree	55,74%	46,30%	71,74%	67,71%
REPTree	54,39%	57,41%	54,35%	57,29%
SimpleCart	61,15%	52,78%	63,04%	59,38%

FIGURE 6.9: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction using PMIDIFF as training feature - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

obtained with the PMI-Difference measure as training feature for the classification algorithms.

It is possible to see that this measure works particularly well when used to distinguish antonym/synonym pairs pertaining to all word classes. **Nine** out of the **thirteen** classification algorithms we trained this way reported above the baseline values. **Six** of these

values pass the Chi-squared test, and so we can be sure they are statistically significant. Using PMI-Difference as a training feature, the ADTree algorithm, has a 62,16% accuracy in distinguishing antonyms from synonyms, thus is 12% above the 50% baseline.

Also, examining how the measure works in training classification algorithms for the different word-classes, we can see that, while it does not perform particularly well for nouns (even if nouns too can be classified using it), it works well with adjectives and verbs.

As showed in Chapter 5, PMI alone proved to be better suited for recognizing antonyms, than it is for recognizing synonyms. In fact, PMI characterize words that tend to occur together, rather than in similar contexts. This is particularly true for antonyms, while it is less true for synonyms, as proved by [Cruse, 1980]. Implementing the PMI-Difference measure, we minimized the cases in which the contrary is true, thus improving the performance of this measure to distinguish antonyms from synonyms.

Can the context types, influence how these measures perform? Scheible et al. [2013] hypothesize that only some word classes are useful for modeling the contextual differences between synonyms and antonyms adjectives. They investigate the influence of adjectives (ADJ), adverbs (ADV), verbs (VV), and nouns (NN) in their distributional model, predicting that the class of nouns will not be a useful indicator for distributional differences. This is motivated by Miller and Charles [1991]’s substitutability experiment, in which they claim that a noun phrase that can incorporate one adjective can also incorporate its antonym.

In a follow-up to the previous experiment, we evaluated the same WEKA classifier, trained using the same set of features, but we built the word contexts using, in turn, only adjectives, only names and only verbs. We do not test this approach on adjectives only (as done by Scheible et al. [2013]) but on the whole set of antonym/synonym test pairs.

Figure 6.10 shows that, when contexts are built using only adjectives as co-occurrence words, only PMI and PMI-Difference are able to distinguish antonyms from synonyms. This partially confirm the substitutability experiment in [Miller and Charles, 1991]. Since the majority of the data constituting our word pairs were nouns, it is reasonable to assume that, when their distributional vector are built using only adjectives as contexts, they would not only be really similar (the other feature suited for distinguish antonyms and synonyms here is Cosine-Difference) but also tend to occur in similar contexts (given that contexts are made only of adjectives). We know that PMI tends to better recognize words that occur in the same contexts, that is the reason why PMI and PMI-Difference are the features that better characterize these pair of words.

The use of noun contexts as features, as shown in Figure 6.11 outperforms the baselines in more scenarios than we would predict, while verbs do not perform as well (cf. Figure 6.12).

This contradicts the results obtained by Scheible et al. [2013], since their assumption was that nouns are the less useful word class for modelling the contextual differences

	2FeatCOSPmi	COS	PMI	COSDIF	PMIDIFF
ADTree	55,91%	45,16%	53,76%	47,78%	62,22%
BFTree	49,46%	45,16%	55,91%	52,22%	61,11%
DecisionStump	49,46%	53,76%	54,84%	52,22%	45,56%
FT	45,16%	50,54%	47,31%	43,33%	51,11%
J48	48,39%	50,54%	48,39%	44,44%	45,56%
J48graft	48,39%	50,54%	48,39%	44,44%	45,56%
LADTree	49,46%	44,09%	53,76%	50,00%	60,00%
LMT	56,99%	53,76%	60,22%	61,11%	60,00%
NBTree	48,39%	50,54%	48,39%	44,44%	45,56%
RandomForest	45,16%	49,46%	61,29%	47,78%	68,89%
RandomTree	48,39%	49,46%	61,29%	47,78%	68,89%
REPTree	54,84%	47,31%	55,91%	47,78%	50,00%
SimpleCart	48,39%	45,16%	53,76%	45,56%	65,56%

FIGURE 6.10: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction on antonyms/synonyms pairs which contexts were built using only adjectives as co-occurrence words - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

	2FeatCOSPmi	COS	PMI	COSDIF	PMIDIFF
ADTree	58,72%	54,13%	57,80%	55,56%	49,07%
BFTree	52,29%	62,39%	59,63%	51,85%	56,48%
DecisionStump	64,22%	64,22%	47,71%	49,07%	56,48%
FT	63,30%	61,47%	50,46%	60,19%	44,44%
J48	58,72%	60,55%	50,46%	48,15%	44,44%
J48graft	58,72%	60,55%	50,46%	48,15%	44,44%
LADTree	57,80%	55,96%	57,80%	54,63%	59,26%
LMT	53,21%	58,72%	54,13%	64,81%	58,33%
NBTree	61,47%	61,47%	50,46%	49,07%	44,44%
RandomForest	59,63%	58,72%	56,88%	58,33%	48,15%
RandomTree	52,29%	58,72%	56,88%	58,33%	48,15%
REPTree	54,13%	56,88%	47,71%	55,56%	53,70%
SimpleCart	61,47%	64,22%	58,72%	51,85%	56,48%

FIGURE 6.11: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction on antonyms/synonyms pairs which contexts were built using only nouns as co-occurrence words - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

	2FeatCOSPmi	COS	PMI	COSDIF	PMIDIFF
ADTree	62,50%	57,29%	41,67%	40,63%	55,21%
BFTree	60,42%	61,46%	47,92%	47,92%	60,42%
DecisionStump	52,08%	52,08%	45,83%	50,00%	54,17%
FT	43,75%	44,79%	47,92%	45,83%	44,79%
J48	45,83%	45,83%	47,92%	45,83%	46,88%
J48graft	45,83%	45,83%	47,92%	45,83%	46,88%
LADTree	58,33%	57,29%	50,00%	46,88%	58,33%
LMT	58,33%	58,33%	48,96%	60,42%	58,33%
NBTree	45,83%	45,83%	47,92%	45,83%	46,88%
RandomForest	57,29%	52,08%	46,88%	43,75%	70,83%
RandomTree	57,29%	52,08%	46,88%	43,75%	70,83%
REPTree	53,13%	58,33%	42,71%	51,04%	56,25%
SimpleCart	59,38%	58,33%	44,79%	47,92%	60,42%

FIGURE 6.12: Table reporting WEKA classifiers' performance at synonym/antonym distinction on antonyms/synonyms pairs which contexts were built using only verbs as co-occurrence words - the highlighted cells show the results that pass the Chi-squared test.

between synonyms and antonyms. Our results seem to tell us, instead, that nouns are the more useful word class to discriminate between synonyms and antonyms. So, why is it so?

First of all, our test pairs are not constituted of adjectives only, but also of nouns and verbs. Actually, only 92 pair out of the 300 total are constituted by adjectives, whilst 108 are nouns and 100 verbs, thus adjectives are the minority of our data. So, whilst nouns are not a useful word class to model contextual differences between adjectival antonyms and synonyms, they might be (and actually, these results prove that they are) useful to model contextual difference between antonym/synonym nouns and verbs.

Nouns relate to the semantic dimension denoted by the adjectives, they are in fact likely to co-occur with both the synonym (SYN) and the antonym (ANT) of a given target adjective (T), resulting in high mutual information values for both, but not necessarily expressing the potential semantic differences between them, as proved by the data in Figure 6.10. For example, assuming *tall* to be the target adjective, the noun *man* can co-occur with both *lanky* (SYN) and *short* (ANT). The set of verbs that co-occur with a given target word, are likely to be more similar to the set of verbs co-occurring with the synonyms of the target word, than to the sets of verbs co-occurring with the antonyms of the target word, resulting in higher similarity values for the pair of synonyms than for the pair of antonyms. We would for example assume that the set of verbs co-occurring with the target *unhappy* is more similar to the set of verbs co-occurring with its synonym *sad* (they both can co-occur with *cry* or *moan*) than to the sets of verbs co-occurring with the antonym *happy* (e.g. *smile* or *laugh*).

We can also assume that the set of names that co-occur with target names or target verbs, are more similar to the set of nouns co-occurring with the target’s synonyms than to the set of nouns co-occurring with the target’s antonyms. We would for example assume that the set of nouns co-occurring with the target *moan* is more similar to the set of nouns co-occurring with its synonym *whine* (they both can co-occur with *wheeze* or *complaint*) than to the sets of nouns co-occurring with the antonym *compliment* (e.g. *praise*). We know that this is not true for names co-occurring with adjectives.

Adjective targets are the minority of all the targets we have, so our results are obviously less influenced by the way nouns contexts model contextual differences between antonym/synonym adjectives, than they are by the way they model contextual differences between antonym/synonym nouns and verbs.

The hypothesis that not all word classes are useful for modeling the contextual differences between synonyms and antonyms is supported by these findings: the word space models built using collocate nouns appear to be the best discriminator of relations overall, outperforming the baseline with all the five measures we use as features. The outperforming values obtained with PMI-Difference as feature are, anyway, not statistically significant. The second-best class according to our statistical analysis is that of verbs, which outperforms the baseline using four out of five measure as features, not working only with PMI. The class of adjectives is the one that performs worst in this experiments, only (significantly) beating the baseline using three measures as features (PMI, Cosine-Difference and PMI-Difference). Despite the fact that the word space model built using collocate nouns is the one that works with the highest number of different training features, the one that provides the best overall result is the one built using verbs as co-occurrence words: when trained with RandomForest and RandomTree, it achieves a 70.83% precision that is 20.83 over the 50% baseline.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Work

The overall purpose of this research project was to study and explore the potential and limitations of the distributional approach with respect to lexical semantics.

The state of the art analysis we performed diffusely illustrated how distributional models present difficulties and interesting challenges with respect to the extraction and classification of the paradigmatic relations that exist between terms in a text, because of the particularities of these distributional relations. In particular, the relations we dealt with in this work are the those of *hyponymy/hypernymy* and of *antonymy*, because of all the peculiarities they present. The *hypernymy/hyponymy* relation, for example, can not be recognized using distributional methods because of its being inherently asymmetric, while the antonymy relations is problematic, because words linked by this relation tend to distribute themselves in texts like synonym words do.

In both cases, we proceeded with the analysis of the linguistic peculiarities of these relations, as well as with the analysis of the state of the art with respect to the use of distributional based approaches for the extraction and classification of paradigmatic relations.

Regarding the *hyponymy/hypernymy* relation, the analysis of its linguistic features has allowed us to identify its directionality. This made us clearly understand the reason why current distributional methods fail to recognize this relation. As explained in Chapter 3, semantic similarity is, in fact, typically computed using symmetric measures such as the Cosine. Assuming that a word meaning can be inferred from the contexts in which such word occurs, implies that verifying if two words are related one to the other, simply means to compute the similarity degree they share, that is to compute the number of semantic contexts they share. This assumption cannot be applied to the hyponymy relation, because this relation is, actually, intrinsically asymmetric.

We then investigated state-of-the-art asymmetric measures, commonly used in the study of lexical entailment (lexical implication). That same measures, however, have not proved to be able to discriminate between *co-hyponyms* terms and terms that share a

hypernymy/hyponymy relation. Analyzing how *hypernyms/hyponyms* behave, we found out that hypernyms are, at the extensional level, semantically broader than their hyponyms (the term *animal* refers to a broader range of entities than the term *dog*). By exploiting this property of hypernymy we implemented two new directional measures, specifically designed for the recognition of the *hypernymy/hyponymy* relation. The results we obtained were above those reported using state-of-the-art measure, not only for the identification of word pairs related by this relation, but also for the task of distinguish them from pair of words related by the *co-hyponymy* relation.

The problem with antonymy is more complex, since antonyms and synonyms tend to occur in the same contexts. To better understand this phenomenon we performed a preliminary study, aimed at describing antonyms and synonyms behavior in contexts. As described in Chapter 5, for each word pairs out of a list extracted using Amazon Mechanical Turk, we computed both the PMI (measures the degree of association between two words, thus indicating how frequently two words tend to occur in the same context) and the Cosine (measures the degree of similarity of the contexts in which two words occur) between the cooccurrence vectors representing the words.

The results of this experiment, confirmed the antonyms cooccurrence theory proposed by [Justeson and Katz \[1991\]](#). The fact that the PMI value is high for antonyms, implies that such words tend to appear together in the specified context, more often than by chance. From these results we can see that PMI values are high also for synonyms, implying that even synonyms tend to occur in the same contexts more often than chance, but this phenomenon is less strong for synonyms than it is for antonyms. The opposite happens with the Cosine, implying that synonyms tend to occur in similar contexts. Cosine values are lower for antonyms word pairs, because while it is definitely true that antonym words tend to occur in similar contexts, it happens way less than for synonyms.

We proceeded to develop a distributional measure to recognize and classify the antonymy relation.

We decided to repeat the experiment already conducted by [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#) and evaluate its performances on English, using different classification features. The goal of their research was to show that, using suitable features, antonyms and synonyms can be identified via a simple word space model, relying on contextual clues that govern the ability to distinguish the relations in context. We then decided to implement the findings described in Chapter 5 as features to train WEKA classification models. We used, as features, a combination of Cosine and PMI, as well as the Cosine-Difference implemented by [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#) and we introduced the PMI-difference. We confirmed that what [Scheible et al. \[2013\]](#) proved about German is true even for English. Our experiments demonstrated that synonyms and antonyms can be distinguished by means of a distributional word space model.

Our model achieves significant improvements over a 50% baseline. For example, using PMI and Cosine together, as feature, we achieved a 56,1% accuracy in classifying all

types of word pairs (nouns, verbs and adjectives), while using PMI-Difference as features, we achieved a 64,2% accuracy while classifying all type of pair of words. This compares favorably to previous approaches by Turney (2008), who achieved an improvement of 9.6% over his baseline, and Lin et al. (2003), whose method is assumed to only work for high-frequency antonyms. We not only proved that this method works for different Languages (German and English), but that it is promising for classifying and distinguishing synonyms and antonyms belonging to every part of speech (the experiment conducted by Scheible et al. [2013] aimed at classifying only antonym adjectives).

With this experiment, not only did we prove that the distributional hypothesis holds true even for antonyms (independently from their part of speech), but we also confirmed that not all word features are equally useful for modeling contextual differences between synonyms and antonyms. So we can speculate that the performance of distributional measures may be further improved by refining the method for feature selection.

Overall, we have proved that, despite their difficulties, Distributional Models (DSMs) are effective for extracting and classifying paradigmatic semantic relations.

With the work developed in the Thesis, we proved these methods to be useful even in dealing with those relations that, up to now, were considered unsuitable to be treated with distributional methods. One of the tasks to pursue as future research, will definitely be that of trying to improve these measures. Regarding the measures developed for the antonymy relation, another interesting aspect will be to address the possibility of using distributional measures not only for classifying antonyms, but also to distinguish gradable antonyms from not-gradable ones. Moreover, another aspect to investigate concerns the application of distributional methods to be used for the analysis of negative prefixes (like *a-*, *im-*, *dis-*) and antonyms that are generated with such prefixes (such as *possible-impossible*).

Appendix A

List of selected target words for the AMT Experiment

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
conjunct	poli1	freqMin	all
weightless	poli1	freqMin	all
knowledgeable	poli1	freqMed	all
uninsured	poli1	freqMed	all
able	poli1	freqMax	all
funded	poli1	freqMax	all
determined	poli2	freqMin	all
disadvantageous	poli2	freqMin	all
inconsolable	poli2	freqMin	all
unconfirmed	poli2	freqMin	all
unsupervised	poli2	freqMin	all
untypical	poli2	freqMin	all
endemic	poli2	freqMed	all
indispensable	poli2	freqMed	all
intentional	poli2	freqMed	all
mortal	poli2	freqMed	all
normative	poli2	freqMed	all
double	poli2	freqMax	all
gross	poli2	freqMax	all
partial	poli2	freqMax	all
vague	poli2	freqMax	all
excitable	poli3	freqMin	all
impure	poli3	freqMin	all
instructive	poli3	freqMin	all
provident	poli3	freqMin	all
recoverable	poli3	freqMin	all

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
thrifty	poli3	freqMin	all
unclean	poli3	freqMin	all
unfavorable	poli3	freqMin	all
unrefined	poli3	freqMin	all
unstructured	poli3	freqMin	all
concise	poli3	freqMed	all
immortal	poli3	freqMed	all
invalid	poli3	freqMed	all
proportionate	poli3	freqMed	all
thankful	poli3	freqMed	all
unaffected	poli3	freqMed	all
uneven	poli3	freqMed	all
unlawful	poli3	freqMed	all
unnoticed	poli3	freqMed	all
unsatisfactory	poli3	freqMed	all
deaf	poli3	freqMax	all
humble	poli3	freqMax	all
left	poli3	freqMax	all
manual	poli3	freqMax	all
maximum	poli3	freqMax	all
philosophical	poli3	freqMax	all
probable	poli3	freqMax	all
progressive	poli3	freqMax	all
representative	poli3	freqMax	all
unknown	poli3	freqMax	all
symphonic	poli1	freqMin	pert
uterine	poli1	freqMin	pert
nihilistic	poli1	freqMin	pert
despotic	poli1	freqMin	pert
geologic	poli1	freqMin	pert
taxonomic	poli1	freqMin	pert
corneal	poli1	freqMin	pert
oceanic	poli1	freqMin	pert
pneumatic	poli1	freqMin	pert
metropolitan	poli1	freqMed	pert
tribal	poli1	freqMed	pert

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
climatic	poli1	freqMed	pert
digestive	poli1	freqMed	pert
dimensional	poli1	freqMed	pert
fiscal	poli1	freqMed	pert
iconic	poli1	freqMed	pert
pathological	poli1	freqMed	pert
pulmonary	poli1	freqMed	pert
English	poli1	freqMax	pert
historic	poli1	freqMax	pert
photographic	poli1	freqMax	pert
postal	poli1	freqMax	pert
prime	poli1	freqMax	pert
psychiatric	poli1	freqMax	pert
psychological	poli1	freqMax	pert
quarterly	poli1	freqMax	pert
vital	poli1	freqMax	pert
arboreal	poli2	freqMin	pert
cyclonic	poli2	freqMin	pert
morphological	poli2	freqMin	pert
orbital	poli2	freqMin	pert
fatalistic	poli2	freqMin	pert
civic	poli2	freqMed	pert
poetic	poli2	freqMed	pert
modal	poli2	freqMed	pert
mystical	poli2	freqMed	pert
neural	poli2	freqMed	pert
terminal	poli2	freqMed	pert
chemical	poli2	freqMax	pert
biblical	poli2	freqMax	pert
disciplinary	poli2	freqMax	pert
linguistic	poli2	freqMax	pert
promotional	poli2	freqMax	pert
sensory	poli2	freqMax	pert
symbolic	poli2	freqMax	pert
associative	poli3	freqMin	pert
superficial	poli3	freqMed	pert
emotional	poli3	freqMax	pert

TABLE A.1: Adjective Target Words

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
knitwear	poli1	freqMin	artifact
maze	poli1	freqMed	artifact
trombone	poli1	freqMed	artifact
aircraft	poli1	freqMax	artifact
gauge	poli1	freqMax	artifact
arbor	poli2	freqMin	artifact
helm	poli2	freqMed	artifact
saloon	poli2	freqMed	artifact
shield	poli2	freqMax	artifact
stretcher	poli3	freqMin	artifact
compass	poli3	freqMed	artifact
coupling	poli3	freqMed	artifact
hedge	poli3	freqMax	artifact
naivety	poli1	freqMin	attribute
sexuality	poli1	freqMax	attribute
completeness	poli2	freqMed	attribute
accessibility	poli2	freqMax	attribute
halter	poli3	freqMin	attribute
saturation	poli3	freqMed	attribute
education	poli3	freqMax	attribute
fee	poli2	freqMax	possession
pocket	poli3	freqMax	shape
alleviation	poli2	freqMin	feeling
preparedness	poli1	freqMin	event
encore	poli1	freqMed	event
rivalry	poli1	freqMed	event
recreation	poli1	freqMax	event
thump	poli2	freqMin	event
stockade	poli2	freqMin	event
intercourse	poli2	freqMed	event
symbolism	poli2	freqMed	event
measurement	poli2	freqMax	event
training	poli2	freqMax	event
metamorphosis	poli3	freqMin	event
rendezvous	poli3	freqMin	event
admiration	poli3	freqMed	event
groove	poli3	freqMed	event
commitment	poli3	freqMax	event

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
workforce	poli1	freqMax	group
nationality	poli2	freqMax	group
phagocyte	poli1	freqMin	body
mantle	poli3	freqMed	body
rationale	poli1	freqMed	cognition
psychology	poli1	freqMax	cognition
audition	poli2	freqMed	cognition
distribution	poli3	freqMax	cognition
goodbye	poli1	freqMed	communication
rumour	poli1	freqMax	communication
parody	poli2	freqMed	communication
assertion	poli2	freqMax	communication
presentment	poli3	freqMin	communication
citation	poli3	freqMed	communication
matter	poli3	freqMax	communication
flask	poli2	freqMin	quantity
stone	poli3	freqMax	quantity
stout	poli2	freqMin	food
coriander	poli3	freqMin	food
punch	poli3	freqMed	food
blueberry	poli2	freqMin	plant
cole	poli2	freqMin	plant
barley	poli2	freqMed	plant
tomato	poli2	freqMax	plant
kiwi	poli3	freqMin	plant
snowball	poli3	freqMin	plant
cod	poli3	freqMed	plant
leaflet	poli3	freqMax	plant
contradiction	poli3	freqMax	relation
tallow	poli1	freqMin	substance
caffeine	poli1	freqMed	substance
iodine	poli2	freqMin	substance
arachnid	poli1	freqMin	animal
zebra	poli1	freqMin	animal
tsetse	poli1	freqMin	animal
omnivore	poli2	freqMin	animal
lobster	poli2	freqMed	animal
elephant	poli2	freqMax	animal
clam	poli3	freqMin	animal
skunk	poli3	freqMin	animal
crab	poli3	freqMed	animal
foot	poli3	freqMax	animal

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
velocity	poli1	freqMax	time
neutron	poli1	freqMed	object
planet	poli2	freqMax	object
sandstorm	poli1	freqMin	phenomenon
artist	poli1	freqMax	person
chap	poli3	freqMax	person
educator	poli1	freqMax	person
emperor	poli3	freqMed	person
innovator	poli1	freqMed	person
musician	poli2	freqMax	person
pastor	poli1	freqMed	person
cameraman	poli1	freqMin	person
shah	poli1	freqMin	person
caretaker	poli2	freqMed	person
slider	poli3	freqMin	person
wrecker	poli2	freqMin	person
cemetery	poli1	freqMax	location
township	poli1	freqMed	location
skyline	poli2	freqMed	location

TABLE A.2: Noun Target Words

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
implicate	poli1	freqMed	stative
consist	poli1	freqMax	stative
aggregate	poli2	freqMed	stative
inhabit	poli2	freqMax	stative
spiral	poli3	freqMed	stative
export	poli1	freqMax	possession
devolve	poli2	freqMed	possession
confer	poli2	freqMax	possession
bill	poli3	freqMed	possession
pine	poli1	freqMed	emotion
appall	poli2	freqMin	emotion
fancy	poli2	freqMed	emotion
uplift	poli3	freqMed	emotion
abdicate	poli1	freqMin	social
toil	poli1	freqMed	social
achieve	poli1	freqMax	social
zone	poli2	freqMin	social
awaken	poli2	freqMed	social
arrive	poli2	freqMax	social
disjoint	poli3	freqMin	social
court	poli3	freqMed	social
confine	poli3	freqMax	social
simper	poli1	freqMin	bodyfunction
emasculate	poli2	freqMin	bodyfunction
wink	poli3	freqMin	bodyfunction
trim	poli3	freqMed	bodyfunction
spring	poli3	freqMax	bodyfunction
misconstrue	poli1	freqMin	cognition
construe	poli1	freqMed	cognition
lump	poli2	freqMin	cognition
resonate	poli2	freqMed	cognition
diagnose	poli2	freqMax	cognition
contrast	poli3	freqMax	cognition
critique	poli1	freqMin	communication
pontificate	poli1	freqMin	communication
allude	poli1	freqMed	communication

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
whisper	poli1	freqMed	communication
alert	poli1	freqMax	communication
sum	poli1	freqMax	communication
pardon	poli2	freqMin	communication
deduce	poli2	freqMed	communication
disclose	poli2	freqMax	communication
document	poli2	freqMax	communication
screech	poli3	freqMin	communication
evidence	poli3	freqMed	communication
interpret	poli3	freqMax	communication
battle	poli1	freqMax	competition
arm	poli2	freqMax	competition
fight	poli3	freqMax	competition
scribe	poli1	freqMin	contact
swat	poli1	freqMin	contact
iron	poli1	freqMed	contact
amalgamate	poli1	freqMed	contact
constrict	poli2	freqMin	contact
lop	poli2	freqMin	contact
hone	poli2	freqMed	contact
park	poli2	freqMax	contact
fan	poli3	freqMin	contact
pyramid	poli3	freqMin	contact
inscribe	poli3	freqMed	contact
slam	poli3	freqMed	contact
kill	poli3	freqMax	contact
split	poli3	freqMax	contact
zigzag	poli1	freqMin	motion
redirect	poli1	freqMed	motion
tour	poli1	freqMax	motion
bop	poli2	freqMin	motion
journey	poli2	freqMed	motion
invade	poli2	freqMax	motion
bulge	poli3	freqMin	motion
whisk	poli3	freqMed	motion
make	poli3	freqMax	motion
strum	poli1	freqMin	perception
twinkle	poli2	freqMin	perception
nose	poli3	freqMin	perception
rub	poli3	freqMax	perception
tabulate	poli1	freqMin	creation
streamline	poli1	freqMed	creation
replicate	poli1	freqMax	creation
catalogue	poli2	freqMed	creation

Target Word	Polysemous Class	Frequency Class	Word Class
picture	poli2	freqMax	creation
furl	poli1	freqMin	change
accustom	poli1	freqMed	change
organise	poli1	freqMax	change
structure	poli1	freqMax	change
foist	poli2	freqMin	change
ink	poli2	freqMin	change
contaminate	poli2	freqMed	change
deteriorate	poli2	freqMed	change
edit	poli2	freqMax	change
immobilize	poli3	freqMin	change
invalidate	poli3	freqMin	change
corrupt	poli3	freqMed	change
polish	poli3	freqMed	change
try	poli3	freqMax	change
abuse	poli3	freqMax	change
power	poli1	freqMax	consumption
intoxicate	poli3	freqMin	consumption
boom	poli3	freqMin	weather

TABLE A.3: Verb Target Words

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